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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DGaaS	Data Governance as a Service
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020	Horizon 2020 - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions - Innovative Training Networks 2020
IRIT	Institut de Recherche en Informatique de Toulouse
JU	Jagiellonian University
LeADS	Legality Attentive Data Scientists
PU	Public
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
UL	University of Luxembourg
UPRC	University of Piraeus
UT3	Université Toulouse III
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WOPA	Working Paper
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable continues the work initiated in D3.2 and D5.1, where the ESRs of the LeADs project settled the foundation of a set of research questions in each Crossroad, linking the individual research statement of each ESR with the collective challenges of the project. We simulated a collection of contributions for a special issue of an international academic journal. This special issue serves as a showcase of the path to the publication of academic research. All the ESRs were involved in the reviewing process by anonymously reviewing at least one WOPA submitted by another group. Crossroads supervisors also served as reviewers, and they invited external reviewers to give external feedback for the WOPAs.

1. Introduction

This deliverable continues the work initiated in D3.2 and D5.1, where the ESRs of the LeADs project settled the foundation of a set of research questions in each Crossroad, link the individual research statement of each ESR with the collective challenges of the project. Building on the achievements and insights of the previous deliverable, this collection of scientific papers focuses on a finer level of detail, inspecting specific research topics that are further expanded and discussed in these Working Papers (WOPAs). Each WOPA is the result of the collaborative work of ESRs to produce a publishable set of documents.

Table 1 Wopas' titles and Authors

	Title	Authors
<i>Wopa 1</i>	The Flawed Foundations of Fair Machine Learning	Robert Lee Poe (SSSA) and Soumia Zohra El Mestari (UL)
<i>Wopa 2</i>	Contribution to data minimization for personal data and trade secret.	Qifan Yang (SSSA) and Cristian Lepore (UT3)
<i>Wopa 3</i>	Measuring Data Access and Re-use in the European Legal Framework for Data, from the GDPR to the Proposed Data Act: the Case of Vehicle Data	Tommaso Crepax (SSSA), Mitisha Gaur (SSSA) and Barbara da Rosa Lazarotto (VUB)
<i>Wopa 4</i>	Data Collaboratives with the Use of Decentralised Learning - an Interdisciplinary Perspective on Data Governance	Maciej Krzysztof Zuziak (CNR), Onntje Hinrichs (VUB) and Aizhan Abdrassulova (JU)
<i>Wopa 5</i>	Transparency and Relevancy of Direct-To-Consumer Genetic Testing Privacy and Consent Policies in the EU	Xengie Doan (UL), Fatma Sümeyra Dogan (JU) and Arianna Rossi (UL)
<i>Wopa 6</i>	From Data Governance by Design to Data Governance as a Service	Armend Duzha (UPRC), Christos Magkos (UPRC) and Louis Sahi (UT3)

As evidence of the quality of the research put in action for each WOPA, we simulated a collection of contributions for a special issue of an international academic journal. This special issue serves as a showcase of the path to the publication of academic research.

Through meticulous peer review, the papers have undergone rigorous evaluation, validating their quality and scholarly merit. All the ESRs were involved in the reviewing process by anonymously reviewing at least one WOPA submitted by another group. Crossroads supervisors also served as reviewers, and they invited external reviewers to give external feedback for the WOPAs.

Several WOPAs have been published in international and external venues. This recognition speaks to the caliber of research conducted by the ESRs and the relevance of their contributions to the broader academic

and professional community.

Figure 1 Crossroads structure

2. The content

The collaborative efforts of the ESRs within the LeADs project have fostered a confluence of vision and expertise. Drawing upon diverse backgrounds and interdisciplinary perspectives, these researchers have synergized their knowledge to explore the complex interplay of data science and legal issues. Their contributions, culminating in this collection of scientific papers, exemplify the project's commitment to knowledge generation and its potential for meaningful impact on society.

This collection of scientific papers represents a deep exploration of the intersection of legal issues and data science. The culmination of research, analysis, and review, these papers address pertinent challenges and propose innovative solutions in the dynamic landscape of data governance and privacy.

2.1 Topics and focuses.

The first paper dissects the current fair machine learning paradigm, exposing fallacious reasoning and questionable practices that lead to biased outcomes. Through a comprehensive evaluation, the authors establish the existence of a trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similarity, emphasizing the need for an objective understanding of fairness. By providing a proof-of-concept evaluation, this paper aims to guide researchers and designers toward equitable, fair machine learning approaches.

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In the second paper, the focus shifts to personal data and trade secrets, exploring their complex intersection. The authors propose a high-quality GDPR-compliant teaching model, designed to protect personal data and trade secrets while ensuring adherence to privacy regulations. With a comparative analysis of the European framework for electronic transactions, this work provides valuable insights for researchers and practitioners seeking to strike a balance between data utility and privacy preservation.

The third paper ventures into the realm of data access and transparency within the European legal framework, with a specific focus on vehicle data. Through meticulous evaluation, the authors identify areas where GDPR transparency requirements may not be adequately met, raising considerations for policymakers and stakeholders. By shedding light on potential gaps, this research aims to empower citizens and organizations with the tools to make informed decisions concerning data access and utilization.

Moving into the realm of genetic testing, the fourth paper addresses the privacy implications of direct-to-consumer genetic testing. Highlighting concerns about non-transparent data sharing and privacy policies, the authors propose user-centered improvements to enhance transparency and user understanding. By advocating for informed consent and risk disclosure, this research fosters a more ethical and privacy-aware genetic testing landscape.

The fifth paper introduces a novel concept, Data Governance as a Service (DGaaS), that contributes to data management practices. Enabling organizations to align with their vision, goals, and legal requirements, DGaaS offers a flexible and scalable framework. By enhancing data governance through user-centric and contextual privacy suggestions, this paper charts a path toward smarter decision-making and improved data management.

The final paper advocates for data collaboratives, leveraging decentralized learning techniques to achieve greater data control and accessibility while preserving privacy. This interdisciplinary exploration demonstrates how innovative technological solutions can shape a more balanced and privacy-conscious data ecosystem. By fostering collaboration and embracing progressive data governance approaches, this research advances the realization of policy goals, particularly in the smart city and healthcare sectors.

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, the wealth of knowledge and innovative research presented in this collection of scientific papers shows the improvement of competences and expertise of the ESRs of the LeADs project. All ESRs have delved into the intricate interplay between data science and legal issues, unearthing new insights and proposing groundbreaking solutions.

The results of this endeavour can be attributed to the cross-fertilization fostered within LeADs Crossroads. Each working team, encompassing ESRs from multiple Crossroads, has served as a melting pot of diverse perspectives, experiences, and expertise. This unique amalgamation of experiences has enriched the research process, culminating in a collection that mixes different disciplines.

This simulated special issue of the journal serves as a proof of concept of the competences of our ESRs. Through rigorous peer review and thoughtful curation, this compilation reflects the high standards set by the LeADs project. The remaining part of the deliverable integrates the contributions of the WOPAs.

ANNEXES

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The Flawed Foundations of Fair Machine Learning

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Abstract

The definition and implementation of fairness in automated decisions has been extensively studied by the research community. Yet, there hides fallacious reasoning, misleading assertions, and questionable practices at the foundations of the current fair machine learning paradigm. Those flaws are the result of a failure to understand that the trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes exists as independent, external constraint rather than as a subjective manifestation as has been commonly argued. First, we explain that there is only one conception of fairness present in the fair machine learning literature: group similarity of outcomes based on a sensitive attribute where the similarity benefits an underprivileged group. Second, we show that there is, in fact, a trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes in any data setting where group disparities exist, and that the trade-off presents an existential threat to the equitable, fair machine learning approach. Third, we introduce a proof-of-concept evaluation to aid researchers and designers in understanding the relationship between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes. Finally, suggestions for future work aimed at data scientists, legal scholars, and data ethicists that utilize the conceptual and experimental framework described throughout this article are provided.*

Keywords: Accuracy, Equity, Merit, Automated Decisions, Fair Machine Learning, Algorithmic Fairness, Algorithmic Discrimination

*This article is a preprint submitted to the Minds and Machines Special Issue on the (Un)fairness of AI on May 31st, 2023.

1 Introduction

Automated decision-making systems are increasingly being used to render high-impact decisions regarding human beings. All the while, notorious accounts of algorithmic discrimination and algorithmic unfairness have been reported by news outlets over the past decade. Due to the many concerns about the potential societal impacts of machine learning, governments are beginning to put forward policy positions and draft regulations. In the AI Bill of Rights, the White House states that automated decisions should be designed and deployed to achieve equitable outcomes. In Europe, the AI Act states that automated decisions should not perpetuate historic patterns of discrimination or create new forms of disparate impact. Right now, policy-makers and regulators are relying heavily on the fair machine learning community to present solutions. However, a unipolar conception of fairness is being represented and advocated for by the fair machine learning community, which does not reflect the same breadth of opinion that exists in wider society.¹

To a limited extent, researchers in the field have understood that they had not happened upon an empty field (of research) but instead a garden that has been fostered, cared for, and in some cases ignored for a very long time. Perspectives from many domains have been incorporated into the literature: legal doctrines like disparate impact (Barocas and Selbst, 2016), fair distribution philosophies dealing with egalitarianism and merit (Arif Khan et al, 2022), socio-technical critiques of technological solutionism (Cooper et al, 2021; Selbst et al, 2019), and concepts from feminist communications and data science like the myth of objectivity and meritocracy (Geburu, 2020; D’Ignazio and Klein, 2020). Due to the multidisciplinary nature of the field, a sufficient framework for understanding the technical limitations and implications of machine learning combined with the goals and implications of “fairness” in between and within related disciplines has yet to be fully realized. This is partly due to the fact that most articles published from the machine learning community are difficult for those in the humanities or legal communities to understand and vice versa. Thus researchers at the crossroads of fairness, discrimination, and machine learning are to some degree speaking past one another. Throughout the entire article, each audience is kept in mind and essential terminology is defined.

In section 2, we argue that the common categorization of fairness in the literature misleading implies that there are three competing conceptions of fairness, when in fact there is one: fairness defined as the similarity in outcomes between groups when that similarity acts in the benefit of underprivileged groups. In section 3, we argue that the trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes is an independent external constraint on fair machine learning, rather than a mere framing problem as is commonly argued. And, we address some misconceptions about the implications of that trade-off found in the literature. In section 3.1, we carefully address a specific example, the highly influential view proposed by Friedler et al. in (Friedler et al, 2016, 2021). Finally, in section 4, we will introduce a proof-of-concept evaluation to aid researchers and designers in understanding the relationship between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes.

¹Problems related to the fair distribution of finite resources are continually addressed in politics, law, and culture with varying views about how best to address those problems.

2 Fair Machine Learning Means Group Similarity in Outcomes

In the fairness literature, metrics are commonly split into three categories: group fairness, causal fairness, and individual fairness. This categorization misleadingly implies that there are three distinguishable conceptions of fairness at play in the fair machine learning literature, when in reality there is but one conception of fairness technically defined in metrics: fairness defined as group similarity in outcomes based on a given sensitive attribute. The mantra of group fairness is that groups should be treated equally or at least similarly. The mantra of group fairness is, however, misleading because "fairness" defined as group similarity ensures the *similarity of outcomes*, not solely the *similarity of treatment*.

Causal fairness shares the same conception of fairness as group fairness and is only different in so far as a different set of techniques are used to achieve that goal (Kilbertus et al, 2017; Kusner et al, 2017; Prost et al, 2022; Castelnovo et al, 2022). The same is true of individual fairness, even though individual fairness has incessantly been offered as an opposing conception of fairness to group fairness definitions with its own mantra of similar individuals should be treated similarly. The maxim of similar treatment that individual fairness embodies is an Aristotelian principle of consistency (Binns, 2020). The individual fairness definition states that there should be consistency between the relevant features of two different persons and their respective outcomes in comparison to one another. More specifically, the similarity between the features of two individuals (measured as a distance) should be preserved between their respective labels.²

Note that the principle of consistency, defined as distance between spaces, *could* be used to detect whether there exists inconsistencies between the relevant features and ground truth of the sample, as well as when there exists inconsistencies between the sample and the outcomes. For instance, the inconsistencies could be seen as an indicator of unreliable data collection processes where data was incorrectly reported, or that the data sample is missing a set of uncollected features that could explain the current inconsistency. We emphasize, however, that the individual fairness metric itself is not concerned with determining the representativeness of the sample nor with determining how well the outcomes generalize to a target population.

Individual fairness defines *fairness* as a comparison of geometric distances. Once distance is defined, individuals can be compared and inconsistencies (unfairness) can be rectified. However, the distance must be defined, and defining a distance presupposes prior knowledge about "fairness." In other words, the principle of consistency is *empty* (Schauer, 2018), and so requires a substantive notion of fairness to define what makes similar cases similar (i.e. the distance). Thus, there is a circularity in the proposition that individual fairness is a definition of fairness. It may be that the principle of consistency is a necessary requirement for fairness to be achieved, but consistency or similarity alone is not sufficient to constitute an independent notion of fairness (Fleisher, 2021). Some advocates of the individual fairness approach argue that substantive notions of fairness need be defined by domain experts (Dwork et al, 2012; Friedler et al, 2021), others argue that the distance can be learned (Mukherjee

²Labels or target variables refer to the variable to be predicted by the machine learning algorithm.

et al, 2020), while still others argue that the group fairness metrics should fill the void (Fleisher, 2021). In any case, individual fairness should be understood as a tool to implement fairness once defined, rather than as a conception of fairness in and of itself.

Thus, there is but one conception of fairness *technically* defined in fairness metrics: group similarity in outcomes based on a given sensitive attribute. To build machine learning models that produce outcomes that are group similar, the first step is to define a measure or metric that reflects a notion of acceptable group dissimilarity. There exists a “zoo” of these metrics (Castelnuovo et al, 2022, p.2) that define the acceptability of group dissimilarity differently using notions of statistical independence, sufficiency, and separation. A number of surveys and reviews on the taxonomy of metrics and interventions have been published (Mehrabi et al, 2021; Pessach and Shmueli, 2022; Castelnuovo et al, 2022; Carey and Wu, 2023).

Once a metric of acceptable group dissimilarity is chosen, one of the three following strategies can be adopted: (1) pre-processing the input data to remove, alter, or curate the underlying data that lead to group dissimilarities (Feldman et al, 2015a; Zhang et al, 2017; Hajian and Domingo-Ferrer, 2013), (2) in-processing where the model is constrained to produce group similar outcomes by modifying the learning algorithm’s objective functions (Berk et al, 2017; Zafar et al, 2017); and/or (3) post-processing the output of the model, rather than changing anything about the sample or hypothesis assumptions, by using an algorithm based on a function that detects potential group dissimilarities and adjusts the labels accordingly (Kim et al, 2019).

As many have observed, requiring similarity of outcomes can either act in the benefit or detriment of underprivileged groups depending on the decision context (Selbst et al, 2019; Cooper et al, 2021; Carey and Wu, 2023)—where privileged and underprivileged groups are identified by a given legal or moral code. To achieve an equitable outcome, rather than a merely equal or similar one, researchers argue that the choice of whether or not to use fair machine learning or of which metric defining the acceptability of group dissimilarity is to be used, must be context specific so that similarity in outcomes only act in the detriment of privileged groups and in the favor of underprivileged groups. Justifications for such a definition of fairness in machine learning are inspired by (1) legal doctrines like disparate impact and affirmative action in the United States or indirect discrimination and positive action in the European Union (Barocas and Selbst, 2016; Thomas et al, 2021; Wachter et al, 2021), (2) critical race and gender studies which find disparities that disfavor underprivileged groups to constitute *de facto* discrimination (Gebru, 2020; D’Ignazio and Klein, 2020), (3) or distribution philosophies based on moral arguments for the acceptance of equity-based systems and the rejection of merit-based systems (Arif Khan et al, 2022) (or a combination of these justifications (Carey and Wu, 2023)). In the end, fairness in machine learning generated decisions is defined as *similarity in outcomes between groups when that similarity acts in the benefit of underprivileged groups to the detriment of privileged groups*.

3 The Trade-Off Between Statistically Accurate Outcomes and Group Similar Outcomes

Statistically accurate outcomes are the result of a robust model trained on a representative sample. Group dissimilarity in outcomes can be the result of (1) an unrepresentative sample and/or non-generalizable assumptions (inaccuracies), (2) group dissimilarities existing in the target population that are reflected in a representative sample and carried into the outcomes by a robust model (accuracies), or (3) unrepresentative sampling and/or hypothesis formulations that add *additional* group dissimilarity beyond the group dissimilarity already present in the target population (both). The goal of traditional machine learning is to produce statistically accurate outcomes. The traditional machine learning approach encompasses a number of techniques and practices to remove inaccuracies including those that would produce more group dissimilarity than that which is present in a target population. A target population can have imbalanced group sizes, contain anomalies like the Simpson’s paradox, have sub-group validation problems, and so on.³ In other words, differences between groups in the target population can result in group dissimilar outcomes. Wrongheadedly, many fall into the trap of thinking that dissimilarities between groups in outcomes *must* be the result of inaccuracies. Statistically inaccurate outcomes can certainly either *exaggerate* or *underestimate* the disparities which exist in a target population, but the solution to statistically inaccurate outcomes is to create a more representative sample and/or robust model.

Researchers should confront the fact that the goal of fair machine learning *is not* to increase the representativeness of a data sample or the robustness of a model. In fact the goal is the opposite. Decisions made on a representative sample have the potential to reflect the target population in the model outcomes, and those outcomes would have the same disparities between groups that exist in the target population. In other words, if the relevant (for the task) base-rate parameters of the target population result in a demographic parity of 0.4, that demographic parity would be the limit of fairness in a model that generalizes to the target population. The realization that there may be differences between groups in the world is a painful one. However, to reject that there exists differences between groups is to reject the existence of “unfairness.” In other words, if there were no differences between groups in the target population, there would be no differences in outcomes for the equitable, fair machine learning approach to address.

To illustrate how difficult it has been for the fair machine learning community to internalize this point, reflect for a moment on the difference in the use of the word “bias” between traditional machine learning and fair machine learning. Traditionally, bias is defined as a deviation from the true value of a parameter or variable. In fair machine learning, bias is defined as a deviation from group similarity (Pessach and Shmueli, 2022; Mehrabi et al, 2021; Chen et al, 2018; Castelnovo et al, 2022). When the true value of a parameter leads to group dissimilarity in outcomes, the *true value* is dubbed biased. When the word “bias” in the sense of deviation from group similarity

³A sub group validity problem occurs when a particular observable characteristic is valid for some groups but not for others.

(normative) is used to reject a true value of a parameter in statistics, the is-ought fallacy is often committed. The is-ought fallacy occurs when one reaches a normative conclusion based solely on descriptive (factual) premises. In this case, by rejecting the true statistical value based on normative concerns, the descriptive aspects of statistics are being mixed with the prescriptive aspects of morality. This terminological mix-up often results in the fallacy of equivocation, which occurs when a keyword of an argument is used with more than one meaning, leading to misinterpretation. Disguising normative judgements in the language of statistics only creates confusion.

While philosophers might best understand the thrust of the argument through examples of the is-ought fallacy, jurists might best understand by comparing the Separation Thesis found in legal positivism to the differentiation made here (Hart, 1957). The separation thesis insists on the separation between (1) what the law *is* and (2) what the law *ought* to be. Here, there is a separation between what *is* (accuracy) and what *ought* to be (fair). In other words, the traditional machine learning approach has been a descriptive effort and the fair machine learning approach has been a prescriptive effort.

Data scientists can only ever follow best practices (under epistemological limitations) when sampling from the target population, including ensuring a sample with a relatively small standard deviation, adequate size, random sampling, and so on. Following best practices will, admittedly, never constitute a proof of representativeness. However, the lack of proof does not mean that a data scientist is unfamiliar with the target population or that they are unable to estimate group disparity. The reader may be tempted, in response to the arguments made throughout this section, to doubt whether awareness of group dissimilarity in a target population is practically possible. Note though, if awareness of group dissimilarity is not practically possible, then there would be no evidence of group dissimilarity—which many researchers in the field use as a proxy for *de facto* discrimination—and so no *justification* for the disparate impact legal doctrine.

The trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes is obvious. The logical conclusion of the trade-off is also obvious: where there exists the greatest need for the equitable, fair machine learning approach (i.e. data settings that contain large group disparities), machine learning itself is most useless.⁴ As the connection between the model outcomes and the target population becomes more tenuous to become less dissimilar amongst sub-groups, the use of statistical learning becomes harder to justify. In other words, the more the outcome is already known (manually coded), the less need there is for a data driven approach. A script or quota could fulfill the same purpose. Thus, the trade-off presents an existential threat to the field.

The response to the threat of the trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes has been to deny its existence by arguing that the trade-off is a subjective manifestation rather than an independently existing constraint (Cooper et al, 2021; Selbst et al, 2019; Friedler et al, 2016, 2021). For instance, authors in (Cooper et al, 2021) argue that the conflict between “accuracy” and “fairness” is the result of framing the trade-off as an optimization problem. Their argument rests on

⁴Where “need” is defined by a normative judgement.

a causal fallacy. Recognizing the “inherent conflict” between statically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes in a data setting which contains group disparities and then optimizing between those competing interests cannot be the *cause* of differences between subgroups of a target population that exist independently in that data setting. The realization that there are group disparities in a target population is the realization that there are differences between groups. The question of what causes differences between groups is beyond the scope of this article. However, to whatever extent subgroups of a target population are different, there will be differences in group outcomes no matter how they are measured. Changing the framing or values that guide an automated procedure (for instance by changing the definition or measurement of economic success) would simply lead to a different group skew in outcomes. Disparities in outcomes are inherent external constraints on any categorization or *classification* of a world filled with group disparities.⁵ The only way to remove disparities in outcomes between groups is to not recognize the differences between groups in the target population, and thus between individuals as well (i.e. to alter the data sample or its processing to reflect a false world.)

It is true that the trade-off is most commonly formulated as an optimization problem. For example, the lower bound of this trade-off has been estimated via proof (Gouic et al, 2020; Zhao and Gordon, 2022). And Authors in (Menon and Williamson, 2018) have proven that in the case of a binary classifier it will be asymptotically possible to maximize both accuracy and fairness simultaneously only if the sensitive attribute and the target label are perfectly independent. On the other extreme, if the sensitive attribute is highly correlated with the target variable then it’s only possible to maximize either the accuracy or the fairness at the same time. In between those two extremes, the trade off is determined by the strength of the correlation between the target and the sensitive attribute. As the (Menon and Williamson, 2018) proof states, if the sensitive attributes and the target variable are perfectly independent of one another, the more generalizable the model is, the more group parity will be present.

Some authors use this fact to argue that accuracy and fairness are complimentary (Cooper et al, 2021; Dutta et al, 2020; Hellman, 2019); even going so far as to state that the “fairness-accuracy trade-off formulation also forecloses the very reasonable possibility that accuracy is generally in accord with fairness” (Cooper et al, 2021, p.4). Statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes are not generally in accord. While it is true that under certain conditions statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes are complimentary, the reliance on that truth to minimize the importance of the trade-off is highly misleading. Statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes can *only* be complimentary in a data setting which is strictly group similar (necessarily defined as group parity in the context of perfect independence). If the data setting is already strictly group similar, there is no need for the fair machine learning approach. Fair machine learning is only required in those instances where unacceptable group dissimilarity exists, and in those instances, statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes will always be uncomplimentary (i.e. the sensitive attributes and target variable will be correlated.)

⁵Let us not forget that grouping based on sensitive attributes defined by the protected classes in non-discrimination law are not the only grouping that could be argued morally irrelevant.

Others observe that, in practice, constraining outcomes to meet an acceptable notion of group dissimilarity can sometimes increase accuracy (Wick et al, 2019). Again, the observation is correct but can lead to misunderstandings. When the use of a fairness constraint increases the accuracy, either the sensitive feature and target variable are independent (and so see the above argument) or the data sample was so unrepresentative that enforcing group similarity increased the accuracy by happenstance. And, that increase in accuracy by happenstance could never go beyond the group similarity present in the target population without decreasing the generalizability of the model.

Authors in (Dutta et al, 2020) suggest that horizontal data collection can alleviate the trade-off.⁶ There, the authors are falling into the trap of thinking that group dissimilarity in outcomes is the result of inaccuracies; in this case, an incomplete feature selection process where all the relevant-for-the-task features are not collected. Other researchers suggest that the trade-off can be alleviated by the targeted, vertical collection of data, where the model is trained on an enlarged dataset that serves the objective of group parity (Chen et al, 2018; Bakker et al, 2020). This will indeed improve group similarity. However, it will also result in a sample of data that is far from being representative of the real world distribution. Moreover, calculating the accuracy on an unrepresentative test set is misleading since the generalizability of the model when deployed may be compromised by this practice. In other words, these practices curate a data sample that satisfies group similarity, and then test the model on a test set which has also been curated. Furthermore, if the purpose of collecting data is not to use the target population as an external constraint, but instead to satisfy a notion of acceptable group dissimilarity, then there is no need to waste time and money collecting more data—simply use the existing processing techniques listed in section 2 to achieve the same result.

Throughout this section, we have highlighted fallacies, misleading assertions, and questionable practices that result from the failure to understand the relationship between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes, and we’ve explained that a failure to understand that relationship often leads researchers to insist that group dissimilarities must be the result of inaccuracies. In the following subsection, we will, to the best of our ability, faithfully describe one of the most highly influential examples of this phenomenon, the model of automated decision-making procedures presented by Friedler et al. in (Friedler et al, 2016, 2021). We believe their view requires careful attention.

3.1 Critiques of the Model of Friedler et al.

The model of Friedler et al. is based on two distinctions (Friedler et al, 2021, p.138-9). First, they make a distinction between the *feature space*, which contains information about people, and the *decision space*, which contains the decisions made about people based on the feature space. In other words, a decision making procedure takes inputs from the feature space and returns outputs in the decision space. Second, they make a distinction between the *construct space* and the *observed space*. The construct space consists of idealized representations about people and the decisions regarding them;

⁶Horizontal data collection is the collection of more features.

whereas the observed space contains only the kind of information that is observable and the decisions that are the result of those observations. These two distinctions allow for the introduction of four combination spaces they call: (1) the *construct feature space* which contains feature constructs like intelligence or frugality (CFS); (2) the *observed feature space* which contains the observable or measurable features that are used as proxies for the construct features like IQ or debt-to-credit ratio (OFS); (3) the *construct decision space* which contains decision constructs like college success or creditworthiness (CDS); and (4) the *observed decision space* which contains decision proxies like college GPA or loan default (ODS).

The observed spaces are knowable, and the construct spaces are unknowable (Friedler et al, 2016, p.3-6). More specifically, the distances between individuals and groups in the observable spaces are knowable and in the construct spaces unknowable. According to Friedler et al., two worldviews emerge from the picture once construct spaces are introduced: (1) the What You See Is What You Yet (WYSIWYG) worldview and (2) the Structural Bias worldview. The WYSIWYG worldview assumes that the observed features and decisions are essentially the same as the construct features and decisions; or, in other words, that the observations approximate the constructs (loan default approximates creditworthiness). Whereas, the Structural Bias (SB) worldview wishes to *find* and define “structural bias” and “non-discrimination” in the transformations between these two spaces. More specifically, they wish to find group skew, defined as more distortion between groups than there is within groups in the transformations between an “unobservable” space and an observable space (Friedler et al, 2016, p.7). “[T]o address this *complication* . . . assumptions must be introduced about the points in the construct space, or the mapping between the construct space and observed space, or both” [emphasis added] (Friedler et al, 2016, p.6). “Structural bias” is defined as group skew between the unknowable construct and knowable observed spaces in general (Friedler et al, 2016, p.7), and “non-discrimination” is specifically defined as an acceptable amount of group skew between the unknowable construct spaces and the knowable observed decision space (Friedler et al, 2016, p.8).

Set aside, for a moment, these unknowable construct spaces and focus on their definition of “direct discrimination.” Under the SB worldview, direct discrimination is defined as the existence of group skew between the knowable, observed feature and decision spaces (Friedler et al, 2016, p.8), which means that direct discrimination can only be the result of a model that produces outcomes that are not representative of its sample. In other words, direct discrimination is the result of statistically inaccurate outcomes rather than the result of group disparities present in a representative sample (i.e. a problem the traditional machine learning approach can address). Note that in all the definitions listed above, group skew is the quotient of “between group distance” and “within group distance”. In other words, to say that there exists group skew is to say that groups are different.

Again, structural bias and non-discrimination are the result of group skew in the transformations between the construct and observed spaces. Unlike direct discrimination, group skew in both of these cases is based on unknowable, assumed mappings. It is in this way, according to Friedler et al., that observational processes of an automated decision procedure cause group skew (Friedler et al, 2021, p.140). We wish to

temper their assertion: if (1) the assumption that a construct space must exist and (2) unknowable knowledge about that space is granted, then the conclusion that observational processes cause group skew can be reached. At first glance, it may appear that the statement that observational processes cause group skew is supporting the “framing” argument rejected previously; however, the argument there was that the framing of the relationship between accuracy and fairness as an optimization problem is the cause of the trade-off between the two.

There is also a difference between: (1) *group skew* that is the result of more distortion between groups than there is within groups in the transformations between construct and observed spaces and (2) *group dissimilarity* that is the result of group disparities in a representative sample. In other words, group skew that results from observational approximations of constructs does not cause group dissimilarity in outcomes *generally* but only ever *additionally* in a data setting that contains group disparities (i.e., those settings where fair machine learning is required). Group skew defined in the SB worldview is addressed, not by producing group similar outcomes in an “unfair” data setting, but instead by selecting observations which accurately (or “correctly”) approximate constructs. However, the approximation is subject to unknowable information and rests on the assumption that decision-makers only ever want to satisfy abstract standards like creditworthiness or academic success rather than specific standards like loan default or college GPA. It is in no way clear to us that the introduction of unknowable construct spaces with definitions that mimic legal terminology produce anything more than confusion.

Regardless, the definitions of structural bias and non-discrimination, developed by Friedler et al., are irrelevant for the equitable, fair machine learning approach. Here is yet another instance of researchers falling into the trap of thinking that group dissimilarity has to be the result of inaccuracies, this time ethereal inaccuracies. As stated previously, the goal of fair machine learning approach is not to produce statistically accurate outcomes nor ethereally “correct” outcomes, but instead to produce equitable, group similar outcomes in data settings that would otherwise produce inequities. In reality, their model does not address issues of equity in automated decision-making systems.

4 Evaluation of the Trade-off

This section provides a numerical proof-of-concept evaluation of the trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes. First, the used data samples and pre-processing techniques will be described and then the results will be discussed.

4.1 Experimental Setup

In order to study this trade-off, we synthetically generate three datasets with group disparities where the probability to receive a favourable outcome is not equal for all groups. Each dataset is composed of 3 variables: group (G) representing a dependant and sensitive, binary attribute, value (V) the insensitive variable and outcome (Y) as a binary label or targeted value which has two values 0 and 1 for the unfavourable and

favourable outcomes respectively. Table 1 describes the characteristics of each dataset. For fairness metrics, we use three group fairness metrics, namely: disparate impact, equalized odds, and statistical parity. In our experiment, we used pre-processing techniques to remove group skew, and we show how these techniques affect the statistical accuracy of outcomes in a data sample where the skew is large. We can clearly see that the resulting distributions will be very different than the original distribution of data. Group skew is computed as the ratio between the between-groups variance and the within-groups variance:

$$GS = \frac{\sigma_B^2}{\sigma_W^2}$$

where:

$$\sigma_B^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{N_g} N_i * (\mu_i - \bar{X})^2$$

$$\sigma_W^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n (x_{ij} - \mu_i)^2$$

Where GS denotes group skew, σ_B^2 is the between group variance and σ_W^2 is the in-between group variance. N_g is the total number of groups and n is the number of observations in each group i . Between group Variation σ_B^2 is the total variation between each group mean μ_i and the overall mean \bar{X} . Within-group variation is the total variation in the individual values in each group x_{ij} and their group mean μ_i .

Dataset	group	size	mean	std	Pr(Y=1)	statistical parity	Disparate impact	group skew
D1	1	10000	5.5	0.6	0.7	-0.20	0.72	2356.41
	0	10000	6	0.4	0.5			
D2	1	20000	5.5	0.3	0.8	-0.59	0.25	2332.88
	0	9000	6	0.6	0.2			
D3	1	10000	5.5	0.6	0.5	0.01	1.02	2790.86
	0	10000	6	0.3	0.5			

Table 1 Overall overview about the used datasets

The Disparate Impact Remover: to remove disparate impact (we note DIR (repair value)) we use the pre-processing algorithm proposed by Feldman et al. (Feldman et al, 2015b) with 3 different repair levels 0.3, 0.5 and 1.0 to control the degree of overlap of the distributions of the two groups, results in table 2.

The Equalised Odds Remover: to remove the effect of equalised odds we experimented using 3 different algorithms namely: (1) reweighing algorithm (Kamiran and Calders, 2012), (2) Fair Balance (Yu et al, 2021) and FairBalanceVariant (Yu et al, 2021), results in table 3.

Dataset	DIR (0.3)	DIR (0.5)	DIR (1.0)
D1	1268.29	710.91	2.30
D2	1257.20	705.24	3.51
D3	1632.39	958.50	4.73

Table 2 Group skew results when using Disparate Impact Remover (DIR)

Dataset	Reweighting algorithm	FairBalance algorithm	FairBalanceVariant algorithm
D1	369.52	167.19	167.19
D2	325.51	144.88	144.88
D3	2720.71	2717.75	2717.75

Table 3 Group skew results when using Equalised Odds removers

The Statistical Disparity Remover: in order to remove the statistical disparity from the data, we used the algorithm proposed by Zemel et al. (Zemel et al, 2013), results can be found in table 4.

Fig. 1 Histograms of the different datasets and their transformed versions obtained when running Disparate Impact Remover (Feldman et al, 2015b) with repair values of 0.3 , 0.5 and 1.0

Dataset	Statistical Disparity Remover
D1	693.32
D2	693.32
D3	1020.47

Table 4 Group skew results when using Statistical Disparity Remover

Fig. 2 Histograms of the different datasets and their transformed versions obtained when running the different Equalised Odds removers ((1) reweighing algorithm (Kamiran and Calders, 2012), (2) Fair Balance (Yu et al, 2021) and FairBalanceVariant (Yu et al, 2021))

Fig. 3 Histograms of the different datasets and their transformed versions obtained when running the Statistical Parity Remover (Zemel et al, 2013).

4.2 Discussion

The Disparate Impact Remover (see table 2) with a repair scale of 1.0 achieved the lowest group skew for the three data samples by ensuring a complete overlap between the groups. The positive point about these techniques is that they preserve the ranking between groups which ensures less distortion in the transformed versions of the data (see figure 1). However, this technique results in the highest group skew differences between the transformed sample and the original which suggests that the outcomes will not be statistically accurate (see section 3), assuming that the original sample is representative.

For the equalised odds removers, we find that the FairBalance algorithm and its variance (Yu et al, 2021) achieved a low group skew on the three datasets. Specifically for this set of techniques, we observe that they change drastically the shape of the resulting distribution (see figure 2) except for dataset 3. For D3, the resulting transformed D3 is less distorted compared to the transformed versions of D1 or D2. D3 contained an initial group skew but the sample was perfectly balanced since the size of each group is equal and the probability of receiving a favourable outcome was equal for each group. This is an indication that the equalised odds removers are sensitive towards group imbalances. The more imbalanced the groups, the bigger the distortion in the transformed dataset.

The Statistical Disparity Remover (Zemel et al, 2013) scored the worst among all techniques in decreasing the group skew except for the data sample 3, D3 where it scored better than all the equalised odds removers.

The distortions that can be observed in the transformed samples when using pre-processing techniques in Figures 1, 2 and 3 show an illustration of how much can a fairness guided learning process reflect a different reality, models receiving and tested on those transformed samples may suffer from a lack of generalizability where the test results are not reliable.

5 Conclusion

First, we hope to have shown that the fair machine learning community represents and advocates for a single conception of fairness, defined as equity in automated decisions. We suspect that the unipolar conception of fairness in the fair machine learning literature is due to the fact that the traditional machine learning approach has the potential to satisfy a meritocratic conception but can never satisfy an equitable conception in a data setting that contains group disparities. Our concern is that by only defining fairness as equity in machine learning, the community may be leading policy-makers and regulators to believe that *fairness* is absent in automated decisions without the use of the equitable, fair machine learning approach. Note that, throughout this article, we have neither advocated for nor disparaged any particular conception. We hope for an expansion in how fairness is conceived in machine learning, so that the literature can capture the same kind of diversity in opinion that is present in the wider societal discourse.

Second, we hope to have shown that the rejection of the trade-off between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes as an independent, external constraint has resulted in fallacious reasoning, misleading assertions, and/or questionable practices. Researchers should confront the reality that equitable outcomes require the introduction of inaccuracies. Admitting that there exists a trade-off does not mean that outcomes should not be equitable. We argue, though, that the research community should be more straightforward about what is being sacrificed in the name of equity. Obfuscating the nature of that sacrifice, for instance by redefining the term “bias” in machine learning, could be misleading policy-makers and regulators. As was once wisely said, “There are no solutions. There are only trade-offs” (Sowell, 1987).

To those ends and in an effort to foster transparency, we introduced experimental results to aid designers of automated decision-making systems in understanding the relationship between statistically accurate outcomes and group similar outcomes. Future work could use the conceptual and experimental understanding provided throughout this article in a variety of relevant disciplines: (1) data scientists might build a toolkit that would allow researchers and designers of automated decision procedures to incorporate goals and compromises into the machine learning pipeline, where primary and secondary goals are represented by chosen fairness metrics and distributions; (2) legal scholars might realize that, perhaps, affirmative action and positive action are the applicable legal doctrines rather than disparate impact and indirect discrimination, because fair machine learning techniques alter (act on), the decision process itself (i.e., the implementation of fair machine learning metrics is positive discrimination and so it must be determined whether that positive discrimination constitutes lawful or unlawful discrimination in a given jurisdiction and decision context);

and (3) data ethicists might offer an alternative proxy for (un)fairness in the machine learning pipeline, other than group similarity (skew as the quotient of between-group and in-group distances), that could allow for a conception of fairness that is not based on equity.

CRedit author statement. **Robert Lee Poe:** Conceptualization, Writing Original Draft, Formal Analysis, Resources, Investigation, Writing Review and Edits.

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Contribution to data minimization for personal data and trade secret

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Abstract. Personal data is a resource with significant potential economic value and has a natural and intrinsic “bloodline” tied to personal privacy. The control over personal data, at the intersection of personal privacy and commercial assets, shapes market competition to slight advantages for market dominants. The data minimization from the General Data Protection Regulation as a general benchmark builds bridges between personal data and trade secrets and imprisons excessive breaches against personal data by trade secrets. Still, the legal and technical framework for achieving this target is left open. This work contribution is multifold. (1) It explores the intersection and relationship between personal data and trade secrets, specifically whether personal data can be considered a trade secret beyond personal data protection and minimization. (2) A high-quality GDPR-compliant teaching model is proposed to protect personal data and trade secrets with legal and technical data minimization considerations. (3) It presents the parallelisms between the European framework for electronic transactions and the introduced model. In the long run, we aim to provide citizens with tools to understand and mitigate privacy issues.

1 Introduction

The internet-based digital market was initially envisioned as an expansive global marketplace where market players (including individuals and companies) could challenge many competitors with minimal transaction costs [87]. The harsh reality has proven that a fair playing ground for all participants in the market is idealistic and utopian, as the emergence of “behemoths” bred by the digital economy has been witnessed over the past two decades.

The digital economy’s distinctive market structures and effects are perceived as breeding grounds for big platforms, and the current status and structure of the digital market are the pre-determined consequence of data and the legal or de facto rules surrounding data. In 2020, the Bundesgerichtshof confirmed Facebook’s abuse of dominance over data collection, highlighting the correlation between competitive advantage in the social media market and the ways to obtain users’ data. The court’s decision stated: “[...] Facebook’s access to a considerably larger database increases the already distinct “lock-in effects”. In addition, this larger database enhances the possibilities to finance the social

network using the profits generated from advertising contracts which also depend on the scope and quality of the data available [17]. The review of data generation reveals that the most valuable data is produced by users (so-called prosumers). Big technology companies' expanding control of users' data creates an insurmountable entry barrier for market competition in this area [85]. As Srnicek mentions, "Simply put, we should consider data to be the raw material that must be extracted, and the activities of users to be the natural source of this raw material" [114].

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person" is personal data.¹ Data subjects are entitled to paramount but vital rights, like the right to access, rectification, erasure, object, restriction of processing, and data portability.² These personal data rights collectively shape data subjects' restrictions on disclosure, use, processing, and storage of personal data and indirectly determine the data flow and sharing level. Based on this, personal data from users is essential to personal privacy protection and generates a valuable source of competitive advantages for internet companies. The Facebook case is not isolated because all Internet companies face the balance between personal data protection and their commercial activities and how to achieve a legal "monopoly" of valuable information beyond personal data protection through investment, innovation, etc. For this reason, the contribution of this paper is two-fold: first, we clarify whether personal data can be considered a trade secret beyond data minimization. Then, we explore a data minimization platform that helps protect personal data.

The paper structure is as follows. The next Section kickstarts the discussion on the criteria for personal data and trade secrets, as well as the challenges arising from technological developments in the two. We illustrate how different techniques affect the border between personal data and non-personal data and how the digitization of information shocks the keeping of trade secrets. Section III frames the principle of data minimization as a sanitary cordon for personal data and recalls the establishment of the data minimization principle in different regions and the current technical solutions to achieve it. In this Section, we discuss how personal data, or information generated from personal data, can legally constitute a trade secret beyond personal data protection from the perspective of data minimization. Section IV presents more detailed standard references based on the data minimization principle from the GDPR and proposes a privacy-by-design tool for data minimization considering legal pillars and the existing European data minimization platforms. We conclude with closing remarks and avenues for future research.

¹ See Article 4 (1) of the GDPR.

² See Article 15, Article 16, Article 17, Article 18, Article 20, Article 21 of the GDPR.

2 Personal Data vs Trade Secrets

In the age of big data, privacy and trade secrets are generally considered two separate legal systems protecting confidential information [49]: The former concerns information privacy law, dealing with "the regulation, storing, and use of personal information of individuals" [49]. When privacy is considered as a form of control over self-information, the right to personal data can be expressed as "informational self-determination" [18], i.e., "control the terms under which personal information [...] acquired, disclosed, and used" [95]. Thus, personal data protection is included in the information privacy protection system.³ Trade secret system protects valuable information unknown to the public, and the holder of such information undertakes reasonable precautions to keep secrecy [49]. It aims to promote innovations in the long term by legally accepting the de facto monopoly through both property and liability rules. With the digitalization of information, personal data not only forms part of individuals' personalities but also may play a crucial role in business operations. It also entails that potential conflicts might arise due to the overlap of two intangible and legal rights conferred by personal data protection and trade secret regulations. In this complex situation of potential conflicts between legal "monopolies," it is crucial to clarify the criteria for personal data and trade secrets in terms of the legislative framework and evaluate to which extent existing criteria enable trade secrets based on personal data to be established. That happens despite, for instance, the EU trade secrets directive envisaging some coordination rules with the GDPR [75].

2.1 Personal Data

The classification criteria adopted by the GDPR for personal data and non-personal data, a widely accepted division, is whether data contains "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject')".⁴ It firstly implies that personal data point to natural persons and not to other subjects [41]. From the legal perspective, the right to personal data is a fundamental right in the EU without a commodity nature; hence the right subject

³ With the evolution of ICT, privacy has been expanding in scope, breadth, and width, and the explication of "privacy" in cyberspace is significantly more complex and blurred. The key to privacy in the information society is the ability to control the use of own personal information by others, i.e. the right to self-determination of personal information [60, 112]. Privacy has significant and complex offshoots, touching different areas and stemming from the traditional privacy theory. Kokolakis classified privacy into three main aspects: "(a) territorial privacy, which is concerned with the physical area surrounding a person, (b) privacy of a person, which refers to the protection of a person against undue interference, such as physical search, and (c) informational privacy, which is concerned with controlling whether and how personal data can be gathered, stored, processed, and disseminated" [65]. In this sense, personal data can be covered in the broader context of privacy, as control means keeping your privacy secret and sharing the information you want.

⁴ See Article 4 (1) of the GDPR.

can only be a natural person, not a corporation, social organization, or other entities. Non-personal information is not protected by personal data protection law. Yet different legal rules apply to them. For instance, the Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for free-flowing non-personal data in the European Union provides their general legal framework. Still, it is potentially subject to regulation under intellectual property law or other legal areas, like the EU Database Directive 96/9/EC, the Digital Services Act (DSA), and the DMA. Secondly, personal data has an identifiable nature relating to a natural person.⁵ An identifiable natural person can be identified directly or indirectly. In other words, the link between data and natural persons can either be already identified or can be directly or indirectly identifiable. For instance, data such as names and ID numbers are typically directly identifiable personal data, while browsing history, purchase history, or comments do not appear to have a direct tie to natural persons. However, the scale of behavioral data offers the possibility of building bridges between such data and natural persons through data profiling or data fusion. Such Links established via data analysis can be considered indirectly identifiable. Direct identification is generally considered more secure and accurate than indirect identification, as it provides a straight connection to an individual. Indirect identification can still be helpful in many scenarios, such as when direct identification is not available or would be overly invasive.

The de-identification of data is only partially equal to the complete loss of identifiability. The scope of de-identification varies from region to region, which makes de-identification to be a tricky concept that must be discussed in a specific context. At its most basic level, all accept that de-identification is a data processing method dealing with identifiers to disassociate the processed information from the specific personal information subject. Yet, the requirement for re-identification is at the heart of the debate. The California Consumer Privacy Act of 2018 (CCPA), Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (HIPAA), and Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) impose stricter requirements for preventing re-identification, like assessing the possibility of re-identification in conjunction with "other reasonably available information"⁶ and "information that cannot reasonably be used to infer informa-

⁵ See *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR and Hartmut Eifert*, Joined Cases C-92/09 and C-93/09, [2010] ECR I-11063 (ECLI:EU:C:2010:662), at para. 52-3; *Amann v. Switzerland* [GC], Application no. 27798/95, ECHR 2000-II (Grand Chamber), at para. 65.

⁶ See Article 99.31 (b) of the FERPA: "De-identified records and information. An educational agency or institution, or a party that has received education records or information from education records under this part, may release the records or information without the consent required by § 99.30 after the removal of all personally identifiable information provided that the educational agency or institution or other party has made a reasonable determination that a student's identity is not personally identifiable, whether through single or multiple releases, and taking into account other reasonably available information."

tion about, or otherwise be linked to”⁷. In China, Information security technology—Personal information (PI) security specification (GB/T 35273-2020) and the PIPL describes de-identification as a “technical process that makes personal information subjects unidentifiable or unassociated without the help of additional information”⁸ or “processing personal information to make it impossible to identify specific natural persons in the absence of the support of additional information”⁹. De-identification, compared to anonymization, does not destroy the association between personal data and data subjects but only overwrites or replaces the identification of data subjects by technical ways such as encryption, pseudonyms, and Hash functions. If a third party (even if not authorized) can access external information to assist, re-identifying de-identified personal information is still potential. Based on divergent definitions, we generally think that de-identified personal data is excluded from personal data in the US,¹⁰ whereas personal data protection laws still regulate de-identified or pseudonymized personal data in the EU and China because such data can still be reconstructed for identification, despite being more secure than unidentified data [100]. The GDPR and the PIPL also stipulate the adoption of encryption, de-identification, or other security technical measures as information processors’ legal obligations to ensure the security of personal information processing activities and prevent the leakage, falsification, or loss of personal information.

Anonymization is designed to safeguard individuals’ privacy and make possible the re-use of data. Standard techniques for anonymization include but are not restricted to replacing identifying information with pseudonyms (pseudonymization) [77] or a generic value (data masking) [81], reducing the precision by grouping it (data aggregation) [63], modifying elements (data deletion), or removing it (data perturbation) [61] and hide information through encryption. A straightforward example is masking the last four digits of a Social Security number to avoid being recognized. Anonymity techniques represented by K-Anonymity [63] were often believed to reach or approximate current anonymization standards set by law. The K-anonymity model groups a few records together, so it is challenging to link a record to a specific individual [105]. Thus, for an attacker is hard to pinpoint and compromise an individual’s data. Besides K-Anonymity, L-diversity, T-closeness, and Personalized privacy preservation are also designed to further enhance the security of sensitive attributes. However, the current model created for data anonymization has defects; even putatively anonymized or de-identified data may still be exposed [48,89,93,101]. Although the legal definitions and criteria are fixed and clear, technologies are dynamic. So in the real world, the border of personal data is blurred. Also, the trade-off for higher security

⁷ See Article 1798.140.(m) of the CCPA: “‘Deidentified’ means information that cannot reasonably be used to infer information about, or otherwise be linked to”.

⁸ See the definition of “de-identification” in Article 3.15 of Chinese GB/T 35273-2020: “technical process that makes PI Subjects unidentifiable or unassociated without the help of additional information.”

⁹ See Article 73 (3) of the PIPL.

¹⁰ See Article 1798.140. (v)(3) of the CCPA: “‘Personal information’ does not include consumer information that is deidentified or aggregate consumer information.”

of anonymized data is more restrictions and lower data availability [35]. Thus, even technologies designed to protect personal data, such as differential privacy technologies, still face a risk-utility trade-off [40]. The notions of personal data and anonymity are strictly correlated. The EDPB has repeatedly clarified its position concerning their interplay. For instance, in its answer to Katja Becker, referring to research data, it stated, “the EDPB underlines that, where the research requires the processing of personal data, and it complies with the relevant provisions of the GDPR, it can be possible to process personal data without resorting to anonymization. The EDPB recalls that anonymization refers to “the use of a set of techniques to remove the ability to link the data with an identified or identifiable natural person against any ‘reasonable’ effort.” To perform a “reasonability test,” the objective aspects (e.g., time and technical means) and contextual elements (e.g., nature and volume of the data) must be taken into account. Suppose personal data can be re-identified using a reasonable effort. In that case, the data cannot be considered anonymous in the meaning of the GDPR; therefore, it would fall within the scope of the GDPR.” [10]. From this analysis, a dynamic notion emerges: data are not permanently personal or anonymous.

2.2 Trade Secrets

In the digital economy, users and their data frequently yield remarkable competitive advantages as a vital company resource. To gain from their investment in users and their data, companies have no interest in sharing the information obtained from their users because they will lose their “privileges” once this data is public or disclosed. But it is easy to guess that companies with precious user data will always be keen to take measures to protect their de facto secrecy. Indeed, in a long-term concern to foster innovation and market competition, modern legal systems allow companies with some legal freedom to exclude others from accessing their valuable knowledge [9, 73], i.e., trade secrets. The study by the European Commission found that trade secrets are particularly important for technology-based startups, with a majority of SMEs in the EU relying on trade secrets to protect their confidential information since trade secrets can help them maintain their competitive advantage and attract investment [29].

In 2016, the European Parliament and the European Council adopted the Directive (EU) 2016/943 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use, and disclosure (the Directive (EU) 2016/943). According to Article 2 of the Directive (EU) 2016/943, a trade secret is information that meets three criteria: “(a) it is secret in the sense that it is not, as a body or in the precise configuration and assembly of its components, generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the circles that normally deal with the kind of information in question; (b) it has commercial value because it is secret; (c) it has been subject to reasonable steps under the circumstances, by the person lawfully in control of the information, to keep it secret.” Article 4, Recital 1, Recital 3, and Recital 14 of the Directive (EU) 2016/943, outline an extensive scope of trade secret objects,

covering valuable know-how (manufacturing processes, formulas, recipes, etc.) as well as business information (business methods and strategies, etc.) contained in “any documents, objects, materials, substances or electronic files”,¹¹ to protect investments, innovation, and intellectual capital. As long as these three criteria are met, almost any information can be protected as a trade secret. There are no requirements about the vehicle or expression of information. Trade secret law is designed to focus on the meaning and content of data.

Moreover, Article 4 of the Directive (EU) 2016/943 further elaborates on the scope and nature of trade secrets by constructing protection standards and liability rules for trade secrets. Based on the infringement and process of trade secrets, the provision divides them into three behaviors (acquisition, use, and disclosure) and two phases (direct and indirect infringement), where the purchase of trade secrets is a prerequisite for trade secrets’ use and disclosure and secondary or indirect infringement is based on the consequence of the first or direct infringement.¹²

Except for the infringement of trade secret use and disclosure caused by prior unlawful conduct, the other scenario is the breach of a pre-existing duty of confidentiality, non-disclosure, or limitation of use.¹³ When it comes to indirect infringement, Articles 4(4) and (5) stress that third parties (indirect infringers) must know - that they knew or ought to have known.¹⁴ In terms of the criteria and scope of trade secret protection, the Directive (EU) 2016/943 is not intended to create a property system or confer absolute rights to trade secret holders, or even to protect secret information per se, but is only aimed at prohibiting infringements and dishonest business practices from fostering competition and innovation in the marketplace [64]. Given that the exclusivity of trade secrets is not absolute, the reverse engineering and parallel innovation ought to be guaranteed [29], and to avoid over-protection, Article 5 of the Directive (EU) 2016/943 lists the special cases excluded from trade secret protection, of which the right to freedom of information is set out.¹⁵

¹¹ See Article 4 (2)(a) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943.

¹² See Article 4 (2) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943; see Article 4 (3)(a) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943: “The use or disclosure of a trade secret shall be considered unlawful whenever carried out, without the consent of the trade secret holder, by a person who is found to meet any of the following conditions: (a) having acquired the trade secret unlawfully;...”.

¹³ See Article 4 (3)(b) and Article 4 (3)(c) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943: “The use or disclosure of a trade secret shall be considered unlawful whenever carried out, without the consent of the trade secret holder, by a person who is found to meet any of the following conditions: (b) being in breach of a confidentiality agreement or any other duty not to disclose the trade secret; (c) being in breach of a contractual or any other duty to limit the use of the trade secret.”.

¹⁴ See Article 4 (4) and Article 4 (5) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943.

¹⁵ See Article 5(a) and Article 4 (5) of the Directive (EU) 2016/943.

2.3 Balancing in conflict: Personal Data vs Trade Secrets

Upon contemplation of the above definitions and criteria for personal data and trade secrets, personal user information is the basic and commercially valuable resource of Internet businesses, both as a form of protection for their user groups and as a ground for business strategies [19], which seems to be protected as trade secrets from some traditional views [75]. At the same time, the GDPR grants the data subject some protective rights to control their data exclusively, like the right to access, rectification, erasure, object, restriction of processing, and data portability¹⁶. Where two protective rights conflict over the same content, investigating how personal data can be eligible as trade secrets is necessary.

In traditional markets and business models, companies have usually been the de facto controllers and absolute holders of trade secrets as well as their components, and they can take technical or managerial measures or create confidentiality obligations to ensure the information stays confidential. However, the data subject legally has exclusive or partial control over personal data, even if it has become their primary object or material. According to the different links between personal data and the data subjects, three types can be distinguished: raw personal data provided by the data subjects, factual personal data derived from reality, and predictive personal data [74].

Raw personal data refers to personal data recorded or generated by the data subject, the original owner or creator who provides it to the company. The company only plays the role of a recipient or recorder and no longer conducts any other (creative) acts in obtaining personal data. The meaning of data "provided" to the company is not limited to personal data provided directly to the company by the data subject but also includes personal data provided indirectly from observation of the data subject's activities, in line with the "provide" meaning of data portability [53]. In this sense, the nature of "raw personal data" decides that the data subjects have a close and strong link to such personal data. The scope of raw personal data "provided" by the data subjects is consistent with that of "the personal data concerning him or her, which he or she has provided to a controller" in Article 20(1) of the GDPR. Hence, the data subjects have the right to data portability of the raw personal data.

Factual personal data derived from reality is true or highly probable descriptive personal information based on the raw personal data provided by the data subjects, which can depict both internalizing and externalizing facts, such as health conditions, preferences, etc. Companies create factual personal data by mainly combining it, aggregating and profiling raw personal data, and whether the created personal data by companies is real at that time or will be real or probably be true in future [74]. Such descriptive personal data is rooted in the raw personal data and naturally points to the data subjects. The data subjects take some rights to control it as granted, like the right to access and erasure.¹⁷

Predictive personal data describes possibly true personal data, relying on personal data and other data or knowledge. Firstly, predictive personal data

¹⁶ See Article 15, Article 16, Article 17, Article 18, Article 20, Article 21 of the GDPR.

¹⁷ See Article 15, Article 17 of the GDPR.

still needs to fall within the scope of personal data. Not all predictive data generated from data sources containing personal data are predictive personal data. The predictive non-personal data is not in our focus. Secondly, factual personal data is real or probably true, but predictive personal data is possibly true, which is an uncertain estimate [74]. Thirdly, other data or knowledge is essential to contribute to the predictive personal data, while the production of factual personal data relies heavily on personal data. Compared to the former two, the link between predictive personal data and the data subjects is somewhat diluted by other factors.

The process of collecting, using, and processing personal data in a marketplace is not one-time but repetitive. For further analysis, we can roughly divide the first process of personal data into three stages: the data collection stage (where data is collected into a dataset or database), the method processing stage (where methods are used to extract, handle, process, reprocess, etc.), and the result analysis stage (where the final information is obtained based on the previous two stages). To qualify as a trade secret, personal data or any information derived from personal data must fulfil the three requirements mentioned in 2.2: Firstly, it must be secret, not be generally known or readily accessible. Secondly, personal data or any information generated from personal data must hold commercial value, whether actual or potential. Lastly, the trade secrets holder must undertake reasonable measures to ensure its confidentiality.

At the first personal data collection stage, the main sources of personal data to companies are the raw personal data provided by the data subjects, including public personal data and raw personal data from individual users. Public personal data is extremely open and accessible, and the data subjects still have some control over it [54]. It is almost impossible for companies to build a closed secret, at least in the collection process. For the raw personal data from individual users, the data subjects can provide their personal data to companies or ask the previous controller to transmit those data to another controller.¹⁸ Although such raw personal data is less open than public personal data, the data subject's rights to access, erasure, and data portability remain to provide considerable freedom of data flowing. And in a perfectly competitive market, where countless providers of products or services offer similar services or products, the data subject is free to choose and change the provider. In this case, personal data provided by the data subjects is not publicly available but can be considered completely free-flowing to a certain extent. Based on this, we can assume that each company in this market has a database (l_n) for this processing. L represents all personal data on the market, so $L = l_1 \cup l_2 \cup l_3 \cdots \cup l_n$ is the set of all databases. Given the openness and flow of raw personal data provided by the data subjects, Company A and Company B in the same market may have similar or even the same initial factor pools if they have similar user groups. Thus, $l_1 \approx l_2 \approx l_3 \approx \cdots \approx l_n$ in a perfectly competitive market.

The methods of collecting personal data may be diverse, and the confidential collection method with commercial value qualifies as a trade secret, but it

¹⁸ See Article 20 of the GDPR.

does not affect the non-confidentiality of the basic element “personal data.” According to Article 7(1) from the Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (the Database Directive), the investments in acquiring, collecting, and assembling existing elements for a database can create a new database right. This kind of protection stems from investment, so its protection neither extends to generated data or intellectual creations nor covers pure facts or data. It only prohibits the “extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or a substantial part, evaluated qualitatively and/or quantitatively, of the contents of that database”.¹⁹ Thus, creating a personal database may give rise to a database right, and the collection methods may constitute a trade secret, but personal data itself, as an underlying element of flows, is almost impossible to meet the confidentiality requirement. In addition, if the particular collection method can result in a database that is significantly different from other databases and affords “a demonstrable competitive advantage”²⁰, this database may also constitute a trade secret.

The method processing stage focuses on how to process personal data. Similarly, any processing method can also constitute a trade secret, provided that it satisfies the criteria of being secret, commercially valuable, and protected by reasonable measures, including generative models, cryptographic (de-identified or anonymized) models, data minimization models, analytical models, predictive models, etc. And there is no fixed term for a trade secret - protection will last as long as the secret is kept. The processing of personal data can be seen as a complex function (f_i). All functions establishing connections between input and output can form a set ($F = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n\}$). When every function within this set exhibits similar relationships between its input and output, discovering this relationship will unveil all functions belonging to the class. Consequently, this method poses a potential vulnerability for compromising the secrecy of the set. If the functions within this set can generate distinct correlations between input and output independently, it becomes more feasible to ensure the preservation of its confidentiality.

After processing, the company obtains newly generated data based on the function and database, i.e. $f_i(l_n)$, ($f_i \in F, l_n \in L$). The new personal data generated by companies concerns factual personal data and predictive personal data. From the view of keeping secret, if the significant contribution to the final output is provided by the essential factor “personal data”, in other words, if most available methods can extract the same or highly similar information from an open personal data set, then the method or model does not provide sufficient secrecy for the final content, at least not to the extent required for a trade secret.

¹⁹ See Article 7(1) of the Database Directive: “Member States shall provide for a right for the maker of a database which shows that there has been qualitatively and/or quantitatively a substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents to prevent extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or of a substantial part, evaluated qualitatively and/or quantitatively, of the contents of that database.”

²⁰ See *Enterprise Leasing Co. of Phoenix v. Ehmke*, 3 P.3d 1064, 1069-70 (Ariz. Ct. App. 1999).

Factual personal data generated by companies basically falls into this case. It does not mean that all factual personal data cannot be a trade secret. If the data subject and the company can achieve confidentiality by agreement or others, then factual personal data may also become a trade secret. Predictive personal data relies on personal data and other data or knowledge. And other data or knowledge essentially contributes to the predictive personal data. Following this, if the processing method is unique and secret, the result should normally be confidential. The confidential information will qualify as a trade secret as long as it has commercial value and is treated with reasonable confidentiality.

Assuming that the databases of market participants are similar and dynamic, depending on the preferences of data subjects, the data processing process can be summarized as follows:

Definition 1. $f_i(l_n) = R, \quad (f_i \in F, l_n \in L)$

where $F = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n\}$ is the set of function f_i , $L = l_1 \cup l_2 \cup l_3 \dots \cup l_n$ is the set of all databases, l_n is a subset of L , $f_i(l_n)$ is a function (the method used for processing) that takes a subset l_n and extracts information, and R is the expected information. Given that $l_1 \approx l_2 \approx l_3 \approx \dots \approx l_n$, R is largely dependent on f_i .

As discussed, with respect to data subject rights and data flows, trade secrets do not seek to protect information obtained by simply piling up personal data. Even if the trade secret can be established, it is frequently destroyed quickly by the data subject's rights to access, erasure, object, and data portability²¹. In conclusion, establishing trade secrets beyond personal data protection does not rely on the volume of personal data, but rather on the uniqueness of their personal data collection, processing techniques, methods, or models.

²¹ The right of access, right to access, rectification, erasure, object, restriction of processing, and data portability collectively shape data subjects' restrictions on disclosure, use, processing, and storage of personal data, and indirectly determine the level of data flow and sharing in particular data portability. Data portability is sometimes treated as an extension or special form of access rights [47, 72], but more often it is a standalone right, seeking to tackle a totally different issue related to data flows and market efficiency/competition [32, 71]. The nature of data portability is to resolve the Arrow information paradox and achieve effective use of personal data by identifying the right, instead of creating an exclusive right like ownership, and it can "be best defined by reference to the data sharing and reuse that it facilitates" [47]. The right to data portability with "encouragement for interoperability" introduces "competitive pressure in the digital markets where combined with various principles of the GDPR (e.g. data minimization) as well as other rights (e.g. right to erasure)" [19]. The breadth and complexity of data portability rights can create overlaps with trade secrets, which can negatively affect the establishment of trade secrets.

3 Data minimization: a cordon sanitaire starting from personal data protection

Data minimization is a practice used by organizations to restrict the amount of personal data (refer to Section 2.1 for a definition of personal data) to what is strictly necessary to accomplish a specific purpose. This principle is driven by the extensive data collection conducted by organizations over the last decade. It aims to increase the customer’s trust, mitigate risks of data breaches and bolster business reputation [118]. It also led governments and businesses to enforce privacy-enhancing frameworks that consider privacy-by-design as a foundational aspect. Above all, in the EU legal framework, it is a key legally enforceable principle in personal data protection. This section frames the state-of-the-art of legal and technical frameworks for data minimization.

3.1 Control and sharing from personal data protection: data minimization

Personal data protection has its root in privacy with the intervention of technologies. Although it is not an absolute and inalienable right to traditional privacy, it is inherently about the borderlines between self and others, between private and shared, or public [76]. As a milestone for personal data protection, the GDPR came into force on May 2018 to replace the old EU Data Protection Directive and provides guidelines for collecting, processing, and storing personal data with the aim of giving individuals control over their personal information. It is built on six principles: data purpose, proportionality, data retention, subject’s rights, security, and privacy-by-design. Data minimization is a core element of at least two principles: privacy-by-design and security.

In the GDPR, the data minimization principle is a direct consequence of the data purpose principle; it stipulates that the data collected must be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the purposes for which they are processed”²². the purposes of the processing must be specific²³ and specified²⁴. To clarify, a purpose must be specific enough to inform the processing, i.e., it must be possible to demonstrate that processing operations are necessary for the stated purpose²⁵. In addition, a purpose does not have to define directly the data subjects or categories of data subjects, data types, and recipients or categories of recipients²⁶ but must be specific enough to determine them before commencing the processing²⁷. The controller must be able to demonstrate that the envisaged data are necessary for achieving the purpose²⁸.

²² Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR.

²³ See, e.g., Article 6(1)(a) and Article 25(2) of the GDPR.

²⁴ See, e.g., Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR.

²⁵ Article 5(1)(b), Article. 25(2) and Article. 35(7) of the GDPR.

²⁶ Article 4(7) of the GDPR: “ (...) determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data (...)”

²⁷ Article 13(1) and Article 14(1) of the GDPR.

²⁸ See Article 5(1)(c), Article 25(2), and Article 35(7)(b) of the GDPR.

In other words, once the (explicit and legitimate) purposes of the processing have been determined, the personal data collected must not be superfluous, unnecessary, or superabundant concerning the same purposes. It has also been referred to as the “principle of necessity.”

It safeguards personal privacy within the broader framework of individual freedom and dignity and sets a cordon sanitaire for each step taken toward personal data. In processing personal data, data minimization requires companies to adopt appropriate measures, with consideration of volume, type, and security of personal data, to ensure that the processing of personal data is proportionate to the purpose. In addition to limiting the collection and processing of personal data, data minimization also involves a risk-based approach to personal data protection. Companies need to assess the risks associated with collecting and processing personal data and take steps to mitigate those risks. This may include implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure personal data security and conducting regular data protection impact assessments (DPIAs)²⁹. Taking such steps can reduce the risk of personal data misuse and help individuals maintain control over their data. The overarching idea is that the best way to reduce risks related to personal data processing is to use only the ones needed and at the scale needed... Any fruitful discussion about data minimization should center on humans and seek policy and technology only at a later stage.

Similarly to the GDPR, the CCPA enforced by the California Attorney General aims at limiting the collection of California consumers’ information to what is strictly necessary for organizations to provide their services [45]. The CCPA grants California residents the right to know what personal information is being collected about them and requests deleting their personal information. Personal data in the CCPA includes biometric data and network activity information. In 2021, the Chinese personal information protection law (PIPL) was adopted on 1 August 2021 and came into force on 1 November 2021. The definition of personal data in the PIPL is essentially the same as personal data in the GDPR but with expanded expressions. The PIPL covers personal information in the non-data form, yet personal information and personal data largely overlap in the digital economy. Also, data minimization principles and the right to data portability are enshrined in the law.³⁰

Besides these essential regulations in privacy law, several other major privacy regulations apply on a regional and national level, like the Personal Information

²⁹ See Article 35 of the GDPR.

³⁰ See Article 6 of the PIPL: “Personal information processing shall be based on explicit and reasonable purposes and directly related to those purposes, and shall exert the minimum impacts on the rights and interests of individuals. The collection of personal information shall be limited to the minimum scope required by the purpose of processing, and personal information may not be collected excessively.”; see Article 45(3) of the PIPL: “Where an individual requests the transfer of his personal information to a designated personal information processor, which meets the requirements of national cyberspace department for transferring personal information, the requested personal information processor shall provide means for the transfer.”

Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA) from Canada, which seek to balance the right of privacy of individuals and the need for organizations [115], Brazil’s General Data Protection Law (LGPD) [117], the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) in South Africa [84], Hong Kong’s Personal Data (Privacy) Ordinance in Asia and several others in the Pacific region [62]. The perimeter of the legal validity of these regulations is the geographical border or the civil status of a person. Other ad-hoc regulations apply instead to specific contexts to guard health data [24], target online services for minors [28], or securely handle credit card information [59]. Reviewing these legal texts and the related literature, it becomes clear that data minimization provisions are often presented as an abstract principle, describing an ideal state or outcome without more specific limitations or criteria. In contrast to other essential concepts of the GDPR, such as the right to erasure or the right to consent, data minimization has yet to attract much regulatory and judicial guidance [13].

Even though data minimization does not take attention at first, it is indeed a widely employed technique for privacy, especially in the implementation of online trust services. A trust service is a framework for realizing secure online transactions and enforcing data minimization through privacy-by-design. Those regulations are built on top of privacy frameworks and aid in building trust among parties. The European Union is at the forefront of layering trust provisioning of personal data through digital certificates with its *electronic IDentification Authentication and trust Services regulation* (eIDAS). The eIDAS requires member states in the EU to publicly agree on a standard schema for data exchange, named eID schema. Defining a typical data exchange mechanism helps to design future standards for data minimization [34]. Different frameworks to guide the adoption of trust services comprise the *pan-Canadian trust framework* (PCTF) that provides a tool to address policy needs for stakeholders and the New Zealand Trust framework [3].

3.2 Data minimization: a cordon sanitaire to protect personal data and trade secrets

In 2.3, we discussed the conflict between personal data and trade secrets. Definition 1 gives the formula to illustrate the personal data process in a perfectly competitive market, which implies that trade secrets based on personal data essentially depend on innovative and unique models or methods applied to processing if the flow of personal data is free. The data process respects the data subjects’ rights. Data minimization provides a cordon sanitaire for controllers and processors to achieve free personal data flowing and processing with concerns about data subjects³¹.

The data minimization principle runs through the whole process of personal data processing.³² We recall that during personal data collection, companies can

³¹ See Recital 39 of the GDPR; *B v. Latvijas Republikas Saeima*, Case C-439/19, ECLI:EU:C:2021:504, at para 98, 110.

³² See Article 5(1)(c), Article 25(1) of the GDPR and *TK v Asociația de Proprietari bloc M5A-ScaraA*, Case C-708/18, ECLI:EU:C:2019:1064, at para 48.

collect only personal data that is “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relationship with the purposes for which they are processed”³³ and their collecting models should also be designed to comply with it. Data minimization allows the data subject to control more data without affecting legal business activities. Compared to (big) companies, data subjects cannot generate or create more factual personal data or predictive personal data and derive huge economic value from it [91]. Logically, the data subjects would have more incentive to share data, as they would hardly benefit as much as the company from data aggregation and network effects [114]. And individuals can consider their preferences in their decision-making process, which are inherently subjective and cannot be directly quantified or assessed by external parties [7]. For those personal data provided or newly generated, the data subjects can be transferred through the right to data portability or managed through the rights of access, erasure, and rejection. But there is no doubt that data minimization initially affords more space for data subjects and guarantees more reliable and free-flowing of personal data.

Likewise, the processing of personal data should be guided by this principle. In other words, even the personal data have already been collected by companies legally, processors should consider and use personal data carefully in every step of the process to ensure that the amount of personal data is restricted for this ongoing step, not for a general purpose.³⁴ On the other hand, data minimization is not the standard for trade secrets, so it cannot prevent innovative methods of collecting or processing personal data from becoming trade secrets. But if the techniques, models, and methods of collecting or processing personal data cannot comply with data minimization, they will never be legally allowed in practice.³⁵

Data minimization does not impact trade secrets yielded by innovative methods; it limits the legal establishment of trade secrets consisting of newly generated information. Trade secrets from newly generated information should generally arise from the personal data source and process governed by data minimization. At least, data minimization cannot destroy any standards of trade secrets. Otherwise, this trade secret will no longer survive if the changes induced by data minimization make it impossible to match the three standards.

As a vine nourished by personal data protection, data minimization builds a cordon sanitaire in the conflict between personal data and trade secrets. It imposes penalties on companies for excessive infringement of personal data. Data minimization can affect trade secrets by limiting data size and availability by controlling purpose and processing. Meanwhile, this cordon sanitaire imposes obligations to protect personal data on companies relying on it for innovation

³³ See Article 5(1)(c).

³⁴ See Recital 34 of Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act):“(...) the third party should only access additional information that is necessary for the provision of the service requested by the user. Having received access to data, the third party should process it exclusively for the purposes agreed with the user, without interference from the data holder.”

³⁵ See Recital 78, Article 25(1) and Article 47(2)(d) of the GDPR.

- excessive personal data processing is punishable by law.³⁶ Thanks to the cordon sanitaire created by data minimization for companies, personal data can be transferred more freely, facilitating the improvement of products or services and contributing to market competition. Furthermore, the principle renders more rational applications of trade secret directives, i.e., forcing companies to focus more on innovative technologies, designs, models, etc., rather than simply monopolizing user data. But this cordon sanitaire stemmed from data minimization is not a provocation to the nature of trade secrets but a tacit consensus -highlighting innovation with a competitive advantage³⁷.

Data minimization allows individuals to have more control as well as delineating a legal space for trade secrets. Firstly, data minimization does not interfere with innovations of methods or techniques and the trade secrets constituted by them, including data minimization models, and any trade secrets formed by newly generated data compliant with data minimization should be given respect.³⁸ Secondly, “data minimization and data protection by design and by default are essential when processing involves significant risks to the fundamental rights of individuals”³⁹. Based on this, data minimization regulates activities between data subjects and data controllers or processors, and also governs some data activities between individual users and third parties. Although the data holder’s obligation to make data available to a data recipient excludes “the disclosure of trade secrets within the meaning of Directive (EU) 2016/943”⁴⁰, trade secrets shall only be disclosed to third parties in cases where the data is “strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose agreed between the user and the third party”⁴¹. In this process, the data holder, the user, and the third party must take all specific necessary measures to preserve the confidentiality of the trade secret.⁴² Since

³⁶ See *TK v Asociația de Proprietari bloc M5A-ScaraA*, Case C-708/18, ECLI:EU:C:2019:1064, at para. 48.

³⁷ The innovation with a competitive advantage includes not only innovations with a positive value, i.e., those that bring economic benefits but also innovations with a negative value, i.e., those that reduce costs and avoid wrong models by trial and error.

³⁸ See Recital 8 of the Data Act: “Such measures include not only pseudonymisation and encryption, but also the use of increasingly available technology that permits algorithms to be brought to the data and allow valuable insights to be derived without the transmission between parties or unnecessary copying of the raw or structured data themselves.”

³⁹ See Recital 34 of the Data Act: “In line with the data minimisation principle, the third party should only access additional information that is necessary for the provision of the service requested by the user(...)”

⁴⁰ See Article 8(6) of the Data Act: “(...) an obligation to make data available to a data recipient shall not oblige the disclosure of trade secrets within the meaning of Directive (EU) 2016/943.”

⁴¹ See Article 5(8) of the Data Act: “Trade secrets shall only be disclosed to third parties to the extent that they are strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose agreed between the user and the third party (...)”

⁴² See Article 4(3) of the Data Act: “(...)The data holder and the user can agree measures to preserve the confidentiality of the shared data, in particular in relation

trade secrets involving personal data are also subject to data minimization requirements for activities between the data holder and the third party, it allows the data holder to disclose such data at the minimum level, which objectively protects the confidentiality of the trade secret.

3.3 Technical existing solutions

The technology leveraging data minimization in online services involves several parties, and their rationale differs in various aspects. The legal model sets data minimization as boundaries in processing personal information to what is strictly necessary for data collection. That means whether an organization gathers more information than is strictly necessary to accomplish the purpose for which data have been collected, the organization is kept from processing it. On the other hand, data scientists' approach streamlines the data gathering issue by acknowledging data minimization in terms of limiting the information shared over a communication channel or stored in a repository [86]. This approach dates back to the early days of computing, where the formalization of data minimization as a principle of privacy was expressed in terms of the secrecy of information.

A quick example that aids in emphasizing the importance of data minimization as a process feeds from practitioners, researchers, and jurists is depicted by a doorbell camera use case. The doorbell camera is a specific type of security camera mounted nearby the front door of a building. It is designed to feed the homeowner with live audio and video recording, allowing residents to communicate with visitors without physically leaving the house. The camera features facial recognition and network capability to identify people and upload images to the cloud. It records 24/7 so that the camera sensor captures people and vehicles at any moment. Without filtering the photos, everyone accessing the videotape can track people or cars, leading to a massive privacy violation. In this scenario, data minimization is proper for pre-processing images for blurring faces and avoiding sending recordings containing sensitive information. This example aimed to show the relevance of data minimization against the risk of privacy breaches coming from apparently harmless smart objects [58].

Engineering data minimization into systems and translating it into technical requirements is particularly complex. It requires proposing strategies and combining them at different stages of ramification with the involvement of stakeholders [58]. The following presents the steps to move from theory to practice in designing systems for data minimization [109]. The first step involves identifying the purpose of data collection. In our previous example, the purpose of the doorbell camera is to monitor and record activities at a property's front door or entrance. At the same time, the type is a standard media file containing sounds and images. The second step is to decide the kind of system for data minimization. The more data collected, the higher the risk associated with its storage

to third parties.” and Article 5(8) of the Data Act: “(...)and all specific necessary measures agreed between the data holder and the third party are taken by the third party to preserve the confidentiality of the trade secret.”

Fig. 1. The three scenarios of data minimization. Transfer a subset of personal data (a), one attribute only (b), and the associated information (c).

and the consequences of data breaches or data misuse. Thus, the system must include several techniques, such as data anonymization and other design techniques, to ensure data integrity and security. Finally, the last stage ensures that data security remains adequate and relevant. That helps to implement technical and policy measures to minimize the amount of data collected and retained and to determine for how long data will be stored and when it will be deleted. The combination of the previous steps aids in determining the minimum amount of data needed to achieve the purpose of data collection, but anyone can implement it differently according to the sector of interest.

We recall a few techniques to implement data minimization in online services as part of the previously presented sequence of steps. Figure 1 shows the possible scenarios of data minimization. Generally, they require transferring only a subset of attributes that constitute our data, such as name, address, and date of birth (scenario (a)); one attribute only, for example, the date of birth (scenario (b)). The associated information, for example, being over 18 years old (scenario (c)). Data scientists’ application of data minimization consists of designing techniques for applying one of these scenarios (or all) in the information shared with the data processor [30]. Albeit we used the term data and information without distinction, those related concepts have conceptually different meanings in data science. Data consists of raw facts or figures that can be recorded and transmitted by an electronic device. Information is instead the knowledge associated with data [70]. Thus, we describe a set of common strategies that span from providing the associate information only (Zero-Knowledge Proof) to presenting a subset of attributes (a subset of attributes) or adding random noise to obfuscate data (data obfuscation). The following is a non-exhaustive list of methods for data minimization:

Zero Knowledge Proof. ZKP is a technique that provides full anonymization to external beneficiaries of the data by sharing only the associated information (see Figure 1 (c)) [33]. ZKP relies on mathematical functions to hide unnecessary information and verify a claim’s accuracy without conveying data other than the claim itself. In cryptography and data minimization, using the pseudonyms Alice and Bob to represent two entities exchanging information is common. Alice and Bob were employed mainly in the 1970s for illustrative purposes and have become widely used in the scientific literature to describe algorithms like RSA [99]. We use the same approach in this paper. Suppose that Alice needs to prove her age to Bob. In a classic scenario, Alice shares her identity card (or a digital version

of it) containing her exact date of birth plus further information (Figure 1 (a)). ZKP allows instead to convey information as a flag that can prove our person's age without the full date of birth. Using bounce-back messaging, hash functions, asymmetric cryptography, etc., Alice can prove her knowledge of a secret without sharing other info. Thus, it is considered a data minimization technique as it limits information sharing to just a flag: true or false if our age is over 18. The number of applications of ZKP is vast, from authentication to proving our identity without sharing personal information to financial transactions, etc. [22].

Access Control List. An Access Control List (ACL) is a list that matches resources with their corresponding permission [80]. It is commonly considered a safeguard mechanism to limit access to resources. However, it can also be a data minimization strategy when applied in the following way. Suppose a company collects customers' data and wants to implement data minimization to reduce the risk of data breaches. ACL can enforce data minimization by triggering four parameters. Identifying different access levels that allow discriminating among the relevance of personal data (1); implementing access based on roles within the organization that assigns access based on jobs responsibility to prevent unwilling disclosure of personal data (2); granting employees the minimum access rights to resources to limit the unnecessary exposure to customers data (3); auditing the ACL to ensure that the list of access permissions is appropriate and always up-to-date (4) [21]. By implementing ACL in this manner, a company ensures that access to data is appropriate and limited to what is strictly necessary for data processing. Thus, although ACL is mostly employed as a mechanism to regulate and manage access to data, in the following article, we consider ACL a data minimization strategy.

Data obfuscation. This technique implements data minimization, transforming the original dataset while preserving the data structure [12]. Methods for data obfuscation include encryption, data masking, and data perturbation. Encryption aims to hide information from prying eyes. Data masking replaces accurate data with inauthentic data that retains the exact characteristics of the original data [97]. For example, Alice can prove her age to Bob by sharing her date of birth with a phony day and month of birth for better privacy, sharing only the actual birth year. It is similar to the scenario of Figure 1(b) but with a fake date of birth. It differs from the previously mentioned ZKP as Alice transmits the entire (modified) attribute (the date of birth) rather than the associated information. Finally, data perturbation consists of adding random noise⁴³ to the original one to make data recognition difficult [16]. Generally, autonomous tools

⁴³ Random noise is a technique that adds random data to the original dataset to protect sensible private information (personal identifiable information, health data, etc.). The objective is to protect the privacy of individuals from malicious users. It can be achieved in different ways, from substituting the last few digits of the National Insurance Number to adding a fake name to a person. Those are all techniques for random noise. However, random noise may affect the accuracy and quality of the data, so it must be used sparingly [98].

randomly query search engines to add fake search information and avoid profiling individuals [1].

A data minimization strategy can be implemented through one of those techniques or collectively by combining two or more. In several situations, the data-gathering process may combine information from multiple sources, allowing the data processor to infer more than just the single transmission's content, rendering data minimization useless (recalls Section 2). In this case, the data processor must acquire the rights to process data accordingly to the factual needs for which data have been collected. The result of data gathering may lead to data linking, the process of connecting data from different sources or origins [23]. Data linking strengthens relationships between data to obtain a more complete and meaningful view of the information. However, existing data minimization strategies only sometimes forbid data linking [46].

The strategies mentioned above for data minimization sometimes apply sophisticated techniques to enforce minimization. Sometimes those techniques do not provide the expected results and are simply a waste of computational effort for the data subject. Depending on the specific method employed by the ZKP, data minimization may require a continuous bounce-back of messages to show proof of knowing a secret. A recent scenario opens up the application of data minimization in a different way. Instead of fancy algorithms to hide data, the data subject may send as many messages as the number of requests from the data controller. For example, the data subject can send one message containing her name and a different message for the date of birth. These techniques do not require computational effort from the data subject, and it is preferable to the strategies mentioned above when the processor asks for a few attributes (e.g., name and address). Yet it is onerous when it requires a continuous bounce-back of messages between the data subject and the processor. Thus, choosing the best strategy depends on several variables: the type of attributes we aim to share, the communication protocol, and the data exchange format. This bounce back of messages is onerous, but sometimes it is still preferable to adopting sophisticated algorithms. In a nutshell, a data minimization strategy must consider foundational principles for embedding privacy into the design of products and services.

Over the last few years, a framework to incorporate privacy considerations into the design and development process of policies and technology is the privacy-by-design framework, which, by default, includes the data minimization principle. The framework involves the collaboration of stakeholders from different disciplines and combines techniques in everyday practice. Privacy-by-design frameworks span from the law (e.g., GDPR) and apply technology (e.g., NIST Privacy Framework [51], ISO/IEC 27701 [38]). In the following section, we propose a technique to implement data minimization through privacy-by-design.

In our case, the targeted human right is privacy, and its importance is well-recognized in any modern society. If the government is able to preserve individuals' privacy using legal tools, this would, in turn, benefit market competition

and economic growth. A common framework for integrating privacy concerns into policy and technology solutions from the early stage of development is privacy-by-design, which includes the principle of data minimization by default. The ultimate goal of privacy-by-design is to prevent privacy violations while ensuring that privacy is considered a crucial aspect at every stage of the design and development process. Thus, exploring data minimization entails delving into the regulations and technical tools used to enforce privacy-by-design. For the aforementioned reasons, this section explores the major regulatory frameworks for privacy-by-design and the latest technology for data minimization as promoted by the W3C⁴⁴, all within the context of privacy as a core human principle.

4 From law to technology: A privacy-by-design tool for data minimization

Today, many organizations establish agreements with tech companies to obtain personal data legally. That generates vast repositories in the hands of organizations and leads to what is known as surveillance capitalism [11]. With surveillance capitalism, companies collect personal data from users to strengthen their dominant position in the market. A solution to foster market competition is limiting data sharing to what is strictly necessary. That can be achieved through legal and technical initiatives combining data protection policies with cutting-edge solutions [119]. The first attempt to return privacy to users through a common framework dates back to the 1980s when the Personal Information Management System (PIMS) promised users to manage their data. PIMS is a set of software tools and applications aiming to give individuals control. Still, PIMS lacks a strategy to embed data minimization within policy [67, 88]. Thus, over time, PIMS has been outclassed by new holistic solutions aiming to spot privacy as a core issue and proposing data minimization by default to minimize information disclosure.

4.1 Main Legal pillars stemmed from Data minimization principle

Data minimization is a fundamental principle outlined in Chapter 2 of the GDPR. It applies to the whole process but does not extend to the pre-processing stage⁴⁵, such as the standard for consent. Before processing, the purposes of such

⁴⁴ The World Wide Web Consortium serves as the primary worldwide body for establishing Web standards.

⁴⁵ See Article 25(1) of the GDPR: "The controller shall implement appropriate technical and organizational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed. That obligation applies to the amount of personal data collected, the extent of their processing, the period of their storage, and their accessibility" and Article 47 (2)(d) of the GDPR: "the application of the general data protection principles, in particular purpose limitation, data minimization, limited storage periods, data quality, data protection by design and by default, the legal basis for processing, processing of

activities should be explicit and specific, and the process must be authorized by the data subject's consent or by law. Given the specific purpose of the processing, the data controller or processor needs to adhere to "sufficiency," "relevance," and "necessity concerning the purposes".

Adequacy Data quality refers to the degree to which data is accurate, complete, consistent, and relevant to the intended purpose of the data processing activity [42]. High-quality data is error-free, up-to-date, and highly relevant to the specific target for which it is used [50]. Data quantity means the amount of data gathered for a specific purpose, which is influenced by various factors, such as the complexity of the task, the desired level of accuracy, and the design of the analytical model. To achieve the desired outcome, data processing necessitates data sets up to certain quality and quantity.

The process for achieving adequacy of data minimization can be recapitulated as the loop depicted in Figure 2. Data processors delineate the purpose and scope of their data activities. Based on the above prerequisites, the outcome and costs of data analysis depend on both the quality (Q) and scale (S) of the data set. Within the specific purpose and scope of data activity, the output is $f(Q, S)$, with data quality Q falling between Q_1 and Q_n and data scale S lying between S_1 and S_n . Assuming that the average data quality in a given market is Q_{avg} , there must be an average data scale S_{avg} in $f(Q, S)$ for a given Q_{avg} . Similarly, for the minimum data scale S_{min} in this market, there exists a minimum data quality $Q_{S_{min}}$ in $f(Q, S)$.⁴⁶ Given the accuracy of the output, a potential negative correlation may exist between the two, i.e. a smaller collection of high-quality data may achieve the same level of result as a large collection of low-quality data [66, 69, 103]. Thus, $Q_{S_{min}} \geq Q_{avg}, S_{min} \leq S_{avg}$.

The quality of input data from data processors is represented by Q_x . If $Q_x < Q_{avg}$, then $Q_x < Q_{S_{min}}$ and $S_x > S_{avg} \geq S_{min}$. If the data quality $Q_{S_{min}} \geq Q_x \geq Q_{avg}$, then $S_{min} \leq S_x \leq S_{avg}$. If the data quality $Q_x \geq Q_{S_{min}}$, $S_x = S_{min}$. If this result can match the minimum requirements, Q and S are sufficient to comply with the adequacy standard. If the minimum requirements are not met, for a given Q_x , the data scale can be expanded, i.e. S_x becomes $S_{x'}$, until the target requirements are fulfilled.

In accordance with the objectives of the GDPR, collecting large amounts of low-quality data breaches the adequacy standard of data minimization if the same purpose can be achieved at a reasonable cost by using a smaller amount of high-quality data.⁴⁷

special categories of personal data, measures to ensure data security, and the requirements in respect of onward transfers to bodies not bound by the binding corporate rules".

⁴⁶ $Q_{S_{min}} \neq \min(Q)$ in all Q , $Q_{S_{min}} \geq Q_{avg} > \min(Q)$ in all Q .

⁴⁷ See *B v. Latvijas Republikas Saeima*, Case C-439/19, ECLI:EU:C:2021:504, at para 110; *TK v Asociația de Proprietari bloc M5A-ScaraA*, Case C-708/18, ECLI:EU:C:2019:1064, at para 47; *Valsts policijas Rīgas reģiona pārvaldes Kārtības policijas pārvalde v Rīgas pašvaldības SIA "Rīgas satiksme"*, Case C-13/16, ECLI:EU:C:2017:336, at para 86.

Fig. 2. Data quantity and Data quality under the adequacy standard

Relevance In data minimization, the relevance requirement points to the connection and necessity between the personal data collected and the purpose of processing activities. However, the relevance standard does not necessarily imply that all relevant data is legally allowed to be covered.⁴⁸ It is necessary to further classify the distinction between relevance in the context of data minimization and relevance in the general sense. Data relevance implies that the data collected should be relevant to the target, either directly or indirectly.⁴⁹ Figure 3 lists all the data associated with the output c . When a factor itself can directly influence another factor or output, the solid line shows a direct correlation between the two. On the other hand, when a factor cannot directly influence another factor or output but affects the target through one or more mediating factors, the link

⁴⁸ See *Digi Távközlési és Szolgáltató Kft. v Nemzeti Adatvédelmi és Információszabadság Hatóság*, Case C-77/21, ECLI:EU:C:2022:805, at para 26, 35, 36.

⁴⁹ See *Ligue des droits humains ASBL v Conseil des ministres*, Case C-817/19, ECLI:EU:C:2022:491, at para 153, 156, 157.

Fig. 3. Direct relevance, indirect relevance, necessary scope under relevance standard

is considered indirect. In Figure 2, the data in the blue box (*data₂*, *data₄*, *data₇*, *data₉*, *data₁₁*) are all directly relevant to target *c*, meaning they have a direct impact on the target without mediation.

While a direct correlation serves as a conspicuous and crucial reference point, the relevance of data to the target does not depend solely on direct correlations, but on objective and necessary connections between personal data and the objective pursued.⁵⁰ When the target is directly linked to some data, collecting all directly relevant data may not be necessary.⁵¹ Instead, only the necessary directly relevant data should be collected, in line with the data minimization.⁵² That is, the scope of relevance for data minimization may be smaller than the scope of direct relevance between data and the target. In some cases, the complexities of the real world may also render directly relevant data insufficient

⁵⁰ See *Ligue des droits humains ASBL v Conseil des ministres*, Case C-817/19, ECLI:EU:C:2022:491, at para 118, 251; *La Quadrature du Net and Others v Premier ministre and Others*, Joined Cases C-511/18, C-512/18 and C-520/18, ECLI:EU:C:2020:791, at para 133,188; *Staatssecretaris van Justitie en Veiligheid v A and Others*, Case C-70/18, ECLI:EU:C:2019:823, at para 63.

⁵¹ See *Ligue des droits humains ASBL v Conseil des ministres*, Case C-817/19, ECLI:EU:C:2022:491, at para 125, 219; *H.K. v Prokurator (Conditions d'accès aux données relatives aux communications électroniques)*, Case C-746/18, ECLI:EU:C:2021:152, at para 50.

⁵² See *Ligue des droits humains ASBL v Conseil des ministres*, Case C-817/19, ECLI:EU:C:2022:491, at para 132, 162.

to achieve the objective. Therefore, in some instances, a minimum amount of indirectly relevant data necessary to accomplish its objective is considered acceptable, as illustrated by the case in the red box.

Necessity in relation to the purposes. The necessity in relation to the purposes requires all data processing activities to have a clear and specific purpose, whether for private, commercial, or public interests.⁵³ When a data controller or processor is capable of identifying specific purposes for collecting, processing, and storing personal data, as well as the precision required to achieve these purposes before collecting or processing, the data controller or processor shall inform the data subject of the specific purposes and the data scope of their activities.⁵⁴ When data controllers or processors are unable to inform the data subject of the specific final purposes before processing due to external factors beyond their control, they should provide a specific current purpose and limit the collection, processing, and storage of personal data to the bare minimum for the detailed purpose provided at the current stage.⁵⁵ In such cases, the necessity of personal data processing can be expressed as the indispensability of elements, meaning that the ultimate goal cannot be achieved if any of the required data elements are missing.⁵⁶

Once the accuracy of goal attainment is classified as minimum, average, and high, it is easy to see that even the same goal, such as the qualification of a candidate, can be attained with different accuracy. If a recruiter's educational requirement for candidates is obtaining a bachelor's degree, then at the minimum level of result accuracy, the recruiter only needs to verify that the candidate has a bachelor's degree without considering other information. However, suppose the purpose is further elaborated to obtain a bachelor's degree in a specific major. In that case, the minimum level for achieving this purpose is validation for both the bachelor's degree and the bachelor's major. In Figure 4, the necessary link between the data and the result accuracy is drawn with a solid line, while a dashed line marks the non-necessary link between them. The necessary link between the data added to achieve the average level. The average result accuracy is in blue; the essential link between the data added to achieve the high level and the high result accuracy is in yellow. As the accuracy of the results improves, more data is required to make it possible.

Almost all personal data protection laws emphasize that personal data controllers or processors should clarify specific purposes and scope of personal data before processing to achieve data minimization. However, since informa-

⁵³ See Article 89(1), Article 89(2) & Article 93(1) of the GDPR.

⁵⁴ See Article 5(1) of the GDPR.

⁵⁵ See *TK v Asociația de Proprietari bloc M5A-ScaraA*, Case C-708/18 ECLI:EU:C:2019:1064, para 51; *Volker und Markus Schecke GbR (C-92/09) and Hartmut Eifert (C-93/09) v Land Hessen*, Joined cases C-92/09 and C-93/09, ECLI:EU:C:2010:662, at para 86.

⁵⁶ See Opinion of Advocate General Pitruzzella delivered on 27 January 2022, ECLI:EU:C:2022:65, at para 225; *College van burgemeester en wethouders van Rotterdam v M. E. E. Rijkeboer*, Case C-553/07, ECLI:EU:C:2009:293, at para 33.

Fig. 4. Necessity with different result accuracy

tion asymmetry poses a considerable hurdle [8], data subjects and companies may not always be able to access or provide all clear information before data processing [52, 65, 78, 111]. In other words, data processors or controllers may be unable to give a clear minimized extent or scope of personal data for the final purpose before processing. And the precise minimized standard for this purpose may only be gained during data processing. In this case, the model or system should prioritize data minimization by default, limit the data processing to strictly necessary information for every step, and minimize the association between data and individuals at the beginning.

4.2 Technical toolbox

In the early 90s, Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) were designed to reduce the amount of information disclosed while maximizing individual privacy [96]. One application area of PETs is the Personal Information Management Systems (PIMS) and privacy-by-design frameworks. These frameworks take a proactive approach to privacy and data minimization by considering privacy from early development and incorporating the data minimization principle at every design step. This approach allows individuals to control their personal information while choosing what data to disclose and with whom, while also helping to build systems, processes, and products with privacy in mind. Privacy-by-design involves minimizing the amount of personal data collected and providing clear and transparent notice about data collection and use. Thus, privacy-by-design

aims to protect individuals' privacy in electronic transactions. When addressing privacy-by-design systems, two questions prevail: (1) *How to verify the correctness of information* and (2) *How to access personal data* when other entities hold those data. The first question involves verifying the information shared by ecosystem members within a system and ensuring that the information has not been tampered with. On the other hand, access to personal data requires identifying entities and tracking their resources. That means the diploma and relevant information must be available whenever Alice can access them.

In the past, classical verification processes relied on websites, or service providers, to manage data in centralized repositories. As time passed, federated models emerged, which allowed outsourcing the verification process to third parties, thus easing the burden for local platforms and increasing reliance on third parties [113]. However, with both models (classical and federated), platforms or third parties still control personal information and decide what data to share with whom. When referring to access to personal data, platforms still apply local policies to grant access to resources (personal data). Those policies are legally enforced by countries or managed by authoritative bodies. In general, the platform provider is the de-facto owner of personal data. The last trend is to move towards a decentralized model to give users more control over the verification process and resource access. Tentative of sketching legal and technical solutions that implement verification and access to resources in a decentralized fashion is ongoing. Some solutions focus on technology such as blockchain-based models [83], others on social aspects [56], data protection compliance [57] and challenges [120].

Among different platforms, the Verifiable Credentials model from the W3C⁵⁷ sets the reference guide for verifying and accessing personal data. Additionally, the VC model includes data minimization by design so that the disclosure of data is minimized as a deliberate part of the design process. The typical archetype to seamlessly share personal data consists of the following entities: issuer, subject/holder, and verifier. The issuer asserts a claim by releasing personal data about subject holders. So, the issuer can be considered as the provider of personal data. A subject is a natural/legal person for whom claims are issued. The subject receives data from the issuer and stores it in an electronic wallet controlled by the holder. The subject and the holder may correspond to the same entity. However, they can differ (e.g., parents who hold personal data about their children). Once the personal data is received, the holder can store it in a digital wallet. Finally, to access online services, the holder shares their data with the verifier, who collects and processes credentials. Figure 5 shows the typical archetype of the Verifiable Credential model as depicted by the W3C [116]. The information flows from left to right, with the issuer that releases information (1), the subject stores this information on the wallet (2), and upon request, the subject presents personal data to the relying party (3). The entire process works without a central authority. Furthermore, the solution allows entities to verify

⁵⁷ The World Wide Web Consortium serves as the primary worldwide body for establishing Web standards.

Fig. 5. The information flow in the W3C Verifiable Credential model [116].

the accuracy of the information and grant access to information thanks to the use of identifiers.

The identifier is an alphanumeric string associated with each ecosystem member and stored within a decentralized (shared) registry. The registry can be a blockchain or a distributed database. Alice produces a pair of keys at run time and embeds them into the identifier. The encryption key, encoded within the identifier, allows Alice to encrypt her information and share it with the verifier. Alice’s encryption key is never shared with anyone but is secretly hidden within her identifier. The identifier is then publicized in the shared registry (4), where the verifier looks up to obtain Alice’s identifier and the corresponding decryption key. Cryptographic properties (asymmetric encryption) that rely on mathematical artifacts guarantee the secrecy of this procedure, where the encryption and the decryption key are kept separate within the identifier. As its name suggests, the encryption key can only be used to encrypt data while the corresponding decryption key serves to decrypt it [110]. Verifiers can only obtain the decryption key used to read the message but cannot modify the message. The system’s data is then tamperproof, as only those holding the decryption key can read the original message, while the encryption key is never shared. Thus, the entire process allows verifying personal information tamperproof without relying on a third party [43]. With verifiable credentials, individuals can create and manage their own data rather than relying on companies to create and manage them on their behalf. That empowers individuals to control what personal data is included in their credentials, who can access them, and for what purposes they can be used. In other words, verifiable credentials put individuals in the driver’s seat regarding their personal data, allowing them to make informed decisions about how their data is used and shared. Moreover, as a framework, the W3C embraces all participants and is not restricted to data subjects, so it can also protect trade secrets, in which case the platform becomes the subject. When trade secrets need to be disclosed or partially disclosed to third parties,⁵⁸ trade secrets can also be designed to be tamperproof and encoded in the form of verifiable credentials to

⁵⁸ See Article 4(3) and 5(8) of Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on harmonized rules on fair access to and use of data (Data Act).

selectively authorize access to the target to preserve the confidentiality of trade secrets.

The ecosystem members in Figure 5 constitute the Trust Triangle, where trust is spread between entities in a decentralized manner. Besides verification, the trust triangle's second benefit is to solve the data access problem. We recall that in classical and federated models, the online platform provides the service and stores personal data deciding the information users access. With the trust triangle, access to information still relies on the platform will; however, individuals have one significant advantage in limiting the information disclosed. That corresponds to data minimization for data scientists. Within the trust triangle, users hold information and share it with the verifier only the minimum amount. That means this model gives individuals great control over their data, reduces the risk of data breaches and misuse, and implements data minimization by design.

An example shows how the W3C Verifiable Credential model proposes to solve the issues of personal data verification and access. It also kickstarts the future discussion on data minimization and control of information. We consider the following scenario: Alice (subject) applies for a job position on the employer's website, requiring her to upload the diploma. She does not hold a certificate, so she asks for her diploma certificate from the university (issuer). The university issues Alice a digital version of the diploma, proving that she has completed her studies. Alice stores the certificate in the digital wallet installed on her smartphone. She also generates a pair of keys to be enclosed within the unique identifier and uses the encryption key to encrypt the diploma. At the same time, she hides the decryption key within the identifier. Later, Alice publicizes the identifier on a shared ledger (e.g., online database) so that everybody can see it. Upon request, Alice attests her diploma to the employer (verifier). The data exchange is what makes the model reliable. The data is tamperproof as Alice's diploma is encrypted with Alice's encryption key (verification), which is kept private. No one else ever shares this key. In contrast, the employer looks up Alice's identifier and obtains the corresponding decryption key through a mathematical process. Once the verifier obtains the corresponding decryption key, it automatically checks the content and verifies the integrity of the message from Alice. Indeed, the decryption key is the only one that allows the employer to read Alice's diploma but does not allow modifying its content. Overall, the process has two benefits: 1) it associates the message with the sender, and 2) it guarantees that the message has not been tampered with. This approach can be applied in several contexts to solve the verification problem. For example, it is worth showing proof of an apartment rental or a person's age using information issued by the residential municipality. In the healthcare system [20] and online banking [68]. On the other hand, accessing information is still platform-dependent, where the definition of policies plays a crucial role in granting access to users' data. Once the data is in the hands of the verifier, it is the responsibility of the verifier to comply with consent enforcement and data processing lawfully.

However, individuals have a slight advantage compared to past approaches; the Verifiable Credential model enables more control⁵⁹ for users because subjects are de-facto providers of personal data. Indeed, data subjects are positioned between the issuer and the verifier and can better control the information shared. Compared to past models, Alice decides whether to share her diploma and what information to share with the verifier. No one else besides the subject can share personal data because they are held in the subject's wallet. Once the data is shared, it becomes a problem of access to it. The W3C model allows data subjects to freely select the personal information to share and authorize access to specific targets, which ensures that only the desired information is collected by authorized targets. During data processing, the W3C model enables selective disclosure of information, i.e., only necessary data is provided to the recipients, reducing the risk of unnecessary data exposure. Also, privacy protection techniques can be embedded in the W3C model, such as zero-knowledge proof, allowing data sharing and verification without revealing sensitive information to protect sensitive data. In the data storage stage, the W3C model enables personal data to be stored in a secure, decentralized way rather than in a centralized database vulnerable to cyber attacks. Similarly, for holders of trade secrets in the digital world, the W3C model gives companies and platforms the power to disclose information selectively and allows other participants to verify information without revealing it by using privacy-enhancing techniques, such as zero-knowledge proof. The W3C model provides a secure and decentralized framework for exchanging and verifying sensitive information like trade secrets. As previously mentioned, access to data happens in compliance with regulations.

The ecosystem members presented in Figure 5 open to data minimization as follows. The data subject can minimize the information disclosed to the minimum amount needed to prove its validity. In the previous case, Alice can employ one of the techniques presented in section 3.3 to limit the information. The flexibility of the serialization type⁶⁰ encoded in the Verifiable Credential model opens up three possible scenarios for data minimization for Alice's example: 1) transferring only a subset of information, for example, name, address, date of birth, and grade in the degree. 2) Send one data at a time, for example, the date of birth, or 3) the associated information, for example, being over 18 years old or having a degree. Splitting the information allows Alice to share what is strictly necessary to present her data. An alternative scenario foresees sharing a flag through a Zero-Knowledge proof (ZKP). For example, the wallet installed on Alice's device could implement ZKP to share just a banner with the data processor [39]. With this approach, Alice would first generate a token based on ZKP technology and associates it with the diploma. Alice can mathematically prove her knowledge of the token and demonstrate to hold the diploma without revealing it. These techniques prove that Alice knows a secret and allows her to

⁵⁹ Data scientists perceive control as users holding the critical features of personal data or the function to dispose of it freely [102].

⁶⁰ We use the term data serialization to refer to the process of conveying and transferring information in a structured way from origin to the destination [37].

limit the information shared to a subset of data or a flag. These techniques rely on data exchange serialization formats.

We outline three families of serialization standards: JSON files, XML, and x509 certificates used in electronic signatures. The W3C proposed to ease the implementation of data minimization through JSON files, such as JWT and JWE [14]. JWT provides a simple and secure way to convey information between parties within a single token and is used by the Verifiable Credential model and OpenID Connect [104]. The JSON format implements data minimization, as Alice decides the attributes exchange. That means Alice’s diploma is serialized into a standard JSON file creating custom fields in the message and filling them with personal data. That gives Alice complete flexibility in designing her favorite packet to share with the verifier. Thereof, Alice can apply data minimization, sharing only one data, a subset of personal data, or the associated information (as presented before). The second family of standards is the Extensible Markup Language (XML), used for encoding documents with the same flexibility as JSON [15]. However, XML files are more verbose and require pre-agreement between parties that converge to a common format for data exchange through an XML schema. For this reason, data minimization is less flexible as it requires pre-agreement with parties. Changing the data minimization strategy at a later stage becomes tricky. For this reason, XML file exchange is less employed than JSON and used for old protocols such as SAML. Finally, x509 certificates are standard for sharing electronic signatures similar to XML [31]. Customization is only possible through extensions of the standard format. Thus, x509 generally is not considered a good solution for data minimization, but it is widely employed in legal frameworks due to its legal recognition and adoption in electronic signatures. So far, JSON will be the future way to convey information and the easiest way to apply data minimization.

Intending to combine standards for data exchange, protocols, industry capabilities, and policy, the VC model has been incorporated within an overarching architecture featuring four layers [94] and two halves known as Trust Over IP (TOIP) [6]. The stack is described as follows: 1) identifiers, 2) secure communication, 3) data exchange, and 4) governance. Each layer serves a specific purpose and builds on top of the other, with the bottom layer constituting a pure pipeline for anchoring privacy and security. The other layers implement secure connection (layer 2), the archetype of the trust triangle (layer 3), and governance (layer 4). Initially, the governance layer concerned the top of the stack. However, early works have led to a different design approach where the governance framework spreads across all four layers forming two halves. For this reason, the TOIP is often depicted as a dual-stack where each layer comprises a governance and technical implementation. Figure 6 shows the four-layer and the two halves in a unified structure.

The two stacks are side-by-side, including policy considerations and technology with social and business practices. The more we climb to the top, the more data minimization is encoded as a utility for trust in practical use cases. This layering structure provides a guideline to develop a decentralized trust infras-

Fig. 6. The Trust Over IP framework combining governance with technical archetypes.

structure that can be widely adopted and used by individuals, practitioners, and organizations. In particular, the first layer acts as a repository to store identifiers through trusted storage (i.e., distributed ledgers, decentralized file systems, databases, or peer-to-peer networks). The identifier is used to pinpoint individuals and organizations and to provide information with great security and privacy. The identifier can be decoupled from centralized registries and certificate authorities, leading individuals to a fully decentralized architecture [2]. However, policies to implement decentralized registries or shared ledgers still need to be defined. Layer 2 provides secure P2P⁶¹ communication between entities. The communication can be instantiated between devices through a QR code via Bluetooth (offline) or by sharing references through the network (online). Layer 3 implements the W3C-VC model with entities involved in the data exchange. Layer 4 defines the ecosystem of applications to meet business needs, for example, mobile applications for healthcare, education purposes, etc. The two halves of the model spread in each layer as a reminder that corresponding governance must be adequately defined for each entity or protocol. It points out the need for policies that specify purposes and principles for ecosystem members, rules to express verifiable credentials, establish security and spread trust among entities. Usually, offerings focus only on one stack, leaving the other stack for future implementations. The following section aims to introduce one of the few works that include the data minimization principle dealing with technical and legal aspects. It depicts the European data minimization strategy, including trust services and online identification.

⁶¹ P2P stands for Peer-to-Peer communication. It is a type of communication that does not involve any third party but only the instantiation of a channel between the sender and the receiver [107]

4.3 A governance strategy for data minimization

This section frames existing solutions that implement privacy-by-design and data minimization at each step of the designing process, considering legal and technical aspects. We use the model explained in Section 4 as a reference guide and mainly focus on the European trust services and electronic transactions (eIDAS⁶²). It is a major privacy-by-design framework worldwide, affecting over half a billion people and involving policymakers as well as technical designers. We further check whether the eIDAS architecture diverges from the data minimization depicted by the privacy-by-design model. Eventually, we evaluate whether adopting a privacy-by-design framework is a utopia or brings tangible benefits for businesses and individuals.

The eIDAS. The importance of a data minimization framework that goes beyond businesses, social activities, and public institutions to embrace citizens and foster economic growth has become increasingly important worldwide. In most cases, presenting personal information offline caps the possibility of applying data minimization on a document. Going back to our previous example with Alice’s diploma presented in Section 4.2, whether Alice shows up physically to provide her diploma to the administrative staff or employer, she may disclose far more information than just what was explicitly requested. The same situation happens in the online world. Today, 72% of users want to know how their data is processed when using social media accounts, and 63% of EU citizens want a trust framework that shields their privacy online [90]. The European Commission commits to solving these problems by proposing a trust framework that enables businesses to innovate and helps citizens to access products and online services in a trusted manner. The resulting framework will allow people to securely share information online without giving up personal data. In response to these challenges, in 2014, the European Union started to oversee eIDAS, a regulation establishing a framework for the cross borders of electronic transactions within the EU [4]. The eIDAS helps citizens easily access products and services and establishes the backbone for trust services in governance and technology, increasing trust in digital transactions and ensuring the protection of the personal data of EU citizens. With the eIDAS, the Commission aims to create a secure, trustworthy, and innovative digital environment for businesses and citizens that includes the 80% of the EU population by 2030.

The regulation came into force in 2016 with a two-year transition period to allow Member States to accommodate services and policies with the law (2018). The regulation foresees two pillars: the Trust Service and Electronic Identification. The former includes services used to verify the signer of an electronic document (eSignature), ensure the origin of data (eSeal), and provide evidence (timestamp, delivery service, and website authentication) [108]. On the other hand, Member States appoint service providers that comply with the regulation

⁶² The acronym stands for Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and Trust Services.

Fig. 7. The eIDAS solution: outer circles are Member States; inner circles are service providers and the eIDAS-Nodes. The dashed square with rounded corners stands for the eIDAS solution.

as Trust Service Providers (TSPs) and Qualified Trust Service Providers (QTSPs). The QTSP meets specific requirements of trustworthiness to issue secrets with legal value. The first version of eIDAS (eIDAS v1) guaranteed the interplay of personal data and documents across Member States through the EU-baked protocol, whose task is to serialize data to a common format. The eIDAS solution wraps claims into a common standard for data exchange and forwards data to other Member States. So that when citizens wish to access services from another Member State, their request is delivered through the eIDAS solution to the service provider of the targeting Member State. Figure 7 shows the activity of the eIDAS solutions where eIDAS-Nodes serialize data and convey it to the destination. Typically, when a citizen of Member State B requires access to services from Member State A (MSA), the SP in MSA forwards the request to the country of origin through the eIDAS solution (1). The eIDAS solution consists of a network of eIDAS-nodes that serialize claims into a common data-sharing format (2). Upon reception, the eIDAS-Node in Member State B deserializes data and sends it to the local (national) trust service for data provisioning (3). The response is returned through the same protocol to Member State A (4). The process is transparent to individuals and services that manage data according to local policies and rules. Thus, personal data can travel across countries. The data format for the signature and transfer of personal data is the electronic signature or Seal that generally corresponds to an x509 certificate [82].

Data minimization is hardly applied in this context because digital certificates like x509 are used for electronic signatures. Digital certificates do not allow the selection of a subset of personal data. Therefore, the eIDAS actual adoption rate stuck to less than five thousand cross-border transactions per year, shortcomings the expectations of the European Union to provide a framework for data minimization on a large scale [5]. The European Union acknowledged the intrinsic limitations of eIDAS. It proposed an amendment to provide citizens

with means to better control data sharing through a toolkit: a wallet aiming to give users more control and secrecy through data minimization. Thus, with some generalization, eIDAS v2 can be considered eIDAS v1 plus the wallet and its ecosystem entities. The result outlines the eIDAS v2 objective to move from a mere interoperability framework for cross borders transactions to a privacy-by-design framework. With eIDAS v2, the Commission nailed several piloting projects aiming to foster the development and introduction of the toolkit in different areas of crucial interest for the economic growth that spans from the driving license to diploma, payment service, and eHealth. Those use cases were later extended to cover a broader range of scenarios, such as requesting birth certificates, opening bank accounts, filing tax returns, and applying for a university loan [36]. The design pattern of eIDAS v2 recalls the W3C-VC model as previously introduced in Section 4.2, with Trust Service providers (national identity providers) releasing personal data. Holders store those secrets in a wallet. Finally, the wallet interfaces with the verifier to share secrets. The information flow moves from left to right, like in the VC model.

Recently, the LIBE committee⁶³ assessed the eIDAS v2 to quest for flaws and weaknesses with privacy concerns in mind [26]. They highlighted two main issues with the current framework: 1) the use of a unique identifier and 2) the limitation of applying data minimization. The former allows governments, financial institutions, and, more generally, third parties to track people; the latter sets a bond to customizing the information disclosure. To streamline these issues, it is now under revision a third proposal regulation aiming at taking over the use of a unique identifier and providing several changes to enhance privacy [27]. Eventually, after a sequence of steps, eIDAS moved from a cross borders electronic transactions framework to a holistic privacy-enhancing solution for controlling personal information.

eIDAS challenges. The number of changes affecting the regulation over the years reflected the divergence of models of the technical architecture as well as ways data minimization applies to users. The first version of the eIDAS was mostly an interoperability framework, heavily focused on regulating cross-border transactions by sharing personal data through digital certificates in the form of an x509 certificate. Although, those certificates are not flexible to enable sending data in a detached manner [55]. Indeed, the x509 standard was invented back in the early days of the Internet to secure communication between two parties, typically a client and a server, and was later used in the context of digital signatures and electronic transactions to give digital signatures with legal recognition. Using x509 certificates helps provide legal certainty and facilitates the acceptance of electronic documents and communications in legal proceedings. However, it has never been designed with the principle of data minimization in mind. For this reason, the first eIDAS framework implemented appliances to wrap the data exchange into a standard container and share it across borders. To

⁶³ The LIBE is a committee of the European Parliament that deals with issues related to civil liberties, justice, and home affairs in the European Union.

strengthen policies and determine a guideline for technical architecture, on June 2021, the Commission adopted a recommendation calling on Member States to work towards developing a toolkit including a technical Architecture Reference Framework (ARF) [25]. This toolkit will serve components and appliances for data minimization and secure storage of personal information. With the eIDAS v2, the EU put a list of public bodies to issue personal data that intrinsically considers data minimization. For example, the EU specified qualified and non-qualified service providers who aim to enable data minimization by releasing only the minimum amount of information needed for the bootstrapping process. The EU defined the level of assurance (LoA) associated with each data exchange to guarantee access control and determine who has access to what resource. This powerful tool reworked the entire architecture of eIDAS, delineating the three entities described in the W3C model: issuer, subject, and verifier. Qualified or non-qualified trust service providers represent the issuer; the data subject stores personal information to bootstrap the wallet, and the relying party acts as a verifier. Thus, albeit eIDAS v1 failed to provide citizens with means to control personal information, the advent of eIDAS v2 embraced a more privacy-enhancing paradigm. The European Union has yet to rely on a stable industry standard while designing privacy-enhancing infrastructures. However, they grasped the idea of a wallet that strives towards a privacy-by-design framework. Since the EU heavily relies on digital certificates, data minimization is still compromised unless the EU decides to migrate towards existing Json-based standards for data exchange, as one of the options described in [34]. Whether the European vision will ever converge to a mere privacy-by-design solution would be a disputable remark. However, it is important to consider legal and technological advancement simultaneously.

4.4 Further first solutions in Europe

Europe is an exciting environment for privacy for policymakers and even for technological edge and capability. We provide an overview of further data minimization strategies in Europe. We only regard privacy-enhancing solutions that impact data minimization and are adopted at a national scale and industry initiatives. In describing further initiatives, we split the divergence of approaches into four European macro areas, each driven by a slightly different approach to privacy. First, solutions with data minimization as a core business across the Nordic European countries are mainly implemented to follow the business needs of banks, financial institutions, and the private sector with applications in the form of web or mobile apps. Usability is a discriminant factor for users in the adoption of these solutions. In 2021, the Swedish government provided Freja eID Plus [92] as a framework to manage personal data, including COVID-19 certificates, that comes with a mobile app. The approach adopted by the Baltic states is, instead, significantly different. After several cyber-attacks that hit Estonia in 2007 [106], Baltic governments pushed for adopting a privacy framework to protect their citizens, heavily dependent on innovative technologies. Estonia became one of the first countries to pave the road for policy in the fast adoption

of blockchain technology by notifying six schemes for privacy services online. A long-term pioneering project resulted in the e-Estonia [44]. For those countries, starting was fast with the adoption of shared ledgers, but they are still bound to it with mobile applications. In mainland Europe and the south, countries relied on smart cards with no possibility to disclose customized information on request. Germany slowly moved to mobile applications. Unlike the Nordic countries, in southern Europe, the lack of involvement from banks and financial services made their public services struggle to return from their previous investments. Hence, existing solutions need to find a balance between usability and security [79].

5 Conclusion

Starting from the literal text of the GDPR, personal data, the most important "atom" in the digital world, is given a clear and fixed literal definition and scope. But the continuous development of anonymization and de-anonymization technologies has led to a dynamic change to the borders of anonymized data excluded from personal data, affecting the borders of personal data. Since the rights and distribution of rights conferred on personal and non-personal data differ, the conditions for the two to constitute a trade secret vary markedly. Data minimization, as one of the most important principles to be observed by personal data controllers and processors in data processing, plays a pivotal role in determining whether personal data can constitute a trade secret. Data minimization, as a cordon sanitaire derived from personal data protection, limits the scale of data collection, processing, storage, and data availability by controlling the purpose and method of processing, which poses a challenge to companies that conduct business solely through piling up personal data because the excessive collection of personal data is punishable by law. But this restriction is not a provocation to the nature of trade secrets but a tacit consensus. This principle prompts the trade secrets directive to be applied more rationally, i.e., forcing companies to devote more attention to innovative technologies, designs, models, etc., rather than simply monopolizing user data. Also, as data minimization pays respect to the data subject's rights, personal data can flow more freely with the individual's intention, facilitating the improvements of products or services and promoting market competition.

The positive effects of data minimization on personal data protection, data flows, the economic value of data, and the development of the data market place the specific requirements for data minimization in a critical position. Article 5(1) of the GDPR provides the standards for data minimization, i.e., adequacy, relevance, and necessity concerning the purposes. The recapitulation of the personal data processing flow further illustrates the requirements for implementing adequacy, namely that adequacy is attained by considering both data quality and data scale. If the same purpose can be achieved by using less high-quality data at a reasonable cost, then collecting large amounts of low-quality data violates the adequacy standard of data minimization. The relevance in the data minimization sense does not rely on direct or indirect correlation; instead, it re-

quires considering both the purposes and the other two standards. The necessity in relation to the purposes requires personal data to be processed to the extent necessary for the specific purpose allowed to be achieved. If the specific purpose and scope are unavailable, the necessity in relation to the purpose should be the extent necessary for the minimum achievement of that purpose.

The analysis of data minimization frameworks in Europe demonstrates how the general context in which Europe fits well in addressing privacy and data minimization. Europe started with the idea of cross borders transactions of personal data. It ended up with a privacy-by-design framework that aligns the private sector offerings (W3C-VC model) in data minimization. Compared to other platforms, the data exchange format designed by the W3C with verifiable credentials is a significant advantage, opening up a better data minimization implementation. For example, JSON files allow individual data or a subset to be shared in an encrypted format. It also opens up the implementation of Zero-Knowledge proofs. The W3C also relies on the identifier and private-public key infrastructures to decentralize the archetype and share information tamperproof. Although promising users more control over their personal secrets, eIDAS lacks a data minimization strategy. Digital certificates do not meet the required level of flexibility to send isolated data. The eIDAS is slowly converging towards a more privacy-enhancing platform similar to the industry offerings. Meanwhile, working groups and practitioners provide valuable solutions for data minimization based on verifiable credentials. However, they still need a governance framework, as shown by the Trust Over IP model (TOIP). Thus, it is desirable that shortly their vision (private and public sectors) might converge towards a common platform for data minimization that unleashes the need of citizens while fostering economies.

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Measuring Data Access and Re-use in the European Legal Framework for Data, from the GDPR to the Proposed Data Act: the Case of Vehicle Data

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Abstract

This article delves into the difficulties and opportunities associated with the acquisition, sharing, and re-purposing of vehicle data, particularly information derived from black boxes used by insurance companies and event data recorders installed by manufacturers. While this data is usually utilized by insurers and car makers, it may benefit consumers, rival firms, and public institutions profiting from access to data for objectives such as data portability between insurance companies, traffic and transportation management, and the development of intelligent mobility solutions. Among other regulations, the authors examine the proposed Data Act as the European chosen champion to address the legal and technical hurdles surrounding the reuse of privately held corporate data, including privacy and intellectual property, competition, and data interoperability issues. The text also offers an overview of the sorts of data obtained through vehicle recording systems and their potential benefits for various stakeholders. This paper presents a methodology for comparing and evaluating, in an ordinal fashion, the degree of access conferred by various regulations and put it to practical use to assess how much data is currently left out from access by the existing legislation, how much of such data is covered by the Data Act, and ultimately, how much still remains inaccessible for reuse.

Keywords: Data Portability, Data Reuse, Data Governance, Event Data Recorder, Access to Vehicle Data

1 Introduction

It is a common industry practice that insurance companies collect people's driving and vehicle usage data in cars' black boxes to better tailor their insurance packages and services [1], as well as evaluate and manage their own financial risks [2]. Additionally, recent international (UN) [3] and European regulations [4] require car manufacturers to install Event Data Recorders ('EDR') to improve safety. In both cases, the more accurate the data, the better its quality, and the better the business decision-making based on the information mined from the car's "sensing systems".

These qualitatively sound datasets so created are normally used for the commercial benefit of either the insurance company or car manufacturer alone [5] and have no envisaged secondary use for the individual, the market, or the public[6]. However, as is also highlighted by the European Commission in the Access to Vehicle Data initiative,¹ all such parties are potential stakeholders of the rich datasets and have multiple interests in their access and re-use. The after-sales economic potential in the re-use of such data is substantial, both in economic and social terms [7]. Consumers might want to port data demonstrating their good driving habits to another insurance company and get better offers for insurance premiums and policy coverage. On the other hand, approaching the situation from a commercial perspective competing insurance companies could through using these datasets avoid costly processes such as data collection, analysis, and profiling of new customers. Additionally, public bodies such as municipalities could use these privately held datasets to perform public-purpose tasks, such as traffic and public transportation management, but also combine them with other available datasets and develop new smart mobility solutions for neighbouring public purposes, such as combating pollution.

Meanwhile, the development of the Internet of Things ("IoT") systems and market uptake of connected cars keeps changing the paradigm from quasi-ownership of data by insurance companies and data holdership by cars manufacturers, to also Internet Service Providers ("ISPs"), software developers, along with changes in the power structures of the market and brokerage for such data.

It is evident how the digital economy is evolving along with new technologies, but its need for quality data has remained unanswered. In fact, access and re-use of privately held data are hindered by legal issues of privacy, data protection, intellectual property, competition, and technical issues of data such as data formats as well as services interoperability.

Nowadays, challenges related to data access are being tackled by legal instruments such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation and the Database Directive. These instruments define the rights of data subjects regarding their personal data and

¹See the EC Call for Evidence for an Impact Assessment "Access to vehicle data, functions and resources", Ref. Ares(2022)2302201 - 29/03/2022

provide exclusive ownership rights to database producers, yet simultaneously facilitate and restrict access to data depending on relational circumstances [7, p. 20].

To the same challenges, the proposed Data Act puts forward solutions ranging from clarifying rules on data sharing, individuating venues for defining portability and interoperability of data and services and creating new access rights. As for the latter, we are particularly interested in the implications of the newly formulated specification of the Business-to-Government (“B2G”) data-sharing exception (recital 58 of the second presidency compromise text) where a public sector body can ask for access to privately held data is in charge of a specific task in the public interest “related to local transport or city planning, improving infrastructural services (...), or producing reliable and up to date statistics”.

This research paper focuses on examining the feasibility of the Data Act in relation to the access and portability of consumers’ personal driving data. Specifically, we analyze the legal and technical obstacles presented by the proposed legislation, with a particular emphasis on the potential hindrances to the complete re-usability of privately held business data.

1.1 Methodology, Research Objectives and Structure

The primary goal of this study is to assess the effectiveness of the current legal framework in the European Union regarding data access and reuse, in comparison to what is envisioned in the data strategy. Specifically, the study focuses on access and reuse of data from insurance-owned blackboxes and manufacturers’ owned event data recorders.

To achieve this objective, Section 2 focuses on the in-depth analysis of the process of identifying, analyzing, and categorizing vehicle data records, clustered into "data elements" (Driver Data, Vehicle Data, and Else Data as defined in Section 2.1) Section 3 identifies the three primary stakeholders, namely individual users or consumers of digital services, businesses, and public sector bodies, interested in accessing and reusing data over which they have no practical control.² Section 4 then examines the relevant articles in the GDPR, FFNPD Regulation, and Open Data Directive to identify provisions that establish rights, or provide access and reuse opportunities for each stakeholder. This initial step enables to reach the first Milestone that is, to determine the extent to which data recorded in black boxes or event data recorders, can be accessed through existing legal mechanisms. Furthermore, in order to obtain a more precise measurement of the access, the latter is subdivided into the four fundamental operations of Create, Read, Update, and Delete (CRUD) that are commonly used in relational database management systems (RDBMS) and other software systems that involve data storage and manipulation.³ The CRUD operations are a versatile classification system encompassing a broad range of actions that can be performed on a dataset, however they leave out a few rights, such as that of the individual to request the controller for its data to be downloaded, or sent directly to (as in Art. 20 GDPR)

²For clarity, the entity exercising practical control over a set of data is said to have "holdership".

³The CRUD operations refer to the following actions: Create: Inserting new data records into a database or system; Read: Retrieving existing data records from a database or system; Update: Modifying or updating the existing data records in a database or system; Delete: Removing or deleting data records from a database or system.

another controller, or for the consumer to have any data made accessible by its holder (Art. 3 of the Proposed Data Act).

It can be reasonably assumed that having only the ability to read a specific dataset leads to a lower level of access or control, as compared to the additional capabilities of creating, updating, deleting, downloading, and so forth, which further enhance the level of access. The same holds true for the degree of accessibility, in regards to either some data or all, as well as to first-party and third-party access. Therefore, utilizing this framework, the evaluation of the extent of control can be achieved not much through numerical values, but via comparative analysis, which is referred to as "ordinal" categorization (greater than, smaller than, equal to, etc.). In other words, it enables the evaluation of whether a new legal text confers greater or lesser "access" authority to a stakeholder.

Section 5 then analyzes the Data Act to ascertain the extent to which it further extends the scope of data access and use per stakeholder for each Data Element, which constitutes the second Milestone. Section 6 covers promising research areas that have not been extensively discussed. These areas include topics such as competition, data governance and markets, and quality of data. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper, summarizing the key findings and providing suggestions for future research directions.

In this paper we have developed a standardized schema to determine which stakeholder has access to what data and for what specific purpose (*see Annex ??*). The schema helps to streamline and enhance the understanding of access regimes while facilitating the creation of a machine-readable version for easier automation or embedding into software. By adopting this schema, the authors aim to provide a practical solution for enhancing data access and reuse while improving transparency and accountability in the process.

In summary, this study adopts a systematic approach to evaluate the extent to which the existing EU legal framework on data delivers on the promise of access and reuse of data as outlined in the data strategy. The comprehensive methodology involves identifying stakeholders, examining relevant data regulations, analyzing the data act, evaluating remaining data, and creating a standardized schema for enhanced understanding and automation. The study provides valuable insights and recommendations for enhancing data access and reuse while improving transparency and accountability in the process.

1.2 Structure of the Paper

2 Datasets of Vehicle Data

This section of the paper focuses on the process of individuating, analyzing, and classifying vehicles' data collection mechanisms, which are datasets comprising information captured by the recording systems integrated into the vehicle.

This analysis includes an examination of data obtained from two types of recording systems: insurance-based black boxes (iBBs) and manufacturer-installed event data recorders (mEDRs). While these systems are similar in terms of their technological aspects, the legal and economic implications associated with them are quite distinct.

In terms of the individuation of data collected by recording systems, Annex 4 of the "UN Regulation No. 160: Uniform provisions concerning the approval of motor vehicles with regard to the Event Data Recorder" ("EDR Regulation") presents a comprehensive inventory of the required data to be recorded by the system in the event of specific incidents. The list of data is quite detailed, and each individual data point has the potential to yield valuable insights for various purposes and stakeholders.

2.1 Clusters of Data Elements

In the EDR Regulation [3], Annex 4 lists 41 data elements that the recorder collects when the specific event happens ("triggering event"). Data elements range from the indicated speed of the vehicle, the percentage of engine throttle, the status of the driver's safety belt (not/fastened), the time to deploy the frontal air bag, the normal, lateral and latitudinal accelerations, to unusual accelerations in any direction, the ABS activity, the status of the stability control, through the seat track position of the driver, the front or driver passenger occupant size classification (adult, female, child) and so on. The reason for listing so many of the data elements is to show that each element can be used, alone or jointly, to prove, infer and support information about the situation around a driving episode. Noteworthy information about such situations could relate to individuals in the car, such as that there was a child in it or that the driver was presumably drunk, or relate to the car itself, such as that the car malfunctioned at the time of the accident, was hit from this and not that angle or it was first hit in the front and then in the back.

While it would certainly be of research interest to link each data element to a particular use case for stakeholders, to maintain brevity and stay within the scope of this paper, it opted to group the data into three main categories: data that pertain to the driver ("Driver Data"), data that pertain to the vehicle systems ("Vehicle Data"), and data that pertain to external factors, such as other vehicles, people, environment, traffic, and so on ("Else Data"). The data elements have been grouped into the aforementioned categories in accordance with rules to ensure that the categories are comprehensive and encompass not only data generated by driver actions or by the vehicle independently, but also data that can provide insights about the driver, the vehicle, or external factors (such as the driver's state of mind inferred from accelerations or sudden brakes). It is important to note that a single data element can belong to multiple categories. For instance, it is possible to draw inferences about the vehicle's status from the driver's behaviours (such as constant braking due to strange acceleration), and also draw inferences about the driver's state from the vehicle's functioning (such as frequent lane corrections).

2.2 Black Boxes

As of July 2022, all cars produced in the European Union are required to be equipped with an Event Data Recorder (mEDR). The technical specifications of these devices are governed by UN Regulation No. 160,⁴ which sets forth the types of data to be recorded

⁴Agreement Concerning the Adoption of Harmonized Technical United Nations Regulations for Wheeled Vehicles, Equipment and Parts which can be Fitted and/or be Used on Wheeled Vehicles and the Conditions for Reciprocal Recognition of Approvals Granted on the Basis of these United Nations Regulations*

by the mEDR and the events that trigger solid-state recordings. In addition, there are regulations and communications at the EU level, including Directive 85/374/CEE, Regulation (EU) 2019/2144, and the C-ITS Communication, which establishes requirements for motor vehicle safety and the protection of vehicle occupants and vulnerable road users.⁵

Until now, the practice has seen some car insurers propose—and in some cases require—their users to install insurance Black Boxes to facilitate a personalized insurance premium. The installation of iBBs in cars entails that data is collected by insurance companies, and it is important to understand the legal and privacy implications of such data collection.

An iBB refers to a data recorder that insurance companies install in customers' cars. The data collected by the iBB is under the possession of the insurance company (the *de facto* holder). The legal basis for the installation of iBBs is contractual, and the purpose of their installation is in the interest of the insurance company.

Although the iBB can potentially collect a vast array of data, privacy regulations such as the US Driver Privacy Act, general data governance regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation ("GDPR"), special regulations such as the ePrivacy Directive or Database Directive, other EU vertical regulations specific to vehicles and digital systems,⁶ and more, restrict the scope of data that can be collected, accessed, processed, and shared. In addition to, and complementing legal obligations and duties, there are security and product requirements playing a role in such access landscape. For instance, to comply with data minimization principles, iBBs must implement technical controls to allow for storage of only relevant event data in solid-state memory, while the rest of the non-relevant data is stored and overwritten in volatile memory.

This complex system of legal and practical access causes that, although insurance companies have material possession of the iBB datasets, their access to data is only granted for legitimate reasons. Consumers, on the other hand, who are not in practical possession of the iBB data, can exert rights over them, although in a limited fashion and only to a certain extent.

In summary, the use of iBBs for car insurance purposes presents a balancing act between the potential benefits of lower premiums for consumers and the potential loss

(Revision 3, including the amendments which entered into force on 14 September 2017) Addendum 159 – UN Regulation No. 160 Date of entry into force as an annexe to the 1958 Agreement: 30 September 2021 Uniform provisions concerning the approval of motor vehicles with regard to the Event Data Recorder This document is meant purely as a documentation tool. The authentic and legally binding text is ECE/TRANS/WP.29/2020/123/Rev.1.

⁵Dir. 85/374/CEE;
Art 6 REGULATION (EU) 2019/2144 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 November 2019 on type-approval requirements for motor vehicles and their trailers, and systems, components and separate technical units intended for such vehicles, as regards their general safety and the protection of vehicle occupants and vulnerable road users, amending Regulation (EU) 2018/858 of the European Parliament and of the Council. Similarly, *see* the C-ITS Communication.

⁶For instance: COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2022/1426 of 5 August 2022 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards uniform procedures and technical specifications for the type-approval of the automated driving system (ADS) of fully automated vehicles; COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) 2022/545 of 26 January 2022 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council by laying down detailed rules concerning the specific test procedures and technical requirements for the type-approval of motor vehicles with regard to their event data recorder and for the type-approval of those systems as separate technical units and amending Annex II to that Regulation

of autonomy. It is important to adhere to data protection principles while ensuring that the legitimate interests of both parties are maintained.

2.3 Event Data Recorder

There are several differences between iBBs and mEDRs that are relevant when examining the data collected by these devices.

The first one is that mEDRs are installed directly by car manufacturers, and the data collected by these devices are held by them, while in contrast, iBBs are installed by insurance companies for the purpose of tracking and monitoring the use of a specific vehicle.

Secondly, while the iBBs are primarily installed for insurance purposes, mEDRs are installed for safety reasons. This reflects directly on the amount of data that is collected by each device. The amount of data collected by mEDRs is larger than the iBBs since it collects mostly Driver Data with the purpose of determining the driver's risk profile, or Vehicle Data, to analyse the correct functioning of the vehicle. Although, the collection of data by both iBBs and mEDRs is subject to data protection regulations, such as the GDPR and other EU vertical regulations that are specific to vehicle data.

Thirdly, currently, the access rights of manufacturers are restricted to mEDR data while insurance companies' access rights are restricted to iBB's data they installed since these mechanisms are not interconnected while they can co-exist. Additionally, car owners typically have limited rights over mEDR data which may vary depending on the specific legislation which will be further analyzed.

3 Stakeholders and their Purposes to Access Vehicle Data

This section will focus on an examination of the interests of three key stakeholders who are interested in accessing the data stored in the iBB or mEDR - consumers, businesses, and public bodies. For each of these categories, the interests of both the single, first-party entities – such as a consumer who owns an insurance contract or a car manufacturer–, and third-party entities – for instance, consumer associations or rival insurance companies – will be evaluated.

3.1 Particular Data and Aggregated Data

In the context of stakeholder engagement, the data types that will be examined come in two distinct forms: personal/individual, which will be referred as "particular data," and aggregated data. Namely, Particular data refers to information that is useful only in the context of a specific instance, such as a specific person, vehicle, or contract. For instance, the consumer data associated with iBB is essential in its individual form for the consumer, insurance companies, the car manufacturer, and other stakeholders involved in that specific instance. Aggregated data, on the other hand, refers to information that is beneficial when analyzed in a collective form, typically for statistical or evidential purposes. This may include collections of anonymized mEDRs datasets

that are used for traffic management or consumer class actions against a faulty car manufacturer.

3.2 Granularity and Quality of Datasets

The quantity of data necessary to fulfil the demands of each stakeholder can fluctuate based on the particular circumstances at hand.

When considering data quality and granularity in the context of GDPR's portability principle and the principle of informational self-determination,⁷ it is important to recognize that the right to access data has subjective connotations. For instance, under Article 20 of the GDPR, individuals have the right to selectively port data based on their subjective preferences [8, 9]. However, exercising this right to its full extent without considering the broader context can lead to adverse outcomes. For instance, if an individual chooses to port only their driving performance data but not data related to alcohol detection, it could create an imbalanced picture of their overall risk profile as a driver, resulting in subjective and distorted reality and reintroducing information asymmetries [10] that data recorders are supposed to reduce [2].

Similarly, there may be situations where an individual wants to sell a car embedded with mEDR data related to malfunctions, but only selectively ports certain data, potentially compromising the safety of the next owner. Thus, it is necessary to find a solution that balances the individual's right to informational self-determination with considerations of good faith and fairness towards the recipient of the ported data, as well as public safety.

In addressing this issue, the concept of data quality is crucial. If data quality is understood in GDPR terms as the accuracy of data,⁸ and based on standardized metrics, then selectively ported data may still be considered accurate and qualitatively sound. However, if data quality is defined as accuracy in describing truth, then porting all relevant data may be necessary in some cases. Ultimately, a nuanced approach is needed to ensure that the right to portability is exercised responsibly and in a manner that does not compromise important interests such as safety and fairness.

It is worth noting that recent policy developments in the concept of portability have shifted from a right to selectively port personal data,⁹ to more open forms of system interoperability.¹⁰ When the shift is materialized in the text of the Data Act and the Common European Data Spaces, it might address the issue of distortion by reducing subjectivity and promoting greater transparency and accuracy, therefore quality, in the data being shared.

⁷The existence of "informational privacy" and a "right to informational self-determination" as deriving from the fundamental right to respect for personality was first recognised in the decision of the German Federal Constitutional Court in the Volkszählungsurteil, BVerfGE Bd. 65, S. 1ff in 1983 https://web.archive.org/web/20101116085553/http://zensus2011.de/fileadmin/material/pdf/gesetze/volkszaehlunsurteil_1983.pdf

⁸Corrected, modified, and updated as and when necessary and erased when inaccurate according to GDPR Article 5,1(c)

⁹As it was in the GPDR

¹⁰As it is now in the Data Act and in the Common European Data Spaces

3.3 Further Uses of EDR Data

The following section will focus on a non-exhaustive analysis of the reasons why each of the above-mentioned stakeholders may have an interest to access or in further using particular and aggregated data collected by both mEDRs and iBBs.

3.3.1 Individuals: Consumers and Collectives

For individuals, accessing mEDR data can provide valuable information about a car's history and potential issues. For example, an individual as the consumer may choose those own mEDR data that depict a "good driver" picture, and transfer them to their next insurer in order to obtain a lower premium. Additionally, when considering purchasing a second-hand car, a consumer may access the mEDR data of the vehicle to determine whether it has been in accidents, required significant maintenance, or is subject to potential malfunctions. This information can inform the consumer's decision-making process and potentially be used as a bargaining tool in price negotiations. It is important to note that in this scenario, the data is being accessed by an individual other than the original car owner.

Consumer associations can also make use of aggregated EDR data in a number of ways. For example, EDR data can be used to initiate legal action under National Consumer's Law for the recall and withdrawal of faulty cars or car parts (f.i., in Italian law). European class action lawsuits may also be informed by aggregated EDR data, providing evidence of widespread issues that affect a large number of consumers. Additionally, consumer associations may analyze EDR data to investigate whether anticompetitive practices, such as the use of a specific brand of tires, are in place. This information can be used to advocate for fair competition and protect consumers from potential harm.

3.3.2 Businesses: Insurances and Car Manufacturers

The use of EDR data by businesses is measured on a carefully balanced scale, while there is a commercial need for the businesses to access EDR data and the businesses who primarily collect, organise and process such data have sui-generis database rights to such data, it is imperative for businesses to not only respect the fundamental right to privacy and data protection but comply with industry standards when it comes to deploying privacy-preserving techniques ("PPT"). The use of appropriate privacy preservation techniques is crucial for the protection of personal data while carrying out data processing, especially in cases where the end result is focused on using such data processing to create training and validation datasets for AI-based functions. It is crucial to appreciate the delicate balance between the fundamental right to data protection enforced through the use of PPTs and the subsequent Fundamental Freedom to Conduct a Business enshrined in Article 16 of the Charter, which is directly impacted by the intellectual property rights and protections awarded to businesses. Therefore, once again, delicate need to balance the Fundamental Rights and Fundamental Freedom emanates, as an overarching focus on either the fundamental right to data protection or the fundamental freedom to conduct a business adversely affects the other. For instance, sui generis databases (as discussed before) that utilize personal

data as the content they collect and organize, may be protected through intellectual property rights, however, this does not exempt the creators of such a database from adhering to personal data protection laws. However, at the same time, the data protection regulatory framework does not bar the creation of a sui generis database based on validly collected and processed personal data [11]. However, in the event such a balance between Intellectual Property Rights and Data Protection rights were not maintained, it would create a chilling effect on both the Fundamental Right to Data Protection as well as the Fundamental Freedom to Conduct a Business, therefore leading to either an economic gridlock or the rampant violation of the Right to Privacy in the garb of exercising intellectual property rights.

There is a wide array of businesses to which EDR data is of crucial importance, however for the purposes of this paper, the investigation is limited to Insurance Businesses and businesses oriented around car manufacturing (including businesses involved in the refurbishment of vehicles).

Insurance Providers:

The processing of EDR data offers insurance providers several opportunities to enhance their operations and decision-making processes. By leveraging this data, insurers can achieve various objectives [12].

Firstly, insurance companies can utilize EDR data, which includes information about driving styles and the number of drivers associated with a specific vehicle, to calculate premiums more accurately. This data allows them to assess driver profiles and determine risk levels more effectively [13].

Furthermore, EDR data can serve as valuable evidence in legal proceedings, enabling insurance providers to contest claims of insurance denial. The data can be presented in court to support or refute allegations made by policyholders. Another advantage of EDR data is the ability to distinguish between regular wear and tear on a vehicle and damages resulting from accidents. By analyzing the data, insurers can evaluate the impact of these factors on vehicle performance and determine the appropriate coverage and claim settlements accordingly [14].

Moreover, insurance companies can identify market trends by analyzing the evolving driving data derived from EDRs. By detecting patterns or shifts in specific technical issues that suggest foul play, insurers can adjust their policies to exclude coverage for damages related to such issues, thereby mitigating potential fraudulent claims

In addition, EDR data enables insurers to create tailored insurance policies based on the number of drivers and behavioural data collected. If the data reveals multiple drivers for a particular vehicle, the insurance provider can adjust or suspend certain features of the coverage to align with the associated risks. Furthermore, insurance providers can leverage EDR data to evaluate the risk profile of potential new customers efficiently. This data allows them to assess the driving habits and behaviour of individuals without requiring lengthy profiling processes, enabling faster underwriting decisions.

Lastly, access to aggregated EDR data from vehicles of the same brand and make empowers insurance providers to evaluate if specific car models exhibit manufacturing problems that increase the risks of accidents. This knowledge can guide insurers in adjusting their pricing, coverage, and risk assessment for these particular models.

Car Manufacturing Companies:

The EDR data holds crucial significance in the car manufacturing industry, as it offers valuable insights that find multiple applications.

These applications include tracking vehicular performance, monitoring car servicing timelines based on recorded wear and tear, and providing emergency services in cases of accidents or unexpected breakdowns.

Additionally, the data helps in detecting warranty tampering of the engine and other car parts, as well as calculating repair and refurbishment costs. It also serves as a valuable resource for research and development purposes.

Furthermore, the EDR data can be utilized as evidence in legal proceedings, particularly in lawsuits involving claims related to manufacturing defects.

Lastly, it facilitates swift resolution of technical issues when the car manufacturing company employs hardware or software components similar to those experiencing malfunctions in vehicles from other manufacturers.

3.3.3 Public Bodies

With the digitization of governments and the interconnection of public databases, public sector bodies can benefit greatly from the use of EDR data, especially Vehicle Data and Else Data both in Aggregated and Particular forms. The use of such data can result in substantial cost savings for society, avoiding repeated collection that could generate the same results, and extracting more value off of the same data for public purposes, such as traffic management since the public sector is not able to collect this amount of data by itself.

Therefore, the next sections will explore potential uses of EDR data by the public sector.

As previously mentioned, Event Data Recorders (EDRs) are devices installed in vehicles to record technical information for a brief period before, during and after a triggering event, which is normally a car crash. Taking inspiration from the United States, Section 2 (4) of the Driver Privacy Act of 2015, EDR data can be used for the purposes of determining the need for, or facilitating, emergency medical response in response to a motor vehicle crash. According to the US Center for Preparedness and Response (CDC), EDR data can be an essential tool to assist emergency care partners to prioritize goals and objectives that advance the use and geographic coverage of current vital records systems to improve vital records data timeliness, quality, and access.¹¹ Thus, it is understandable that the data from EDRs can be used by the public sector to facilitate the management and planning of emergency medical personnel adapted to specific areas.

¹¹ 2019-2024 Public Health Emergency Preparedness (PHEP) Notice of Funding Opportunity – Supplemental Guidance and Resources, by Center of Preparedness and Response (CDC)

Municipalities, especially the ones that adopt the name of "smart city" often want to improve municipal traffic management through the collection and use of data. Taking inspiration from Montana's regulation on Recorded Data¹², EDR data might be retrieved or used in for the purposes of improving traffic management with the condition that the identity of the owner or driver is not disclosed in connection with that retrieved data.

As Abdulhafedh points out, this data might be valuable for the making of a traffic management plan, which can include data from vehicle accidents that have occurred in a specific area. With this data it is possible to track if the road or the traffic environment contributed to the accident, shaping future public policy on road management and future design of a safer road infrastructure [15].

The introduction of event data recorders storing a range of crucial anonymised vehicle data, accompanied by requirements for data range, accuracy, resolution and for its collection, storage and retrievability over a short period before, during and immediately after collision (for example, triggered by the deployment of an airbag) is a valuable step in obtaining more accurate, in-depth accident data. All motor vehicles should therefore be required to be equipped with such recorders. These recorders should be capable of recording and storing data in such a way that the data can only be used by Member States to conduct road safety analysis and assess the effectiveness of specific measures taken without the possibility of identifying the owner or the holder of a particular vehicle on the basis of the stored data.

The most common exception for the retrieval or use of EDR data is for the purpose of an investigation. As Hampton et al., point out, the use of EDR data has the potential to provide an independent measurement of crash severity allowing an easier accident reconstruction for the purposes of investigations [16]. Automobile event data recorders hold data that is crucial to court proceedings and can be a reliable source of evidence for court proceedings related to collisions [17]. In United States legislation, this exception is located in the Driver Privacy Act of 2015, Section 2 (3). As previously mentioned, so far 17 states in the United States¹³ have enacted statutes relating to event data recorders and privacy, while in others although the topic has not been legislatively addressed, interesting Court rulings were issued on the topic of EDR and privacy.¹⁴

In the case of investigations, when a court orders the retrieval or the use of data or within the context of an investigation, the data from the EDR might be used, even without the consent of the vehicle's owner.

When it comes to the EU, EDR regulation came later, in 2019 with Regulation (EU) 2019/2144. However, contrary to the US legislation, according to Article 6, (4) d) EU EDR data collection is limited to the purposes of accident research and analysis

¹²Administrative Rules of Montana (ARM) Section 2.6.203 "authorized drivers and uses"

¹³Namely Arkansas, California, Colorado, Connecticut, Delaware, Maine, Montana, Nevada, New Hampshire, New Jersey, New York, North Dakota, Oregon, Texas, Utah, Virginia, and Washington

¹⁴State v. Worsham, 227 So. 3d 602 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 2017) in this case, the Fourth District Court of Appeal of Florida, ruled that data recorded by an EDR may not be accessed by anyone other than the owner of the vehicle, comparing the EDR box to other electronic storage devices that require a warrant to search. In State v. West, 548 S.W. 3d 406, the Missouri Court of Appeals reinforced the position that law enforcement investigations require a warrant to search and seize the EDR data.

not liability in cases of vehicle accident investigations. Therefore, the US EDR federal legislation is broader and has more application possibilities than the EU one.

The Public sector also may access EDR data for the purposes of vehicle safety research, this is an essential use for this data since traffic accidents are one of the major causes of death in the world. For instance, Event Data Recorders provide accurate data on driver's use of seat belts during vehicular crashes, data that is more reliable than drivers' statements. Through the use of this data, it is possible to conduct research on the use of seat belts and skew estimates of the effectiveness of seat belts in reducing fatalities and injuries [18, 19]. This is the main purpose of the EU Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 which has its main focus on accident research and analysis.

EDR data also can be valuable data for statistical purposes, through the aggregation of data, statistics can be made on traffic accidents. Statistics can be made by the Municipal Data Office (based on Article 15(c) of the Data Act Proposal and Recital 162 GDPR), by the Member State Statistical Office (based on Member State Statistical Regulation) and also by the Statistical Office of the European Communities (based on the EU Regulation 223/2009). Statistics on vehicle accidents also fall under the scope of the EU Regulation (EU) 2019/2144, since its main focus is accident research and analysis.

Following this non-exhaustive analysis of the possible interests of each stakeholder to both access and port data, in the following sections, this study will focus on the legal analysis which will either permit or block data access.

4 Legal Bases to Access Vehicle Data: Legal Enablers *De Lege Lata*

The present section will concentrate on the analysis of the legal mechanisms that might enable the access and use of mEDRs and iBBs data according to the interests presented in the previous section. To do so, this section will be divided into three main horizontal regulations regarding data, namely the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation (FFNPD), and The Open Data Directive (ODD).

These already existent legal mechanisms allow certain interested parties, under specific circumstances, to access particular types of data, as long as the data is processed according to established rules. Yet, the sheer number of stakeholders, available data, and potential use cases have resulted in a massive backlog of unfulfilled requests under the current access regimes—which begged for the ideation of the Data Strategy.

Therefore, to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the current legal framework and realize the full potential of the Data Strategy, it is crucial to analyze the scope of the data access gap, including the existing access rights and possible obstacles that hinder the reuse of data. By doing so, insights can be gained into what measures might be taken to bridge the access gap and facilitate the secure and responsible sharing of data.

In this analysis, any use of the EDR data that goes beyond that for which the data was collected is by definition a "further use". When the purpose for the use of the data changes, so does the legal basis for its processing.

4.1 GDPR

4.1.1 Individuals in GDPR

This subsection aims to identify provisions within the GDPR that grant individuals access to data stored in iBBs or eMDRs that they would not otherwise be able to obtain. Such data may include an individual's own personal data, which is referred to as a "Subject Access Request," or incidentally to personal and non-personal data of third parties. The term "incidental access" refers to situations where a requesting party seeks access to a personal dataset that is inherently interconnected with the data of others. In these scenarios, conflicting protection mechanisms come into play, granting rights to both parties involved, including the data protection rights of individuals whose data is intertwined. Nevertheless, access may still be permitted if a careful balancing of rights determines it to be justified.

Regarding access to aggregated data, if such data has been anonymized, it is no longer classified as personal data. Therefore, individuals may have access to such data without infringing upon GDPR regulations [20, *contra*].

Taking a high-level view, the expansive definition [21, 22] and broad interpretation of personal data can be viewed as a meta-mechanism for individuals to gain access to information held by third-party private (business) or public (municipality) entities, provided that the individual can be identified through such information. If the definition or interpretation of personal data were narrower, such as including only a person's name, surname, and address, or sensitive data, then access to data held by third parties would be limited to only such evidently personal data, while excluding other types of data, such as observed or inferred data.

According to Article 6,1(f) (Legitimate Interest to Access) the processing of personal data is considered lawful if it is necessary for the legitimate interests of the data controller or a third party, as long as those interests do not override the rights and freedoms of the data subject, especially when the data subject is a child. The legitimate interests of third parties, in the context of GDPR, can refer to situations where another individual who is neither the Data Subject nor the Controller has a justifiable reason to access personal data. In such cases, the Controller may have valid legal grounds to process personal data where it is necessary to fulfil the legitimate interests of the third party.

For example, an individual may have a legitimate interest in accessing the driving records of another person if they are considering renting out their car to someone, such as car dealers who rent cars to Uber drivers. Similarly, if an individual is looking to hire a chauffeur for a family or business trip, they may have a legitimate interest in accessing the driver's personal data to ensure that they are a safe and competent driver. Here, the primary focus lies not on evaluating whether legitimate interests surpass the three-part test involving purpose, necessity, and balancing with the rights and freedoms of others—which depends on the context. Instead, what holds significance is

the acknowledgement that, according to the interpretation of the WP29 and subsequent authorities, nearly any legal interest can be deemed legitimate [23],¹⁵ thereby facilitating access.

According to Article 9,2(f) (Access to Sensitive Data to Exercise Legal Claim), data processing may be necessary in cases where it is required for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims or when courts are acting in their judicial capacity. The described scenario involves an individual acting in the capacity of a controller and making a request to access another person's personal data within a BB, citing a legitimate interest, such as gathering evidence to support a civil liability case. Specifically, accessing Driver Data can reveal whether the driver involved in an accident was under the influence of alcohol or drugs. To comply with the principle of data minimization, the recipient of the data should only have access to information that enables them to make such an inference, which in this case is limited to data collected within a reasonable timeframe following the accident. This requirement should also be reflected in the technical means employed, although it is likely that machines already only collect data in the vicinity of the triggering event.

According to Article 15,1 (Right of Access by the Data Subject) the data subject has the right to request confirmation from the controller regarding whether their personal data is being processed or not. If their data is being processed, they have the right to access that personal data and receive a copy of it. In general, data protection laws give individuals the right to access their own personal data held by a controller. However, as said, there are situations where an individual may request access to his own personal data that incidentally also pertain to someone else. In these cases, the controller must ensure that the data subject's request meets certain criteria before granting access.

One such criterion is that the requested information must also pertain to the data subject. This means that the data subject shall have a valid reason for accessing the information, such as needing it to prove their own involvement in a particular situation, as in the example given of person A accessing their own data to demonstrate that person B was in the car with them. There are plenty of similar examples in the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the European Union, starting with the *Nowak* case admitting the possibility of accessing others' personal data for the need to access their own.¹⁶

Irrespective of the limited range of processing activities available for the personal data of a third party, a controller cannot exclude the data subject's right of access even if their request is based on subsequent rights, such as the right to erasure.

According to Article 16 (Right to Rectification), the data subject has the right to request that any inaccurate personal information about them be corrected by the data controller promptly. Depending on the reasons for the processing, they also have the right to have any incomplete personal information about them completed, which may involve providing additional information to the data controller.

¹⁵ See for example the case C-275/06 *Productores de Música de España (Promusicae) v Telefónica de España SAU*

¹⁶ Case C-434/16, REQUEST for a preliminary ruling under Article 267 TFEU from the Supreme Court (Ireland), made by decision of 29 July 2016, received at the Court on 4 August 2016, in the proceedings *Peter Nowak v Data Protection Commissioner*,

When a data subject makes a rectification request, the activities related to the personal data belonging to both the data subject and a third party are more extensive than those for a simple access request. While the data can be accessed, in the case of incomplete or inaccurate personal data, some of it may need to be created, updated, or deleted. For instance, incomplete personal data may need to be created, inaccurate data may require updating, and any update may require the deletion of previously stored data.

When one ground of a limited list apply, the data subject has the right to request the deletion of their personal data from the controller without undue delay, and the controller must promptly comply with this request (Article 17 - Right to Erasure).

As established by the Google Spain case,¹⁷ individuals have the right to request the erasure of their personal data if the information is inaccurate, inadequate, irrelevant, or excessive for the purposes of data processing. The term "inadequate" may encompass situations where the data is no longer relevant, where consent has been withdrawn without alternative legal grounds for the processing, where processing is unlawful, or where valid objections have been raised.

All data, including links to where the data is available, must be deleted upon request. However, exceptions may apply. For instance, the right to erasure may not be exercised if it would infringe on the rights and freedoms of others. For example, in the case of inextricably mixed datasets, the deletion of personal data may also result in the deletion of other individuals' personal data or other legitimate business data that has been collected and processed.

Article 20 GDPR (Right to Personal Data Portability) has the primary purpose to empower consumers of digital services by preventing lock-ins, facilitating data subjects in the process of switching providers and multi-homing "without hindrance" [24]. It does so by allows individuals to "receive" their personal data, and "transmit" it to another controller. To ensure data interoperability between systems and services, the dataset of personal data must be downloadable in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format.

Experts in the field claim that the Data Portability right can be used in the context of Vehicle Data [5, p. 19]. If the circumstances so allow, the individual has the right to request the original controller to directly transfer the data to a new controller. However, the ease of such transmission is contingent upon certain datasets. Technical limitations may arise where direct porting would impede service functionality, while economic limitations may occur if fulfilling the request proves excessively costly for the controller. Finally, so called "legal limitations" relate to the rights and freedoms of others, especially when third-party data is involved. In cases where businesses have invested resources in the acquisition, transformation, or analysis of personal data belonging to the data subject or other individuals, porting of, for instance, filtered pictures or collages made with proprietary software, private conversations or group pictures may pose challenges. Therefore, the chance of porting third-party data will be determined on a case-by-case basis.

¹⁷ Google Spain SL, Google Inc. v Agencia Española de Protección de Datos [es], Mario Costeja González, Case number C-131/12

Restrictions and Exceptions

The GDPR provides certain exceptions outlined in Articles 85-89. With a valid legal basis, these exceptions permit controllers to process the personal data of a data subject under certain circumstances, such as for exercising their freedom of expression and information for journalistic, academic, or artistic purposes as outlined in Article 85. Additionally, personal data contained in official documents held by public bodies may also be made public to "reconcile public access". In such cases, personal data protection rules safeguard the data of others. These rules create a protective barrier around personal data, making it more difficult for third parties to access and use such information. However, for those seeking access to personal data, these exceptions serve as a means to obtain such information.

Importantly, the exceptions outlined in Article 89 can serve as access points, allowing third parties to penetrate the protective shield surrounding personal data, but only under certain safeguards. Article 89 of the GDPR stipulates that processing personal data for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical purposes must be subject to appropriate safeguards. These safeguards are technical measures that ensure data minimization is observed, such as the use of pseudonymization or anonymization techniques whenever possible. In addition, national laws can include derogations that limit the rights of data subjects for the purpose of public archiving (Articles 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21), or for research and statistics (Articles 15, 16, 18, 21).

Article 23 of the GDPR allows for restrictions to be placed on the rights of data subjects or the obligations of controllers by law when necessary, provided that the restriction respects the essence of the rights and freedoms of data subjects. Recital 79 provides further clarification, stating that restrictions may be imposed by Union or Member State law on specific principles and rights, such as information, access, rectification or erasure of personal data, the right to data portability, the right to object, decisions based on profiling, communication of a personal data breach to a data subject, and certain related obligations of controllers. These restrictions are only permissible if they are necessary and proportionate in a democratic society to safeguard public security, protect human life, prevent or prosecute criminal offences, execute criminal penalties, safeguard important public interests of the Union or a Member State, including economic or financial interests, maintain public registers, further process archived personal data for specific purposes, or protect the data subject or the rights and freedoms of others, including social protection, public health, and humanitarian purposes. It is important to note that any such restrictions must be in accordance with the requirements set out in the Charter and in the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms.

Finally, Article 21 (Right to Object to Processing) grants data subjects the right to object to the processing of their personal data based on point (e) or (f) of Article 6(1), including profiling based on those provisions, if the objection is related to their particular situation. The controller must stop processing the personal data unless they can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds for the processing that override the interests, rights, and freedoms of the data subject, or for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims.

Technical Blockers

In the case of data portability, the law stipulates that the exercise of such data protection right is dependent on the technical capabilities of the data controller. With regard to the Right to Direct Data Portability, as outlined in Article 20 of the GDPR, the ability to exercise it is contingent upon the technical feasibility of transferring data in a machine-readable format. If the data controller is unable to provide the data in a compatible format, the full exercise of the right to portability may not be possible. From the individual data subject's standpoint, exceptions to the exercise of data protection rights that grant individuals access to their data can be viewed as blockers to such access. However, these same rights can also pose obstacles to access for others, such as data holders willing to aggregate them into larger databases. In such cases, exceptions to the exercise of rights of the data subject become access enablers for third parties.

4.1.2 Businesses in GDPR

The GDPR is a mighty tool when it comes to delineating the contours within which the processing of data must occur. In its provisions, the GDPR alienates the purposes for which the processing of data may be deemed as lawful, Article 6 of the GDPR, which details the lawfulness of processing through a combined reading of its subclauses Article 6(1)(a) and Article 6(1)(c) which state that the processing is deemed lawful if the data subject has provided their consent for processing of data for one or more specific purposes as well as when the processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject, which in this case is directly applicable to businesses since they are bound by contractual legal obligations of the businesses who are processing EDR data for providing services to their clients. The businesses processing EDR data are free to do so in compliance with the provisions of Article 6 of the GDPR (as detailed above), which discusses the lawfulness principles attached to the processing of personal data. In order to duly process the data, the businesses require specific consent from the data subject coupled with the need to process the data in order to perform the obligations under the insurance contracts such as honouring insurance claims and for car manufacturing businesses to provide breakdown maintenance or car servicing notifications [25]. It is evident that there are no specific roadblocks in the processing of EDR data and free but regulated access to the same is provided under the provisions of the GDPR. Further, through the provisions of Article 9 of the GDPR we see that car manufacturing businesses, through the EDR data can act as a link between their customers and emergency responders [?] in case of accidents and therefore, the processing of special categories of personal data is allowed under Article 9(2)(c) of the GDPR. Further, Article 9(2)(f): Although, EDRs are seldom found to include special categories of personal data, the use of EDR data will be legally allowed under the GDPR if such data has to be used in order to indicate a certain fact or behavioural pattern in courts (as illustrated in the use cases held in Section 3.2.2 where insurance companies and car manufacturers may use EDR data as evidentiary support in a court of law).

Contrary to provisions which illustrate the enablement of processing EDR data by Car manufacturing companies and businesses, the GDPR through its provisions also lays down a set of reasonable restrictions when it comes to the processing of personal

data which may be held in the EDR dataset. Transparency has been a central feature of the EU data protection law, it is about engendering trust in the processes which affect the citizen by enabling them to understand, and if necessary, challenge those processes. As a part of the provisions of the GDPR under Article 5(1)(a) in addition to the requirements that data must be processed lawfully and fairly, transparency is now included as a fundamental aspect of these principles.¹⁸ Further, Article 5(1)(c) which harbours the data minimization principle might also be invoked as a technical blocker when it comes to the processing of EDR-based personal data by businesses [26]. Further, Article 17 of the GDPR provides a data subject with the Right to be forgotten and in turn, the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of the personal data, therefore, requiring the personal data contained within the EDR being processed by the businesses to be removed from the dataset, required to create insights [27]. The GDPR also lays down a few restrictive rights such as the Right to restriction of processing under Article 18, this provision allows for the data subject, in the present case the consumer to allow for the restriction of processing their personal data in the event, one of the conditions laid down in the provision of Article 18 is met. In the present case, in the event the consumer decides against the use of services of a particular business, they may require a restriction on the processing of personal data under Article 18,1(d) [28]. Additionally, the right to data portability which is contained in Article 20 of the GDPR, allows the customer the freedom of choice to decide to port their personal data to another business and therefore requires the Right to Data portability to be exercised, which would indubitably set into motion a restriction on the processing of the customer's personal data by the business which is the primary custodian of their personal data and is obligated to port their customer's personal data to another business at the direction of the customer [29]. In addition to the right to data portability, the GDPR also provides the data subjects the right to object under Article 21 and in this case, it empowers the customer to exercise their right to object against the processing of personal data based on the grounds held in Article 6(1)(e) or Article 6(1)(f) which, incidentally is also one of the enablers of the personal data processing, under the GDPR [30]. Lastly, the GDPR under Article 22, which details the legal obligations concerning automated individual decision-making (including profiling), acts as a crucial and indispensable guard-rail against the practice of automated decision-making and empowers the customers whose EDR dataset is being collected to object against being subjected solely to automated decision-making processes fueled through the processing of their personal data [28].

4.1.3 Public Bodies in GDPR

This segment aims to make an analysis of the GDPR provisions that enable access to personal data by Public Bodies. Due to the multiple legal systems and administrative organisations in the EU, the term "public bodies" is used in a broader sense, which might have different interpretations depending on local understanding.

¹⁸The Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (WP 29) published the final Guidelines on Consent under Regulation 2016/679 adopted on 29 November 2017

The analysis of the GDPR was done both article by article but also in a holistic manner which allows this exploration to observe the underlying principles and objectives of the regulation. The first article that is relevant to the analysis is the legal basis for processing which is located in Article 6,1(c) GDPR. Throughout the analysis, it is possible to observe that the public sector might have access to the eMDR recorder driver data for legal obligation purposes if this legal obligation originates directly from Member State law. Thus, in the hypothesis that a Member State enacts a law that obliges the sharing of EDR data with the public sector. It is important to highlight that this law must require a certain processing operation.¹⁹ This legal provision must be clear, precise and define exactly that the public sector will process EDR data for the purposes of compliance with legal obligations.²⁰

The second basis for processing which is pertinent is processing for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest located under Article 6,1(e) GDPR. Under this hypothesis, the public sector might process eMDR data to carry out a task in the public interest. Although the concept of “public interest” might vary on Member States’ legal landscapes, the nature of the eMDR data is essentially linked to the public interest, such as technical inspections, traffic investigations, road management, and many other purposes. Some of these tasks are already outsourced to private entities, for this reason, this legal basis must be interpreted under a functional approach, even if the controller is a public authority, private entity, or publicly owned entity.²¹

Purpose Limitation Principle under Article 5,1(b) GDPR, can be, under certain conditions, a legal blocker for public sector access to personal data. The underlying rationale under this principle is that personal data can only be used for specific purposes, in a transparent, and predictable manner. Predictability is present when further processing is sufficiently related to the original purpose. When it comes to the use of eMDR data, its primal processing is the collection of driving data for insurance purposes and the secondary processing would be for purposes of analysing driving patterns for purposes such as improvement of traffic management, investigation of vehicle accidents, and other general research purposes. Under this analysis, it is possible to observe a sufficient relationship between the original processing of EDR data with the secondary processing purposes.²²

Additionally, this further processing falls under exceptions listed in Articles 5(1)(c) and 6(4) GDPR which are the possible further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical purposes; further processing allowed or required by Union or Member State Law; further processing for a compatible purpose under Article 6(4) GDPR and further processing based on the data subject’s consent.

¹⁹WP29, Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, 844/14/EN, 9 April 2014

²⁰Heberlein, in Ehmann, Selmayr, *Datenschutz-Grundverordnung*, Article 6 GDPR, margin number 15 (C.H. Beck 2018, 2nd Edition)

²¹Buchner, Petri, in Kühling, Buchner, *DS-GVO BDSG*, Article 6 GDPR, margin number 111 (C.H. Beck 2020, 3rd Edition).

²²See Article 29 Data Protection Working Party Opinion 03/2013 on purpose limitation.

4.1.4 Technical Blockers

When it comes to legal blockers, it is relevant to highlight that although the GDPR aims to allow the free flow of personal data under a certain legal basis, it also has put in place principles that aim to give data subject control over the use of their data.

According to the principle of data minimisation located in Article 5,1(c) GDPR, data collected and processed should be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is strictly necessary for relation to the purposes for which they were processed. Therefore, in this case, it must be assessed if the processing of personal data is adequate or appropriate, and relevant for the purpose of the processing. Therefore, this principle might be a blocker for further access to eMDR driver data by the public sector since the further processing of driver's personal data might not be proportionate for the purpose of processing such as traffic management.²³

At last, one possible blocker for the further use of eMDR personal data is Article 12 GDPR, which regulates that the data subject has the right to obtain transparent information, communication, and modalities for the exercise of his/her rights. According to this article, controllers must take the appropriate measures to provide any information referred on Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR. The further processing of data by the public sector also makes the duty of ensuring the rights of the data subject harder, such as the right to erasure. This article is closely related to Recital 60 which poses the obligation to data processors to inform data subjects of the existence of processing operations and their purposes, including the existence of profiling and its consequences.

Further processing of eMDR data also poses a question when it comes to the right of data erasure – under Articles 17 and 19 GDPR – since multiple data processors would have to ensure that personal data are not kept longer than is necessary, making it harder for the data subject to keep track of his or her personal data.

4.2 Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation

4.2.1 Individuals in FFNPD

The lawmaker behind the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation [31] identified that two key barriers to data mobility and the growth of the data economy in the European Union were data localization requirements imposed by Member State authorities and vendor lock-in practices prevalent in the private sector. These factors hindered the effective and efficient functioning of data processing and the development of a harmonized internal market for data-related services.

As per Article 2 of the FFNPD Regulation, there are two distinct categories of individuals who may be interested in accessing data from iBBs or eMDRs. These include "users" and "professional users". The former encompasses a natural person who uses or requests a data processing service. The latter, is to a natural person who uses or requests a data processing service for purposes related to their trade, business, craft, profession, or task.

²³Roßnagel, in Simitis, Hornung, Spieker, Datenschutzrecht, Article 5 GDPR, margin number 119 (NOMOS 2019).

However, the Regulation primarily focuses on promoting the free flow of non-personal data within the European Union and facilitating the switching of cloud service providers for professional users, rather than on individual access to data.

As the aim of this section is to identify provisions that create access rights to individuals, it is important to acknowledge that the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Directive does not directly provide such access rights. While the directive may indirectly facilitate greater availability and accessibility of datasets for individuals through its efforts to promote competition and reduce barriers to entry in the cloud services market, it primarily focuses on promoting the free flow of non-personal data within the European Union and facilitating switching of cloud service providers for professional users.

This could potentially lead to a more open and accessible data ecosystem, with more opportunities for consumer organizations to access data for research, advocacy, and other purposes. While the directive does not guarantee access to data for consumer organizations, it sure creates a more favourable environment for such access to occur.

4.2.2 Businesses in FFNPD

There are no observed legal restrictions under the Free flow of non-personal data regulation which may lead to a restriction in the collection and processing of non-personal EDR data as held by businesses involved in the insurance sector and car manufacturing. In fact, the provisions of the FFNPD through its Article 6 encourage businesses to develop self-regulatory mechanisms such as codes of conduct for the free flow and regulation of the non-personal data in the EU, thereby strengthening the data portability requirements for the non-personal EDR data held by businesses and established an expansive scope of the right to data portability from personal data (as held in the GDPR) to non-personal data [29]. This also has a direct impact on the competition within the various businesses which are involved in using EDR data-which comprises both personal and non-personal data (as explained in section 2.1 of this paper).

4.2.3 Public Bodies in FFNPD

The EU Regulation on Free Flow of Non-personal Data aims to create a borderless EU for the flow of non-personal data, removing obstacles such as data localisation restrictions. Different from the GDPR, the FFNPD only covers non-personal data, which makes the re-use of eMDR data by Public Bodies an easier task. Under Article 5 FFNPD, competent authorities in the public sector have powers to request and obtain access to eMDR data for the performance of their official duties, such as traffic accident investigations and other connected activities. Therefore, taking a holistic interpretation of the GDPR and FFNPD, Public Bodies have the possibility of using both personal and non-personal eMDR data. Additionally, following the underlying principle of liberating the flow of non-personal data within the EU, Article 7 FFNPD creates a procedure for cooperation between authorities, facilitating cooperation between different Member States, this cooperation would eventually facilitate the public sector access to vehicular and else data in an easier manner.

Yet, no blockers were found in the analysis of the FFNPD, which facilitates the main objective of this study which is a joint analysis of multiple regulations for the purposes of further use of eMDR personal and non-personal data, referred to as “particular data”.

4.3 Open Data Directive

4.3.1 Individuals in ODD

The Open Data Directive ("ODD") [32] recognizes the interest of individuals, in their various roles as citizens,²⁴ users, end-users,²⁵ consumers,²⁶ and researchers,²⁷ to gain access to public sector information.

By mandating member states to make all existing documents²⁸ reusable, the directive is effectively creating an opportunity for individuals to access public sector information. This opportunity does not amount to an absolute right as it is subject to restrictions and exceptions.²⁹ This notwithstanding, the likelihood of a scenario where a car manufacturer or an insurance company operates as a public undertaking, and is additionally required to disclose certain data under the auspices of the open data directive, is exceedingly low to the point of being negligible.

4.3.2 Businesses in ODD

The Open Data Directive is a regulation aimed at fostering sharing of data held by Public Sector Bodies of the Member States of the EU, therefore, this regulation finds no application in the schematic concerning the flow of data generated by EDRs of private citizens and accessed by private businesses such as Insurance Companies and car manufacturing businesses[33]. Further, it is noted that the Open Data Directive does not apply to the documents held by companies which hold commercial value such as insights pertaining to business analytics etc., [34]therefore, the insurance companies which appear in the EU’s register of insurance undertakings are exempt from application of the Open Data Directive. Finally, the Open Data Directive also finds no applications towards documents which are excluded from access by virtue of the access regimes in the Member State, including on grounds of commercial confidentiality (including business, professional or company secrets). Therefore, owing to the aforementioned reasons it is concluded that the open data directive has no bearing on the sharing or blocking of EDR-generated data and its use by businesses.

²⁴Recital 8: “Providing that information, which includes dynamic data, in a commonly used electronic format allows citizens and legal entities to find new ways to use them and create new, innovative products and services.”

²⁵Recital 14: “Allowing the re-use of documents held by a public sector body adds value for the benefit of re-users, end users and society in general and in many cases for the benefit of the public sector body itself, by promoting transparency and accountability and by providing feedback from re-users and end users, which allows the public sector body concerned to improve the quality of the information collected and the performance of its tasks.”

²⁶Recital 9: “Public sector information represents an extraordinary source of data that can contribute to improving the internal market and to the development of new applications for consumers and legal entities. Intelligent data usage, including their processing through artificial intelligence applications, can have a transformative effect on all sectors of the economy” ([European Parliament, 2019, p. 2]

²⁷Recital 27

²⁸See Article 1(1)(b) Open Data Directive

²⁹See Recital 23.

4.3.3 Public Bodies in ODD

It was not found any legal enabler or blocker to public sector access to EDR data in the Open Data Directive.

4.4 Milestone 1 (M1): Examining Accessibility of Event Data Recorder Content Through Existing Access Regimes

4.4.1 M1: Individuals

The broad interpretation of personal data in GDPR results in the extension of access rights to a substantial amount of data in an EDR dataset. However, the expansion of these personal rights over data amplifies access solely for the individual, while limiting that of others. This is despite the fact that, from an economic perspective, data is a non-rival good [35, 36], and that data protection regulation aims to promote the free flow of personal data. The reason for this is that the existence of rights to control the flow of information can, in certain cases, lead to the exclusion of others from accessing the data, while in others, significantly limiting its processing. Thus, as the data within an EDR is finite, any increase in the amount of personally identifiable information (the Driver Data) contained in the dataset effectively reduces the number of other types of data, such as Vehicle Data and Else Data categories, along with the access rights to the same dataset of other interested parties. In the broader context of data access, the data subject has progressively more methods to obtain and modify their Driver Data, with an increasing ability to have it modified by the controller. These manipulations generally fall under the CRUD classification, with the exception of data portability where the data subject can request that their data be downloaded or transferred directly to a third party—when technically feasible.

The aforementioned analysis is accurate when referring to individuals' Particular Data. However, in the case of Aggregated Data, the information extrapolated from the EDR no longer can be labelled as Vehicle Data, Driver Data or Else Data, because it loses the characteristics of individuality and identifiability. As such, it can be accessed and utilized by any other relevant stakeholder, for purposes ranging from exercising public tasks to conducting private business, to research, statistics, and so on. Notably, the loss of granularity in data should not necessarily be considered a loss in quality. In fact, the impact on quality can vary depending on the context. For example, in some cases, the aggregation of data can eliminate outliers that may be attributed to data collection errors, resulting in a more refined data set. When EDR data is Aggregated, then rules enhancing the Free-Flow of Non-Personal Data data augment the access regimes, creating a more open and accessible data ecosystem, with opportunities for consumer organizations to access data for research [37], advocacy, and other purposes.

4.4.2 M1: Businesses

The combined regulatory framework concerning data access which includes the above-discussed regulations namely the GDPR, ODD, FFNPD Regulations provides a substantially wide scope for Driver Data access by Businesses engaged in car manufacturing and providing insurance services. The GDPR lays down a regulatory matrix

under which businesses such as car manufacturers and insurance providers are enabled to access, update, port and share the personal data (collectively process) which is included in the EDR dataset. Further, the FFNPD Regulations categorically allow for the processing of the non-personal data held in the EDR dataset through porting of the personal data and non-personal data respectively.

Finally, the Open Data Directive also finds no applications towards documents that are excluded from access by virtue of the access regimes in the Member State, including on grounds of commercial confidentiality (including business, professional, or company secrets). Therefore, owing to the aforementioned reasons it is concluded that the open data directive has no bearing on the sharing or blocking of EDR-generated data and its use by businesses and such vacuum acts as a data access enabler instead of a blocker in the current situation.

Therefore, upon the combined reading of the above-mentioned regulatory matrix, the access regime is focused on providing businesses with unfettered access to both personal and non-personal data contained in the Event Data Recorder.

4.4.3 M1: Public Bodies

Following the previous analysis of the enablers and possible blockers in the already enacted Regulations, namely the GDPR and the FFNPD, it is necessary to reaffirm that the analysis of these regulations cannot be done individually, in fact, they are complementary for a full comprehensible analysis. Therefore, under this premise, it is possible to observe that there is already great room for EDR data access by Public Bodies since the GDPR already provides legal enablers that allow the access of personal data without consent when necessary for the previously mentioned purposes. According to Martens [7], one such example is the collection of road traffic data. Telecom service operators track mobile phones in cars to obtain important data on road traffic patterns. This tracking is a technical requirement to maintain connectivity between the phones and the network antennas. Therefore, the GDPR permits this data collection without consent as it is necessary for the technical operations of the service.

When transposing this example to EDR data and the public sector, the GDPR is clear in delineating a lawful basis for data access and portability for other purposes that can be considered of public interest which will depend on Member State legislation. Furthermore, the GDPR allows for the onward transmission of this data, provided it is anonymised. In the case of road traffic data, the aggregation process must strip the data of any private phone numbers, ensuring that individual users' identities remain protected [7, p. 18].

If not, this processing might be blocked by general principles of the GDPR, especially the principle of data minimisation since the use of drivers' personal data might be considered disproportional for the mentioned purposes. Additionally, the further reuse of personal data might also make it difficult for data subjects to exercise their rights such as the right to erasure.

5 The Proposed Data Act and the Expansion of Access Regimes: Legal Enablers *De Lege Ferenda*

Following the general conclusions of possible mechanisms for data access and portability by each stakeholder, the next section will focus on the Data Act Proposal, which aims to expand data access beyond the above-examined regulations, especially for individual and public sector stakeholders.

The Proposed Data Act is a legal solution put forward by the European Commission to unlock the potential of data-driven innovation in Europe [38]. The Act aims to address the reality that data is a vital component of the digital economy, but much of it remains unused or concentrated in the hands of a few large –American—companies [39]. To unlock this potential, the Data Act provides opportunities for data reuse and removes barriers to the development of the European data economy.

The Data Act facilitates the establishment of governance frameworks and infrastructure, as well as enable data sharing beyond the boundaries of Data Spaces. It is designed to complement the forthcoming European Common Data Spaces (Health, Industrial, Agriculture, Finance, Mobility, Green Deal, Energy, Public Administration, and Skills) which have yet to be fully developed [40]. Future legislation in relevant areas should align with the broad principles outlined in the Data Act to promote horizontal consistency and coherence across the regulatory landscape. In addition, vertical legislation can set more specific rules tailored to address sector-specific regulatory objectives, allowing for targeted and effective regulation.

One such Common European Space is the Common European Mobility Data Space (EMDS), which aims to enable efficient, safe, sustainable, and resilient transportation by facilitating data access, pooling, and sharing. The EMDS will build on existing initiatives and applications related to transport data and will be supported by efforts to enhance interoperability, security, and the availability and provision of data and services. An upcoming communication will provide information about the EMDS and its role in promoting effective transportation.

Until the European Common Data Spaces are established, the Data Act provides a framework for governance and infrastructure related to data sharing, including outside of the boundaries of data spaces. However, access regimes for data that should be governed within specific data spaces are not yet fully defined, leading to uncertainty in how data access and governance is managed for certain sectors until the corresponding data spaces are operationalized.

5.1 Individuals in DA

Chapter II of the Data Act ("Business to Consumer and Business to Business Data Sharing") enhances legal clarity for consumers (and businesses) to access data derived from the products or affiliated services they possess, rent, or lease. In correspondence to such access regimes, manufacturers and designers of digital services are obliged to create products in a manner that facilitates effortless access to data by default, while

data holders have obligations to make data available to third parties upon the request of the user.³⁰

As expressed in the Explanatory Memorandum, the Proposed Data Act expands and complements the right to portability expressed in Article 20 GDPR by granting users the right to access and make available to a third party to *any data* generated by the use of a product or related service, irrespective of its *nature* as personal data, of the distinction between actively provided or *passively observed data*, and irrespective of the *legal basis* of processing. In the context of switching between data processing service covering the same service type, the broadened scope encompasses the portability of "digital assets", which refer to "elements in digital format for which the customer has the right of use, including data, applications, virtual machines and other manifestations of virtualisation technologies, such as containers."

According to Article 3 (Obligation to make data generated by the use of products or related services accessible) of the Data Act, it is mandatory for products to be developed and produced, and for associated services to be provided, in a way that ensures the data produced through their usage is readily accessible to the user in a secure and convenient manner. Additionally, if it is suitable and applicable, the data should be directly available to the user. Such obligations should normally cover the technical specifications and design strategies thanks to which manufacturers and designers develop mEDR.

The requirement set forth in Article 3 entails that the individual user possesses the right to access any data generated by the use of the product or service, irrespective of its nature, and that such data must be made available. The "data-be-made directly accessible", or "direct access" seems to be something more than its GDPR twin that is a mere reading right: The fact that it is not explicitly categorized within the CRUD classification system highlights that the Data Act expands the individual's rights by introducing a novel type of action on the dataset. This serves as a clear illustration of how the Data Act extends beyond conventional CRUD operations and incorporates new rights for individuals regarding their data.

The right of users to access and use data generated by the use of products or related services (Article 4) applies to situations where the generated data is not directly accessible by the user from the product, which applies to any data collected in the mEDR that is not shown to the user through an interface. In such cases, the user has a right to immediate, free, continuous, real-time "data availability". According to Paragraph 3, the data holder and the user have the option to establish measures to safeguard the confidentiality of shared data, particularly concerning third parties. This provision offers a practical solution to the dilemma presented in Article 20 of the GDPR, which stipulates that the transfer of data must not infringe on the rights of third parties. By enabling the data holder and user to agree on measures to protect the data of third parties, this provision allows for the secure transfer of data, even when it involves the information of others. This scenario may arise in cases such as those where data from the mEDR system contains information about individuals other than the user (Else Data) [note: widening of data access and use!]. The expansion of data

³⁰ This Regulation "takes as its starting point the control that the data holder effectively enjoys, de facto or de jure, over data generated by products or related services."

access rights is restricted only in cases where the data is used for developing a product that directly competes with the product from which the data was originally obtained. However, this restriction does not apply if the competing product already exists in the market. This provision may be perceived as a limitation on competition, but it is intended to strike a balance between promoting innovation and protecting the rights of data holders.

Article 5 of the Data Act (Right to share data with third parties) establishes a right that complements and expands upon the right to data portability outlined in the GDPR. This right mandates that, upon request by a user, the data holder must *make available* the data generated through the use of a product or related service to a third party without delay and free of charge, at the same level of quality available to the data holder, and in real-time where relevant. Unlike direct portability, this right to "make data available" to third parties is not dependent on "technical feasibility", making it an unconditional obligation. Moreover, to "make available" is technically less complex than to "transfer" data, thereby easing compliance with the obligation of transferring data to a third party. Furthermore, the right is more comprehensive and specific, leaving less room for the controller to evade compliance. As for Articles 3 and 4, also article 5 seems to be fit for addressing data access requests from a consumer to its own mEDR.

Regarding the expansion of the right to data portability, it is important to note that this right is subject to careful scrutiny due to its impact on competition. Both Article 7 and Article 5.2 should be interpreted in this context. Article 7 excludes small and micro enterprises from the obligation to facilitate data portability in certain circumstances, specifically with respect to business-to-consumer and business-to-business data-sharing obligations [41]. Such exemptions do not apply to data generated by the use of products or related services provided by qualifying micro or small enterprises. Differently, Article 5.2 states that any entity providing core platform services, which have been designated as gatekeepers, cannot be considered an eligible third party for receiving the ported data.

The extension of the data portability right to non-personal data gives rise to a corollary wherein a user requesting data to be ported may not necessarily be a data subject. For instance, this may be the case when a legal entity makes such a request, or when the dataset being transferred contains vehicle data or personal information belonging to a third party. This scenario is acknowledged in Article 5, paragraph 6, which states that "Where the user is not a data subject [...]." This may be considered as an instance of expanding access rights over another individual's data.

Similarly to Chapter 2, Chapter 6 of the Data Act introduces expanded access rights for individuals, and establishes a set of corresponding rights and obligations. Article 23 (Removing obstacles to effective switching between providers of data processing services), for instance, mandates that providers of data processing services ensure that their customers can switch to an alternative processing service that covers the same service type. Furthermore, since the porting of services must ensure "functional equivalence," it is likely that a larger volume of data can be ported under Chapter 6 than under the GDPR, which offers a more limited scope for data portability.

Lastly, addressing cases where the consumer is switching from a data processing service that is not an Infrastructure-as-a-Service type and is not compatible with an open interoperability specification or EU Standard, Article 26 comma 3 (Technical Aspects of Switching) provides a right to the Consumer to “export all data generated or co-generated, including the relevant data formats and data structures, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format.”

5.2 Businesses in DA

The proposed Data Act in Article 3 (Obligation to make data generated by the use of products or related services accessible) states the requirement of product manufacturers which include car manufacturers that fit their vehicles with EDRs to ensure that the data generated by their product is accessible by the user, which in turn may allow for the user to port or share such data with other businesses such as insurance companies, lawyers, other vehicle manufacturers, vehicle service stations etc. Further, it is crucial for us to understand that the Data Act has been created as a *horizontal legislation* in order to facilitate data sharing between stakeholders such as businesses (including small and medium enterprises (SMEs)) and customers. The Data Act lays down specific provisions for B2B (business to business) data sharing, B2C (business to customer) and B2G (business to government) data sharing. Article 3 of the Data Act read with Article 5 ensures that the free flow of EDR data is enabled between businesses at the behest of the EDR user or data subject therefore, further allowing businesses to be able to horizontally share data with the various stakeholders [42].

Additionally, the data act through its Article 7, which discusses the scope of business-to-consumer and business-to-business data sharing obligations provides the contours within which EDR fitting car manufacturers, primary insurance providers and secondary insurance providers interact with each other when it comes to data sharing and therefore acts as an enabler to data sharing practices in both vertical and horizontal capacities [42].

Following suit we see that the Data Act also enumerates the conditions under which data holders make data available to data recipients and Article 8 discusses the conditions under which data sharing of the EDR data might be operationalised by the businesses at the behest of the customer. These conditions are focused on creating a conducive atmosphere for such data sharing and call for such data sharing practices to be carried out through fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory terms and by providing adequate focus to transparency requirements. Further, Article 8 states that a data holder shall not discriminate between comparable categories of data recipients and that the data holder shall not make the dataset available *exclusively* to a data recipient, unless such a request has been made specifically under the provisions of Chapter II of the Data Act which dictates the rules of B2C and B2B data sharing. This is especially fruitful for businesses which are engaged in providing services for vehicular insurance and allow for data subjects to be able to transfer their data from one data holder to another, this ease of data porting between businesses has a direct and positive impact on not only the competition perspective in the businesses but also allows for data subjects that are the customers of such businesses to benefit [43]. In its efforts to allow for a more inter-operable and effective data sharing regimen, through Article 23, the

data act aims to strengthen the requirements for the semantic interoperability of data amongst various businesses and ensures that the customers can move freely within the market, therefore, promoting competition and ensuring market checks. This provision is directly focused on ensuring that interoperability between businesses, insurance providers as well as businesses and insurance providers is seamless and can help in not only first-party access of EDR data but also 3rd party access to such EDR data without any form of undue hassle [41]; In keeping with the provisions of Article 23, Article 28 speaks to strengthening interoperability requirements for the EDR dataset within the businesses (car manufacturers as well as insurance providers) per the requests of the customer, or the internal cooperation between companies based on lawful consent of the data subject. This has a direct impact on the free and technically compatible movement of data across businesses [44].

Although, *not a direct blocking* of the use and free flow of EDR data between businesses, the proposed Data Act provides certain conditional provisions which may act as a blockage towards the use of the EDR data by businesses however does wonders for the free market is Article 13 which deals with the unfair contractual terms unilaterally imposed on a micro, small or medium-sized enterprise and this provision aims to balance the interest of parties and liability schematics when it comes to the dealings between established businesses and micro, small or medium-sized enterprise [44].

5.3 Public Bodies in DA

The Data Act is a Regulation proposal that was mainly focused on data access by users of connected objects and their software. Nevertheless, the regulation came to light after the COVID-19 pandemic, which had a heavy influence when it comes to sharing private data with the public sector. Therefore the Data Act has a chapter fully dedicated to the topic of business-to-government data sharing.

One of the main legal enablers present in the Data Act Proposal is located in Article 14 related to the obligation to make data available based on exceptional need. This article lays out the general ground for business-to-government data sharing under the Data Act, according to it the Public Sector can have access to data upon a specified duly justified request limited in time and scope demonstrating an exceptional need to use the data requested. This special need is further exemplified in Article 15, (a) Data Act in emergency situations, such as climate emergencies, and (b) in other non-emergency circumstances where the public sector body or Union institution, agency or body is "acting on the basis of Union or national law and has identified specific data, which is unavailable to it and which is necessary to fulfil, a specific task in the public interest that has been explicitly provided by law such", e.g., traffic management.

Under these circumstances, the Data Act provides a legal enabler to the public sector would have the possibility to access drivers' and vehicle data and else based on exceptional need, which can be an emergency situation or non-emergency circumstances in which the public sector body is acting to fulfil a specific task in the public interest. Therefore, the above-mentioned article opens the possibility for the public sector to access data when it is needed for the purpose of a public interest task [43].

When it comes to the possibility of Public Bodies, EU institutions, agencies, or bodies exchanging data obtained with another public sector body, Article 17, 4 Data

Act requests However, the data obtained pursuant to this purpose shall be only used for the purpose specified in the request, a section that connects with the GDPR principle of purpose limitation, already analyzed in this study.

When it comes to Article 22 of the Data Act, it also is very much connected with the previously analyzed FFNPD since it regulates that Public sector bodies and Union institutions, agencies, and bodies must cooperate and assist one another, in case of data exchange, facilitating data access by other public sector bodies.

5.4 Milestone 2 (M2): Examining the Scope of Data Access Enabled by the Data Act

The Data Act aims to provide a framework for governance and infrastructure related to data sharing outside of the scope of data spaces. However, as the European Common Data Spaces are not yet fully developed, there may be uncertainty in the access regimes for data that should be governed within them. Each data space is designed to address specific critical sectors, and until they are fully established, the governance and management of data access may not be fully defined. The Data Act represents an important step towards establishing a framework for data sharing, but further work is needed to fully realize the benefits of the European Common Data Spaces.

5.5 M2: Individuals

One could view the Data Act as a substantial amplification in agency, range, extent, and depth of the Article 20 of GDPR, or colloquially speaking, as data access, reuse, and portability "on steroids". Under the proposed framework, all stakeholders, including B2G (business-to-government), B2B (business-to-business), and others, possess expanded entitlements to access each other's data. Interpreted in light of EDR data, this implies that every B2X (business-to-anything) relationship constitutes an extension of access. The rights to access, use and share data under the Proposal are likely to encompass entities beyond the data subjects, such as commercial enterprises, subject to the legal status governing the usage of the device in question. Moreover, As the definition of 'user' encompasses legal persons, in case of the exercise of this right by a business, this takes the form of a commercial obligation for the manufacturer/-data holder to provide access to data to businesses and allow its exploitation, rather than the individuals' 'right' to access and port their personal data. In fact, according to the concept of 'user' adopted by the Proposal, individuals become entitled to enhanced portability right only incidentally, depending on the legal title under which they use the product or the related service (ownership, rental or lease) rather than on their relationship with the information concerning their private use of the product or service [45]. As for individuals, thanks to the concept of "user" embraced by the Proposal, individuals' enhanced right to portability arises, but only "incidentally", depending on the "legal title" they are using rather than on their relationship with the data [45]. According to Recital 31, users have a right "to access and make available to a third party any data generated by the use of a product or related service, irrespective of its nature as personal data, of the distinction between actively provided or

passively observed data, and irrespective of the legal basis of processing”, the expansion of access for the user can be appreciated under two perspectives: on the one hand, the user can access data that was observed by the product or service, concluding a long scholarship debate on whether the concept of data "provided" by the user also encompassed data passively "observed", or even "inferred" by the provider [8, 9, 46]. For each stakeholder, the expansion in the range of data encompasses Driver Data, Vehicle Data, and Other Data. Additionally, with regards to switching cloud providers, users (both individuals and commercial entities) are entitled to port their "applications" and "other digital assets" along with their data (Article 23), as well as "virtual machines and other manifestations of virtualisation technologies" (Recital 72).

Article 35 (Databases containing certain data) should also be regarded as an advancement in access and reuse. It specifies that the *sui generis* right outlined in Article 7 of Directive 96/9/EC (Database Directive) does not apply to databases that hold data obtained from or produced by the utilization of a product or a related service. This provision explicitly aims to prevent impeding the exercise of users' right to access and utilize such data under Article 4 or their right to share such data with third parties under Article 5.

Ultimately, the Data Act's emphasis on technical interoperability underscores a shift away from expanding stakeholders' access regimes subjectively and towards enhancing the overall technical accessibility into the information systems, and legal accessibility into the market for the information economy.

In comparison to the GDPR (Art. 9,2 ; 15,1 ; 16 ; 17 ; 20) the combination of articles 4, 5, 6 and 26 of the Data Act gives the user (individual and business) extended access and control to the EDR dataset by (1) extending the CRUD actions to "direct access", "get availability"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "immediate availability", or "including relevant data formats and data structures"; (3) extending the access to third-party businesses; (4) giving access to all dataset, (5) first- and third- parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data.

5.6 M2: Businesses

The Data Act is a horizontal, multi-faceted and multi-stakeholder-oriented legislation, which is a boon for data sharing across businesses, customers and governments. A central feature of the Data Act is its focus on not just awarding the right of data portability across data subjects, data holders and data recipients but also its keen focus on the fairness, transparency, semantic interoperability, non-discrimination and reasonableness of data portability requirements through legal obligations and contractual requirements. Therefore, in terms of EDR data access, the Data Act champions the cause of carving out adequate access regimes of the EDR data and their free flow between businesses, from consumers to businesses and also from businesses to governments, therefore, pairing well with the regulatory regime crafted under the GDPR as well as the FFNPD Directive, and adequately covers the interoperability requirements for both personal and non-personal data, this heterogeneous mixture of personal and non-personal data is also the composition of the EDR dataset and therefore, when examined through the perspective of access regime. [43]

Additionally, insofar as the definition of 'user' includes legal entities, if a business exercises the right to portability under Recital 31, it imposes a commercial obligation on the manufacturer/data holder to grant access to data to businesses and permit their exploitation [45].

The combinations of the provisions of the GDPR (Article 6,1; 9,2) and Articles 5, 7, 8, 13, 23, and 28 of the Data Act give the business) extend access and control to the EDR dataset by: (1) extending the CRUD actions to "direct access", and "get availability"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "immediate availability", or "including relevant data formats and data structures"; (3) extending the access to third-party businesses; (4) giving access to all dataset, (5) first- and third- parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data.

5.7 M2: Public Bodies

The Data Act Proposal is the latest regulation proposed by the European Commission, which is a part of the European Data Strategy. Its analysis must be done in tandem with the other regulations, especially GDPR and FFNPD. Therefore, when analyzing all the regulations in a holistic manner it is possible to comprehend that there is a legal landscape that enables the access and portability of both driver's personal data and non-personal data for the public sector bodies. Although the Data Act has its main focus on individual interests in assessing data from connected objects, Chapter V clearly opens an avenue that allows the Public Sector to access meaningful data for fulfilling tasks in the public interest.

Nevertheless, the concept of "fulfilment of a task in the public interest" has been under modification along the legislative process of the Data Act, and might be transformed into a legal blocker depending on how the legislative process of the Data Act evolves. Although this concept can change depending on the Member State in question, the EDPS-EDPB raised concerns on their joint opinion of the data act, due to the possibility of public sector abuse. Additionally, the industry raised questions regarding this open concept, which might result in further modifications. For instance, the most recent modifications by the Swedish presidency have addressed these points by detailing public tasks on the Recitals.³¹

Ultimately, Articles 14 and 15 of the Data Act give public bodies enlarged access to EDR data for the purposes of "tasks in the public interest" by (1) extending the CRUD actions to "access", "use"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "including metadata"; (3) extending access to the public sector; (4) giving access to non-personal data, (5) first parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data.

6 Discussion

While this paper has explored several important aspects of the access, reuse, and portability of data, there remain certain topics that have not been addressed in detail.

³¹For more information on the timeline of the Data Act Proposal see <https://eulawlive.com/opened-business-to-government-data-sharing-on-the-data-act-between-a-rock-and-a-hard-place-by-barbara-lazarotto/>

These topics represent promising avenues for future research and could shed further light on the complexities and nuances of this subject.

Market for EDR data

Typically, changes in the landscape of providers of prime materials within a market often result in a significant shift in the power structure of the market's actors [47]. Similarly, it is expected that the shift in production and ownership of vehicle data from insurance companies to car manufacturers will have an influence on the market for this category of information. In the words of Martens and Mueller-Langer, "even minor shifts in these markets may re-route billions of euros into other hands" [5]. In the past, insurance companies held exclusive access to data, which gave them the power to set monopolistic prices for selling or retaining it for their own use. However, with the introduction of Event Data Recorders (EDRs) by manufacturers, alternative sources of data are now available, reducing exclusivity and lowering market prices. Additionally, the connectivity of vehicles to the Internet means that some data that was previously only accessible through in-vehicle EDRs is now also accessible by Internet Service Providers (ISPs). As a result, the availability of alternative data sources has reduced monopolistic rents, as noted by Martens [7, p. 18]. Indeed, as evidenced above, the transfer of control over vehicle data to car manufacturers also implies a shift in the balance of power to broker this data, in a manner that has not been witnessed previously. This shift comes at a time when the law has broadened the access regimes to include other stakeholders who may have an interest in vehicle data. As a result, the industry faces a complex and evolving landscape, where legal frameworks and technological developments will continue to shape the conditions of access, ownership, and control over vehicle data. In this context, industry players must remain attentive to emerging trends and regulatory developments, as they navigate this rapidly evolving environment. Ultimately, the outlook for EDR data is uncertain, given the lack of clarity on whether insurance companies will require the installation of their proprietary black boxes or demand access to the event data recorders held by manufacturers. Furthermore, the conditions dictating such access, whether through contractual agreements or legal directives, are yet to be fully defined. As a result, the future trajectory of the vehicle data market remains uncertain, with industry stakeholders awaiting further regulatory guidance and market developments to shape the landscape.

The previous discussion raises an important point: changes in data access rights can have significant economic consequences for individuals, firms, and society as a whole. While the push for data sharing may seem beneficial when accessing other people's data, it is important to consider the implications for one's own data when extracted "against his will and at a cost to him" [7, p. 20]. If this is read in the context of personal information and the holder of information is the individual, then the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) and European Data Protection Board (EDPB) joint opinion begins to appear more logical. They have called upon the co-legislators to impose constraints or limitations on the use of data resulting from the use of a product or service by any entity other than the data subjects, particularly relevant if the data can lead to accurate inferences about the private lives of data subjects or pose a significant risk to their rights and freedoms. The EDPS and EDPB have proposed

the implementation of explicit limitations regarding the use of such data for direct marketing or advertising, employee monitoring, insurance premium computation, and credit scoring [45], but it is worth studying whether such limitations would in practice solve the issue.

Competition and the European Commission's visible hand

Another interesting point of discussion pertains to the expansion of the right to data portability in the Data Act, which warrants careful consideration due to its potential impact on competition. In this context, Articles 7 and 5.2 are of particular relevance. Article 7 exempts small and micro enterprises from the obligation to facilitate data portability in certain circumstances, such as business-to-consumer and business-to-business data sharing obligations. This is a common strategy employed by legislators to reduce barriers to entry for smaller businesses, similar to creating an entry point at the bottom of the market. In contrast, Article 5.2 proposes a less common approach in this context. It stipulates that entities that provide core platform services, designated as gatekeepers, cannot be considered eligible third parties for receiving ported data. Consequently, this provision does not remove barriers to entry but rather creates them. This can be likened to imposing a ceiling on the top of the market. These provisions have political implications and seem to make the otherwise invisible hand quite visible. However, it should be noted that even with these provisions, dominant players may still find ways to gain an upper hand. As such, it is crucial to read them in conjunction with the Data Strategy and the Digital Markets Act to understand their intended purpose of targeting specific companies.

Quality, informational determination, and perception

One important aspect of data portability is the extent to which the contractual power of insurance companies may impact an individual's right to port their data, particularly in cases where the insurance company may refuse to accept only a portion of the personal data related to driving or require access to all of it. While the theory of informational determination supports the right of the data subject to port as much data as they wish, the practical implementation of this right in the insurance industry is still uncertain. In such a scenario, although it may be technically legal that the data subject chooses to port only certain data and leave out others, this approach could lead to a distorted perception of reality and potentially create issues and risks for other parties.

A Copernican revolution in data sharing?

While discussing GDPR and other existing legislation, Martens notes that "such initiatives are bouncing back and forth between two poles: (a) offering more exclusive rights, either for the protection of personal rights or as an incentive to invest in data collection, and (b) making data more widely available and accessible to facilitate the extraction of new insights from data" [7, p. 19]. However, what seems to be happening is a fundamental shift in the strategy for access and re-use of data, a Copernican revolution from subjective access to systemic accessibility. Ultimately, the Data Act's emphasis on technical interoperability underscores a shift away from expanding stakeholders'

access regimes subjectively, towards enhancing the overall technical accessibility into the information systems and legal accessibility into the market for information.

7 Conclusion

This study analysed the General Data Protection Regulation, the Free-Flow of Non Personal Data Regulation, and the Open Data Directive from the perspective of three different stakeholders, namely, Individuals (consumers), Businesses (Insurance companies) and Public Sector bodies.

The main aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the existing EU legal framework concerning access and reuse of data in comparison to what envisaged in the data strategy. To do so, the authors developed a framework to measure differences in access regimes across regulations and put it into practice on the case study of Event Data Recorders as example of privately held dataset.

Thanks to this methodology, the authors found that:

- from the perspective of individuals, in comparison to the GDPR (Articles 9,2 ; 15,1 ; 16 ; 17 ; 20), the combination of articles 4, 5, 6 and 26 of the Data Act give the user (individual and business) extended access and control to the EDR dataset by: (1) extending the CRUD actions to "direct access", "get availability"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "immediate availability", or "including relevant data formats and data structures"; (3) extending the access to third-party businesses; (4) giving access to all dataset, (5) first- and third- parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data.
- from the perspective of businesses, the combinations of the provisions of the GDPR (Articles 6,1 ; 9,2) and the Articles 5, 7, 8, 13, 23, and 28 of the Data Act give the business) extend access and control to the EDR dataset by: (1) extending the CRUD actions to "direct access", "get availability"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "immediate availability", or "including relevant data formats and data structures"; (3) extending the access to third-party businesses; (4) giving access to all dataset, (5) first- and third- parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data.
- from the perspective of public sector bodies, articles 14 and 15 of the Data Act give public bodies enlarged access to EDR data for the purposes of "tasks in the public interest" by: (1) extending the CRUD actions to "access", "use"; (2) bolstering the CRUD actions with "including metadata"; (3) extending access to the public sector; (4) giving access to non-personal data, (5) first parties data; (6) and to Vehicle Data

This analysis made it possible to observe that so far the GDPR is the Regulation which offers the broadest possibility of accessing Event Data Recorder data for the three stakeholders. Although the scope of the Regulation is focused on personal data, it gives a broad range of tools for data access which was not provided by other regulations.

The proposed Data Act has the potential to create a conflict with the GDPR, particularly with regards to the distinction between personal and non-personal data. This is because the Data Act primarily concerns access to data generated by connected products, and does not differentiate between personal and non-personal data. Instead, it emphasizes technical aspects of data, such as format and quality, and includes

the right to data portability for mixed datasets that contain both personal and non-personal data.

As a result of this study, the authors illustrate differences in EDR access rights across European Regulations. Although the Data Act has enhanced access and control over data held by businesses, the map highlights areas that require further development to enable practical data portability and data reuse rights. This challenge is compounded by the possibility of conflicts among overlapping Regulations concerning the same data, as well as uncertainties regarding future vertical or special regulations that will emerge with regards to vehicle data.

8 CRediT Author Statement

Tommaso Crepax: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review and Editing. Barbara da Rosa Lazarotto: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review and Editing. Mitisha Gaur: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review and Editing.

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Data Collaboratives with the Use of Decentralised Learning - an Interdisciplinary Perspective on Data Governance

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Abstract. The endeavor to find appropriate data governance frameworks capable of reconciling conflicting interests in data has dramatically gained importance across disciplines and has been discussed among legal scholars, computer scientists as well as policy-makers alike. The predominant part of the current discussion is centered around the challenging task of creating a data governance framework where data is

‘as open as possible and as closed as necessary’. In this article, we elaborate on modern approaches to data governance and their limitations. It analyses how propositions evolved from property rights in data towards the creation of data access and data sharing obligations and how the corresponding debates reflect the difficulty of developing approaches that reconcile seemingly opposite objectives – such as giving individuals and businesses more control over ‘their’ data while at the same time ensuring its availability to different stakeholders. Furthermore, we propose a wider acknowledgement of data collaboratives powered by decentralised learning techniques as a possible remedy to the shortcomings of current data governance schemes. Hence, we propose a mild formalization of the set of existing technological solutions that could inform existing approaches to data governance issues. Our proposition is based on an abstractive notion of collaborative computation as well as on several principles that are essential for our definition of data collaboratives. By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective on data governance, this article highlights how innovative technological solutions can enhance control over data while at the same time ensuring its availability to other stakeholders and thereby contributing to the achievement of the policy goals of the European Strategy for Data..

Keywords: Data Governance, Decentralised Learning, Data Access, Data Sharing, European Strategy for Data.

1 Introduction

The interest in data governance has spiked over the last years, gathering the worldwide attention of policy-makers and various research communities. The machine learning

community is most concerned with gaining access to an uninterrupted source of high-quality data. From the engineering side of view, the problem concerns mostly building trust between data providers and deploying an infrastructure that may support data access. The European Commission, taking into account the current market disadvantage of smaller entities, wants to guarantee such access, albeit still ensuring a high degree of protection for fundamental rights. From the European policy perspective, access to data should therefore be "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", which generally implies finding a point of equilibrium between conflicting interests in data. Consequently, the creation of data governance frameworks that enable the emergence of a data-agile economy [18] where tensions, resulting from the seemingly opposed objectives of enabling control of data and guarantee its availability to other stakeholders at the same time, exceeds the boundaries of a single discipline.

This paper provides an interdisciplinary perspective on how to solve tensions resulting from diverging interests in data by providing insights in both, the regulatory as well as technological layer in data governance. While the provided solutions are mainly discussed in the European context - they may not necessarily be limited to such. The main contribution of this paper consists of the following:

First, it analyses how the creation of property rights in data was envisioned by scholars and policy-makers as a possible solution to reconcile conflicting interests: enhancing control over data while at the same time ensuring its availability to stakeholders. Furthermore, it explains the shortcomings of this idea and why it was subsequently abandoned and replaced by a new approach in EU policy that should achieve similar objectives but by different means: the creation of mandatory data access and sharing rights. Second, the analysis then shifts towards the technological layer in data governance and how distributed computation methods might promote data access and data sharing. It builds upon the concept of data collaboratives which have been described as new emerging forms of partnerships where privately held data is made accessible for analysis and where collaboration between participants is facilitated to unlock the public good potential of previously siloed data [31]. It shows how technological solutions through distributed and collaborative processes might be capable of achieving the seemingly opposite objectives of data control and availability and could thereby contribute to reduce existing tensions in data economies. This framework should provide constraints on the access and control of the shared individual data and give back to each participant an acknowledgement of the contribution by means of a repertoire of metrics. The paper is structured in the following way: Section 2 outlines how data governance has turned into a key policy concern for the European legislator. Section 3 is dedicated to the discussion of past and current regulatory approaches to data governance in EU policy as well as their shortcomings. Section 4 introduces the concept of data collaboratives, defined through the set of four principles, as a possible tool shifting data governance in the technological layer towards mutually beneficial cooperation. Section 5 presents conclusions of this work.

2 DATA GOVERNANCE AS A KEY POLICY CONCERN

Whereas the European Commission does not offer a comprehensive definition of its “European way of data governance” [22], data governance has in general been defined by scholars as the exercise of authority and control over the management of data, whilst its purpose would be to increase the value of data and minimize data-related costs and risks [1]. Von Grafenstein differentiates between three analytical layers that are equally mentioned by the legislators with each having their own challenges: (i) the regulatory layer (ii) the organisational layer (iii) the technological layer [32].

Since the Juncker Commission identified the creation of a Digital Single Market as a critical policy objective in 2014, the EU has been extremely active in proposing regulation for a digital economy that ensures a high level of data protection while, at the same time, boosting competitiveness and innovation capacities. With the recognition of data as an “essential resource for economic growth, job creation, and societal progress” [17], the interest in data governance has spiked over the last years, gathering worldwide attention of policy-makers and research communities. Whereas the regulation of data flows originated in attempts to protect the fundamental rights to privacy and data protection [63], regulatory perspectives evolved with the growing understanding of benefits that result from data-driven innovation that relies on data as a resource [60]. Since data would not have any intrinsic value but its value would rather depend on the context of use as well as the extent to which it can be reused [61] ensuring availability and access to quality data has become a key concern.

Whilst the European Data Protection Framework has been conceived in fundamental rights terms, it has a dual purpose to also ensure the free flow of personal data [48]. EU policy of the past years therefore equally aimed at adding a fifth to the four existing freedoms of the European Single Market (free flow of goods, capital, services, and labour): the free flow of data. [12,80] However, in addition to growing concerns about the internal consistency of this patchwork of rules and regulations [13] the question comes up if the current path to data governance taken by the EU in its Data Strategy is capable of achieving its objectives. How a framework should look like that ensures both the availability of personal and nonpersonal data to a wide variety of actors as well as the protection of fundamental rights of different stakeholders is far from clear. Whilst substantial gains are expected from exploiting the non-rivalrous character of data by increasing its availability, neither companies nor individuals would necessarily want their data widely available due to potential threats to privacy, intellectual property rights, or trade secrets if data is disclosed [11], [12]. Resolving these tensions lies at the heart of discussions on how to design a framework for the data-agile economy. It, therefore, comes as no surprise that commentators described the regulation of data markets as “shaping up to be one of the major challenges of the twenty-first century” [77].

3 FROM PROPERTY RIGHTS TO DATA ACCESS AND SHARING OBLIGATIONS

Current approaches and propositions with regard to appropriate frameworks for data governance, however, do not come out of the void. Instead, they build upon previous discussions and proposals that equally attempted to find solutions on how conflicting interests in data could be resolved. Therefore, before turning to our model of data collaboratives based on decentralised learning techniques, this section first retraces how property rights in data have been considered as a means to create a flourishing data economy. It thereby sheds light on objectives which regulatory frameworks should achieve. Second, it analyses how a property approach was abandoned and replaced by a regulatory approach that focuses on creating data access and sharing obligations instead. In line with the distinction of three analytical layers in data governance [32], this section therefore focuses on the first, i. e. the regulatory layer and different approaches that have been discussed by scholars and policy-makers.

3.1 Data Property

A frequently used example for the explanation of the necessity of property rights in society constitutes the "tragedy of the commons" elaborated by Hardin [54]. Scarce resources that are accessible to all members of society would ultimately end up being overexploited and depleted – freedom in a commons would bring ruin to all [35]. This tragedy could only be averted either with the introduction of a system of private property rights that should enable efficient resource allocation according to market mechanisms, or via government regulation that define rules for the use of that resource. Whilst the characteristics of data as an intangible, non-rivalrous resource that does not get depleted upon consumption make it a difficult fit for traditional economic and legal categories [39], debates emerged how property rights in data could contribute to the preservation of the 'privacy commons' which might otherwise degrade due to concerns about an (over)use of personal information [70]. As described by Thouvenin et al., data propertization gave "hope to those wishing to unlock the potential of the data economy and to those trying to re-empower individuals that have lost control over their data" [78].

Whereas a certain degree of legal protection can already be offered by non-property regimes such as trade secrets or contracts, and de facto ownership positions via technical protection measures, none of these regimes create rights *erga omnes* – i.e. enforceable rights against the world [36]. It is property law that confers exclusive rights that can be invoked against more than a number of specific persons and it is precisely this universality that has been described as the touchstone of property rights [8]. The existing European intellectual property rights regimes, however, do not provide for a comprehensive property right in data as such. Instead, they offer different degrees of protection based on criteria such as creativity, investment, or secrecy. Some commentators have therefore rightfully used the metaphor of a patchwork to describe the protection offered by existing intellectual property regimes in data [33,87]. Furthermore, neither

the Data Protection Directive nor its successor the General Data Protection Regulation, grounded in the unalienable fundamental right to data protection, created any property rights for data subjects over their data.

Whether or not the introduction of a new comprehensive unitary property rights regime might be the appropriate approach to solve diverging interests in data has been subject to a long-lasting scholarly debate. Early proponents in the US argued that property rights in data would empower individuals to regain control over their data and to value their privacy according to their preferences [45]. The protection of data would thereby be linked with the incentives of the market by using the laws of property as a control mechanism [45]. Others, however, feared that a property rights approach would ultimately erode existing levels of privacy if individuals simply traded away their personal data [10]. Market solutions based on a property rights model might thus not cure any of the problems related to control, but only legitimize them [46].

Particularly in Europe, where information privacy is considered as a fundamental right and where personal data should consequently not be considered as a commodity that could be bought and sold on a market, a property rights approach appeared problematic. At the same time, critics observed that maintaining the argument that personal data should be nobody's property would be illusional in a data-driven economy [66]. Instead, the status quo devoid of well-defined property rights in data would result in a de facto assignment of (economic) property rights to the information industry, eroding data subject's autonomy, privacy and informational self-determination [66].

Other scholars discussed the introduction of property rights in data not from the angle of the empowerment of the individual but the creation of data markets [86]. Property rights in non-personal data might create incentives to generate and disclose data – thereby enhancing the general availability of data for other market actors. Whilst the proposition was taken up in the proposal by the European Commission on the possible introduction of a data producer's right [17], criticism prevailed. The reliance of Big Data on permanent, dynamic access to real-time data sources could hardly be aligned with individual ownership [15]. Instead, creating an additional layer of rights in data might cause disruptive overlaps with existing copyright and the sui generis database right [36]. Consequently, competing claims of ownership would risk resulting in a "tragedy of the anticommons", i.e. an underuse of data due to complex interrelations of overlapping ownership claims [75].

With the European Strategy for Data, a turning point in the EU's approach to the regulation of the data economy has been reached. After decades of discussions, the creation of property rights in data seems to have been discarded as a suitable mechanism that is capable of resolving conflicting interests in data. However, the rationale behind its proposition, i. e. empowering individuals and companies with regard to 'their' data as well as enabling the emergence of a data-agile economy, is still existent. Before turning to our model of data collaboratives and how it might contribute to solving those tensions, the following section elaborates on the shift away from property rights towards data access and sharing in EU policy.

3.2 The EU's Shift towards Data Access and Data Sharing

As the academic debate shifted away from conceiving property rights in data as a potential legal solution to resolve conflicting interests in data, a similar tendency could be observed in EU policy. Whilst the goal of the European Strategy for Data remains to realize a 'genuine single market for data', any reference to (legal) data ownership rights disappeared from the European Commission's communications and proposals. Commentators hence described the strategy as a 'paradigm shift' in EU policy from data ownership towards facilitating data access and sharing [57].

Since data would constitute an essential resource for companies to develop new products, services or train AI systems, a regulatory environment should enable stakeholders to have easy access to an almost infinite amount of data. Regulation should enable data to flow easily while at the same time ensure that European rules and values are fully respected. Key pillars of the European Strategy for Data thereby attempt to enable precisely the creation of such a regulatory environment that ensures 'better access to data and its responsible usage' [18]. Regulating data access instead of creating property rights in data have thus become the new instrument that should solve conflicting interests in data.

First, the Data Governance Act (DGA) [23] intends to facilitate access and encourage use of data held by public sector bodies. Whilst the Open Data Directive already established minimum rules governing the re-use for data that is not subject to, for instance, intellectual property rights or commercial confidentiality, the DGA harmonizes access conditions for reuse of protected categories of data. Moreover, the DGA puts in place a framework for 'data intermediation services' and 'data altruism organization' which should play a key role in the data economy by supporting, facilitating, and promoting (voluntary) data sharing by bringing demand and supply of data together. A notification scheme for data sharing services should thereby increase trust in these data intermediaries (and hence in data sharing) by companies and data subjects.

Second, the European Commission intends to create Common European Data Spaces [20] in strategic sectoral fields [21] that bring together relevant data infrastructures and governance frameworks to facilitate data pooling and sharing. Key features of this data spaces should be that they provide a secure infrastructure to pool, access, share, and use data while ensuring the protection of European rules. The structure should thereby provide access to and use of data in a fair, transparent, and non-discriminatory manner via trustworthy data governance mechanisms. The DGA is thus supposed to play a fundamental role for the creation of data spaces as it should create the foundation for the establishment of trustworthy, neutral data intermediaries.

Third, the Data Act proposal [22] constitutes together with the DGA the second horizontal legislative instrument of the European Data Strategy. Whilst the DGA aims at opening up data held by public sector bodies, the Data Act proposal creates mandatory access rules to data held by private actors in B2C, B2B as well as B2G relations. The data access rights are thereby supposed to fulfil the twofold purpose of empowering individuals and companies over 'their' data while at the same time ensuring that data is available for other stakeholders. It is still unclear, however, how mandatory data access

rights would have to be designed in practice to comply with, for instance, the requirements of the current Data Act proposal. Whether they would have to be designed as ex-situ rights that enable the porting of data directly to another platform or as in-situ rights that would require external algorithms to be transferred to the data location to perform data analysis [41].

Since the Data Act proposal merely demands that data should be ‘made available’ or to implement the principles of data minimization and data protection by design by using technology that ‘permits algorithms to be brought to the data’, it seems likely that in many instances it might favor in-situ access rights that do not require the transfer of data.

Finally, this paradigm shift towards fostering data access is not only visible in the European Strategy for Data but has also been observed in other new European digital regulations [59]. Provisions in the Digital Markets Act (DMA) [24], the Digital Service Act (DSA) [25] and the proposal for an AI Act [19] would also contain provisions that reflect the EU’s attempt to open up data while at the same time finding a balance between new access and transparency obligations and competing interests in data. New access and/or portability obligations in the DMA, DSA, and the AI Act would therefore equally constitute part of the latest regulatory effort of the EU to end data enclosure while departing from a “single-minded rights-based and data ownership approach” [59].

At the same time, however, authors have been critical of approaches based on access rights alone. Focusing exclusively on the problem of whether a company should get access to data would be insufficient. The “data as a resource” framing of the European Strategy for Data that regards ‘data abundance’ as desirable would necessarily continue to conflict with the purpose limitation and data minimization principles in European Data Protection law [76]. This tension would not be automatically resolved in a regulatory governance model that merely proscribes data access and sharing obligations. Viljoen argues that a common flaw in existing data governance frameworks based on proprietarian or fundamental rights based approaches would be its consistent focus on attempting to reassert individual instead of more collective forms of control over ones datafication. Since data processing practices by major companies would primarily aim at deriving population-level insights, data governance approaches would have to move beyond individualist claims and develop institutional responses to represent the relevant interests at stake on a more collective level [83]. Other scholars insist that a broader analytical approach would be necessary, for instance, by the use of data trustees or technological solutions that impact the allocation of de facto control of data [40].

The following section thus presents a model of data collaboratives based on decentralised learning techniques that might remedy some of the existing shortcomings by moving beyond individual control of data. Instead, it employs a more collective approach that enables participants in the collaborative to have access to different datasets and to collectively train one model without the need for transferring any raw data. It exemplifies how a solution on the technological layer could contribute to reduce tensions which the regulatory layer alone could not solve, i.e. enabling control over data while at the same time making it available to other stakeholders. Furthermore, the following proposition mirrors equally the demand of the Data Act to conceive data access

rights in a way they implement the data protection by design and data minimization principle.

4 DATA COLLABORATIVES AND DATA ACCESS

4.1 Data Governance and the Commons Management Problem

When Hardin saw either a market-based approach via property rights or government intervention as the only possible solutions to prevent the tragedy of the commons to occur, scholarship on the commons [62] argued that an alternative approach was possible. This approach would rely on collective resource management, i.e. the institutionalized sharing of resources among members of a community [50]. Commons thereby consist of three elements: (i) a resource (ii) a community that has access to and takes care of the resource (iii) collective action of creating, maintaining, and governing in common [52]. Since they are based on the idea of access rather than exclusion, they would challenge the dominance of private property [52] or even constitute the opposite of property [55]. The main function of commons would therefore be to institutionalize freedom to operate within symmetric constraints, free of the particular risk that any other can deny use of that resource set [6]. The commons-framework therefore does not imply unmanaged access to a particular resource, but requires that groups engage in managed resource sharing [49].

Ostrom famously defined eight design principles [62] that enable successful collective resource management, such as collective-choice arrangements that allow groups to adapt governance conditions to their needs and local circumstances. Whilst initially conceived for the management of natural resources whose characteristics are evidently very distinct from data, they would still be highly relevant with regard to data governance as they could provide insights for assessing the types of institutions needed to govern access and use of data [49]. How data could be subject to regulation via commons governance institutions has been subsequently further analysed within research on governing knowledge commons that have been defined as "institutionalized community governance of the sharing and, in some cases, creation, of information, science, knowledge, data, and other types of intellectual and cultural resources" [29]. Its key insight would be how information resources are governed as a shared resource via a collective and not in markets via intellectual property rights regimes or state intervention [49]. New technologies thereby would have played a key role for the possible development of knowledge commons as they facilitated the ability to capture the previously uncapturable and to draw value from it by means of advanced data analytics [67].

Studies therefore attempted to adapt Ostrom's design principles for collective self-managing institutions and translate them to and extract useful insights for data governance [64], [11], [2]. This further resulted in discussions and analyses, [2], [85] on various models of data stewardships, such as data trusts, data foundations, data cooperatives or data collaboratives [85]. Data collaboratives thereby have been described as new emerging forms of partnerships where privately held data is made accessible for analysis. The collaboration between participants that is facilitated within these structures aims to result in new insights and innovation and to unlock the public good potential of

previously siloed data [31]. Our approach to data collaboratives and collaborative data sharing is based on many advancements in the technological field that were presented in the span of the last 20 years. We draw from such solutions as personal data stores [58,72], distributed learning [42,81,82] or even data licensing [4]. What we propose is a mild formalization of the set of existing technological solutions adjusted to mitigate the issues arising from the current data governance methods. For the sake of better generalization, we limit ourselves to the method-agnostic notation, not to exclude any new or existing technological solutions that may be adopted to serve as a building block of new data collaboratives. Our method of defining the boundaries and goals of data collaboratives is based on the identification of common principles and basic computational operations that can be performed by the participants. In the following, we introduce the goal of data collaboratives, together with the four essential principles that define it. Next, we elaborate on the notation of collaborative computing that is a baseline for the presented structure. Lastly, we introduce current limitations of proposed approach.

4.2 Goal of the Data Collaborative

The proposed approach is based on an application of decentralised learning for better data governance and could provide a substantial leap towards independent and self-sovereign data management inside trusted communities.

The main goal of data collaboratives is to allow trusted parties to establish a private or hybrid (public-private) collaboration and train one shared model without transferring the raw data beyond the local storage. In this sense, the data collaborative is an applied case of data access and data sharing - because each party is allowing only access to derivative aggregates of its resources – and does not consent to any transfer of raw data. It therefore reflects demands set by the Data Act proposal with regard to access rights that should implement the data protection by design and the data minimization principle (in-situ instead of ex-situ access right). The trained model is then shared between all parties. We deliberately do not define here the notion of a party or a participant to the collaborative. We assume that it may be a physical person or an organization, and that the shared data may or may not constitute personal data. All these scenarios will require different legal approaches, as different types of rules may or may not apply, depending on a specific use-case. However, any approach to the data governance in the technological layer requires a degree of abstraction that would allow for a fine generalization of the presented method, and any synthetic definition of a participant may be harmful to this objective.

The main objective of the data collaborative is to always perform at least one collaborative computation (which is abstractly defined in the next section of this paper). At the same time, the collaborative may be capable of tracking the individual contribution of all participants with regard to the final output. Although this is a distinct problem on its own, that is overviewed as an open challenge, a data collaborative might therefore strengthen control over data in several ways. First, by not requiring participants to transfer raw data which is directly embodied in the four essential principles that define the data collaborative. Data access within our data collaborative would therefore be less invasive with regard to potential privacy, intellectual property, or commercial interests

the stakeholders might have with regard to their data. Second, if we assume that the data collaborative is able to track and evaluate the contribution of each participant, this could enhance trust in the collaboratives as it empowers individuals to understand their contribution and thereby promotes the participation and collaboration to the collective model. Furthermore, one might envision the possible implementation of rules that enable proprietary or contractual claims with regard to the trained model that are made dependent on the proportion of the registered contribution by participants. At the same time, the collaborative could succeed in breaking up previously siloed data and thus ensuring its availability to other stakeholders. Where previous regulatory approaches failed, data collaboratives might contribute to reconcile conflicting interests in data.

As briefly mentioned in the previous paragraph, we define our commons management system through the set of four essential principles that are used to classify it as a data collaborative and which are loosely connected to previous attempts to transpose Ostrom's principles on managing the commons to data governance frameworks. Firstly, the data collaboratives should provide an accessible infrastructure for performing various analytical tasks without the necessity to transfer raw data beyond the participants' devices. Consequently, the proposed architecture strengthens control of participants over their local datasets. [**Decentralised Data Storage**]. Once the model is trained (or once an analytical task is accomplished) it should be governed by all the members (in proportion to their marginal contribution). Shared governance is a key guarantee that all the members will benefit from joint participation in the analytical tasks. Collective-choice arrangements could be realized by allowing participants to the collaborative to create their own rules and governance conditions. What's more, it can be envisaged that during the establishment of the collaborative, parties establish operations and actions that require a certain number of votes and can only be initialized if a certain quorum has been reached. [**Shared Model Governance**]. The formal structure of a data collaborative should be mostly implementation-agnostic. This is because any structure or implementation that satisfies the baseline definition and four essential principles can be treated as a data collaborative - irrespective of the implementation details [Universality]. Finally, data collaboratives can be established and executed in many different ways, combining the available technology with local needs. However, each data collaborative should be able to perform at least one analytical operation in a distributed environment [**Minimal Utility – Collaborative Computation**].

These principles can be fulfilled by the utilization of many already existing technologies. The last decade has seen the development of a large-batch synchronous distributed learning [14], federated learning [3, 5, 9, 42, 43, 51, 56, 68, 79, 84, 88, 89] and other "no-peek" approaches such as split neural network [81] that allowed us to develop a completely different mindset regarding machine learning, escaping the dogma of collecting the whole data in one centralized location in order to develop a model based on the chosen objective. Although many challenges regarding those methods are still open [38], decentralised learning has seen a number of use-cases that may be seen as a showcase of the potential hidden in that approach [9,34,68]. Most importantly, decentralised learning may serve as the backbone of a different approach to data governance, where the data "owners" are able to establish closed communities of high and medium trust and then collaboratively participate to the training of ML models.

4.3 Problem Statement and Basic Definitions for Collaborative Computations

The data collaborative is established between three or more parties that share an interest in performing one or more collaborative computation and retaining controls of outputs of those computations throughout the existence of the partnership. The principle of **Minimal Utility** requires the parties to be interested in performing at least one collaborative computation throughout the existence of the collective partnership. Therefore, we need to define – at least briefly – the notion of this term. For this, we use mostly the notation used in the theory of decentralised machine learning [71,82,84]. We assume to have a set of available clients (that are synonymous to the notion of parties of participants) $C = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n\}$ and each client C_i stores a set of data $X_i = \{(\bar{x}_1, y_1), (\bar{x}_2, y_2), (\bar{x}_3, y_3), \dots, (\bar{x}_p, y_p)\}$ where each (\bar{x}_1, y_1) is a one sample, \bar{x}_p is a vector n-dimensional vector containing all features and y_p is a label that is attributed to the vector \bar{x}_p . The objective is to estimate a surrogate for a hidden function $h(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$, that assign a label y to the observation \bar{x} .

Machine Learning training method recreates a hypothesis function $\tilde{h}(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$ as a proxy of $h(\bar{x})$ such that $\tilde{h}(\bar{x}) \sim h(\bar{x})$. We want this approximation to be the closest to the unknown function $h(\bar{x})$ as possible. We can generally express that idea as:

$$\min \mathbb{P}[\tilde{h}(\bar{x}) \neq h(\bar{x})] \leq \varepsilon$$

where ε is some previously defined margin of error that we can tolerate given the projected task. The generalised error on distribution \mathcal{D} and in relation to some underlying function $h(\bar{x})$ can be defined as generalization error:

$$\mathcal{L}[\tilde{h}(\bar{x})] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{P}[\tilde{h}(\bar{x}) \neq h(\bar{x})] \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) describes the generalization error that our hypothesis function is making on the given population. During training, we don't have access to the whole population, but only to the training sample that we have gathered for that particular purpose. In a centralized scenario, the dataset will be defined as a collection of data gathered from all available clients, i.e. $X = X_1 \cup X_2 \cup X_3 \dots X_i$ where X_i is data stored at the client C_i . In such an environment, we can directly train one hypothesis function $\tilde{h}(\bar{x}) \rightarrow y$, and then evaluate it on the possessed data:

$$\mathcal{L}(\tilde{h}(\bar{x}_i))_{ELF} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [\tilde{h}(\bar{x}_i) \neq y_i] \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) describes the empirical loss function, where we sum over all the n samples from a dataset, comparing the output of the function to the original label (independent) variable attached to the feature vector \bar{x}_i . Equation (2) also assumes that we can gather the whole dataset X in one (or few) centralised locations, irrespective of the number of clients that have generated said data. Although this is a common for a centralised scenario, such an action devoid independent actors from any control over their own data.

Therefore, we assume that clients do not want to consent to direct data transfer and are only considering engaging in a collaboration which do not require them to take such

steps. Given that the participants have limited knowledge about the information coming from other distributions than their own, they still may be interested in information that could help them better understand the whole population. In such cases, all the actors may engage in a collaborative activity of collaborative computation (e. g. distributed analytics or distributed learning): in the first case (distributed analytics) they are interested in a single statistic regarding samples from other distributions; in the second (distributed learning) they participate to learn a hypothesis function $\tilde{h}(\vec{x})$ that minimizes the local loss functions on the datasets distributed differently than their own.

Both distributed computations, as well as the notion of **collaborative computation** in general, can be formalized as the composite function:

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}) = F(X_1) \oplus F(X_2) \oplus \dots \oplus F(X_i) \quad (3)$$

where: $F(X_1), F(X_2), \dots, F(X_i)$ are functions computed locally at each client, such that $F(X_i): R^d \rightarrow R$, and equation

(3) denotes the composition of all local contributions.

For example, let us assume we have p clients, and one possessing a dataset $\mathbf{X}_p =$

$\{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{y}_1), (\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{y}_2), (\mathbf{x}_3, \mathbf{y}_3), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_i)\}$ that may be distributed differently, and the maximum length of the dataset $|\mathbf{X}_p|$ may differ from client to client. Let us also assume that each vector \mathbf{x}_i contains n different features. In such case, one may be interested in statistics regarding the selected features across all the population. Function $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}_i)$ may in that case locally compute mean of the sample

$$\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i = \frac{\mathbf{1}}{|\mathbf{X}_i|} \sum_{i=1}^{|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i|} \mathbf{x}_i$$

where for each dimension n we obtain one scalar describing the mean of the local samples. Such results can be then aggregated and once again averaged before returning the final vector:

$$\bar{\mathbf{X}} = \frac{\mathbf{1}}{|\bar{\mathbf{X}}|} \sum_{i=1}^{|\bar{\mathbf{X}}|} \bar{\mathbf{X}}_i$$

is calculated and returned to all participants of the collaborative.

Another example of distributed computation is a collaborative approach to establishing the common hypothesis function $\tilde{h}(\vec{x}) \rightarrow y$ that is indirectly trained on data from all the clients. Given that the random variables are not independent and identically distributed, each local client can compute $F(X_i): \tilde{h}_i(X_i) \rightarrow y$ and send back only the aggregate representing the final hypothesis function \tilde{h}_i to the other members of the collaborative. Compound function from Equation (3) will be then a global hypothesis function that is made from composition of the local hypotheses functions. One simple algorithm that can be utilized to perform such aggregation is FedAvg – a vanilla baseline for Federated Learning [43].

The following definitions are independent of any particular implementation design. It may be possible that all the local aggregates are send back to the Central Orchestration

Node (CON) that is deployed by a third-party as a service [44]. It is also possible that the following schema is implemented in a fully decentralized manner with peer-to-peer connections [5,25,51]. The universal notation of compound operations denoted as \oplus was employed specifically, not to limit the domain of possible implementation designs. Hence, collaborative computation can be defined as any function $F(\mathbf{X})$ that accepts aggregates of the local functions $F(\mathbf{X}_1) \oplus F(\mathbf{X}_2) \oplus \dots \oplus F(\mathbf{X}_i)$ and broadcast the output to all the members who provided some aggregates of their local data.

Considering the multitude of circumstances under which the aforementioned methodology of data collaboratives can be used, it is advisable to define this concept as a set of principles that are fundamental to its existence, while the particularities of implementation may vary from case to case. Given an example, the personal data stores [58] may be seen as data collaborative, although their real implementation is quite different from what was presented here. On the other hand, existing solutions based on federated learning can be turned into data collaboratives. This flexibility is something that the concept of data property was devoid of. Hence, we believe, that the concept of data collaboratives is something that may fill up a gap in the current system of data governance.

4.4 Open Challenges Regarding Data Collaboratives and Directional Proposals

We can distinguish two major issues concerning the implementation of such an architecture, introduced here by a name of data collaborative, namely: metrics for individual contributions and the trade-off between local and global utility. The metrics for individual contributions could add an additional layer of utility to the functionality of data collaborative, as they would allow participants not only to perform collaborative computations, but also to track their individual contributions, thus enabling them to reward those who contribute more to the global data exploration. The trade-off between local and global utility is characteristic for methods of decentralized learning, although in the case of Data Collaborative, it is gaining even more importance, as generally such a solution should seek some kind of balance between interests of a different parties by its very definition. Therefore, we want to elaborate on these issues a little bit more, posing them as a challenge for further research on data collaboratives. Firstly, it is not a trivial task to establish common metrics for individual contribution, especially taking into account privacy constraints. If the information about contributions is disclosed to all members of the collective, each such disclosure may add an additional risk of infringing privacy or business interests in the data - and the magnitude is defined by the amount and type of information being disclosed. It is also a non-trivial question how we can measure individual contributions. The simpler the measure, the less informative it is regarding the real value of the contribution. The more complicated, the more risk there is that the measure will indeed cause a privacy infringement or will give raise to unjust and arbitrary model allocation.

Three approaches to the problem of contribution evaluation have been addressed in the literature so far, but the work on this issue should still be deemed to be at an early stage of development. The simplest and most intuitive approach to this problem is to take into

account the number of times that the particular client has been selected in respect to the total number of selections during the computational task. Let's assume that a computational task T requires at least k rounds, where in each round T_k only a subset of clients $C_s \subset C$ of cardinality $|C_s|$ is selected. Each round T_k we have a possibility to form $\binom{|C|}{|C_s|}$ different subsets. Depending on the relation of $|C_s|$ to $|C|$, a client C_i will have a different probability of being chosen multiple times. We can simply register the number of times each client C_i is chosen, and then divide it by the number of clients we choose each round, i. e. contribution

$$Con(C_i) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\text{selection}(C_i)}{k * |C_s|} \quad (4)$$

Approach presented in equation (4) requires a few additional assumptions that may not necessarily hold in our application scenario. Firstly, we must treat all the clients' participation equally, irrespective of the result. In many cases, this will not hold, because some clients' updates may be less valuable than others (we can just imagine client holding in its local dataset n samples, and a client possessing more than 10^n samples). In such a scenario, the disproportion of the contribution is striking. Secondly, we don't take into consideration the real computational resources needed to prepare the aggregates before sending it to the other members of the collective. In reality, such a simple metric will not hold in majority of cases.

The most common method for data evaluation, presumably started by [91] in a context of Federated Learning is the deletion diagnostic used to evaluate the difference between the selected metric of the model trained with and without the client i , i.e.

$$Con(C_i) = V(S \cup \{C_i\}) - V(S) \quad (5)$$

where V is a selected value function (e. g. the model accuracy on a test set). This way we can measure the difference that agent i is making on the aggregated (global) model. The [74] has extended this measure further by employing Data Shapley, an equation based on the Shapley Value [73]. This method was further used elaborated on in [92-94]. If we use Shapley Value for calculating the client contribution, then for each agent

$$Con(C_i) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{C_s \subseteq C \setminus \{i\}} \binom{|C| - 1}{k}^{-1} [V(S \cup \{C_i\}) - V(S)] \quad (6)$$

Formula (6) can be interpreted as simply calculating marginal contribution of client i in every possible combination of coalitions. Some authors have also moved beyond the Shapley value, proposing other methods of establishing individual contributions [3,27,47,90]. The deletion diagnostic is a static method of contribution evaluation. Therefore, it requires computing a model a number of times, which is far from a feasibility criterion posted in the real-life implementations. Additionally, the usage of Shapley value itself to calculate individual contributions may pose additional challenges, as the axiomatization of Shapley value presented in [73] may not be necessarily compatible with machine learning applications. One possible remedy that comes along consists of either reconstructing the models belonging to particular coalitions from gradients [citation] or performing Monte Carlo sampling to reduce the computational complexity

[citation]. Both methods are explored in the literature and deliver promising results. Resolution of the time complexity problem does not change the fact that the metric itself will only reflect the contribution expressed as the marginal change of the metric quality on the tested against preselected dataset. Thus, deletion diagnostic does not take into consideration the computational resources that are consumed during the collaborative computations nor the usefulness of the global model for the local collaborator.

Finally, we can take into consideration only the computational resources that are consumed during the training phase. The [84] presented some early and general considerations on the quantification of resource allocation in the Federated scenario [84], this works is also reflected by many other authors [27,79,88,89]. It may be up to the debate how this can be reflected in measuring the individual contributions.

Another open issue is connected to the trade-off between individual utility and global utility that was briefly mentioned in the preceding paragraph. As mentioned at the beginning of this subsection, in machine learning we distinguish between the generalised error and the empirical error. In ideal circumstances, we would like the global predictor to have smaller empirical loss on each of the local datasets than the locally trained predictors, i.e.

$$\mathcal{L}(\tilde{h}(X_i))_{ELF} \leq \mathcal{L}(\tilde{h}_i(X_i))_{ELF} \forall X_i \in \mathcal{C}$$

On the other hand, such situation may not occur, as empirical loss of the global hypothesis function may be greater than the local one on a number of local clients, i.e.

$$\exists X_i \in \mathcal{C}: \mathcal{L}(\tilde{h}(X_i))_{ELF} \geq \mathcal{L}(\tilde{h}_i(X_i))_{ELF}$$

In such cases, the general performance of the global model (hypothesis function) on the local client may seem lower than the performance of the local model. On the other hand, such model may generalise better even if the empirical loss (tested against the local dataset) is greater than the loss of the model trained on local data. Such model may still be more profitable to the individual agent, even if the empirical loss function would suggest otherwise. It is important to acknowledge, that the main goal of the hypothesis function $\tilde{h}(\bar{x})$ is always to predict new samples, which generally will be sampled from the distribution of the population, not the distribution of the client. Even if the empirical loss function seems to be higher for some particular local dataset, as the agent will encounter new samples sampled from the space of the population, the general loss function will behave better than the local one.

Taking into consideration all presented above we can formulate three additional directional proposals regarding data collaboratives. Primarily, each collaboration should be reflected in the fair division of shares between the collaborators. While those shares do not entitle to monetary compensation per se, they may be used – for example – as a quantification of a voting power of a particular participant. This way, while still formally being a collaborative, we implement a self-sovereignty mechanism for controlling commons. Secondly, calculation of shares should not only reflect the contribution brought into the model (defined as a marginal increase in a model’s performance), but also consumed resources. Furthermore, we open collaboratives for possible participants, who bring contributions not in the terms of data, but in terms of raw processing

power. This could also lead to distinguishing different role inside collaborative itself. Lastly, collaboratives should measure not only the objective contribution of each member, but also the local utility that is obtained by each of its members. Local utility may be measured, for example, in a distance between performance of the global model on the other models' data sets and on the local data set. Local utility could be further offset by the consumed resources – if the local utility is excessively below the consumed resources, each participant should have opportunity to opt-out from such a collaboration.

It can be noticed that all of the directional proposals are derived directly from the four essential principles presented before. Those essential principles are – in turn – derived from Ostrom's design principles for collective self-managing institutions. In this way, the proposed concept is not an arbitrary proposal, but a set of implementable solutions that are based on a well-established set of guidelines, while the implementation details are not constrained in any way by the imposed set of definitions. The transition between those three layers is even more manageable given the fact that Ostrom's principles were already explained in the context of data governance [2, 11, 64]. This article thus contributed to this discussion by further exploring and giving substance to the potential of data commons for data governance.

5 Conclusion

This paper took an interdisciplinary perspective on how to solve tensions resulting from diverging interests in data by providing insights in both, the regulatory as well as technological layer in data governance. First, it analysed the regulatory layer and the debates among scholars and policy-makers on how the seemingly opposed objectives of enhancing control over data while at the same time ensuring its availability to different stakeholders could be reconciled via a legal framework. Whilst property rights were discussed for several decades as a potential mechanism to empower individuals and companies with regard to 'their' data and to thereby enable the emergence of a data-agile economy, this approach has been abandoned by now. Instead, a 'paradigm shift' in EU policy has taken place from (legal) data ownership towards facilitating data access and data sharing.

Turning to the technological layer, we have framed data collaboratives as a commons management problem, therefore seeking a solution that may enable stakeholders to retain control over their local data while also allowing them to participate in the exchange of utilities (computational power) and collaboration (collaborative computations). We have presented our own novel approach to the problem of defining data collaboratives, introducing the notion of collaborative computation and four essential principles as a cornerstone of our definition. This approach exemplifies how technological solutions contribute to reconcile the seemingly opposed objectives of simultaneously achieving data control and data availability. The main difference between the standard use case of federated learning (or any other decentralised learning paradigm) and the solution proposed here is that in the data collaborative, there is no central entity that profits from the training and deployment of the model - every collaborative entity has its own interest in the model sharing and without the collaborative effort - the model would probably

never be created. It is the sum of common interests, combined computational power and granted access to the data that has given rise to the model creation (shared model governance). The four essential principles encapsulate the idea of shared data governance through collaborative partnership.

Whilst it was argued that data collaboratives can contribute to reduce tensions that result from the objectives of data control and availability, several open questions remain. Even though raw data does not have to be transferred among participants in the collaborative, it might remain possible to make inferences about the individual contributions of participants. This might consequently negatively impact their respective privacy or intellectual property interests. Furthermore, this article did not address the question on how to incentivize stakeholders to participate in the collaborative. More research is thus necessary to further elucidate how data collaboratives can be implemented in practice to resolve tensions in the data economy – requiring an interdisciplinary perspective from law and data science.

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Transparency and Relevancy of Direct-To-Consumer Genetic Testing Privacy and Consent Policies in the EU

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Abstract

The direct-to-consumer (DTC) genetic testing market in Europe is expected to grow to more than 2.7 billion USD by 2032. Though the service offers ancestry and wellness information from one's own home, it comes with privacy issues such as non-transparent sharing of highly sensitive data with third parties. While the GDPR states transparency requirements, in practice they may be confusing to follow and fail to uphold the goals of transparency – for individuals to understand their data processing and exercise their rights in a user-centered manner. Thus, we examined six large DTC genetic companies' public privacy and consent policies and identified information flows using a contextual integrity approach to answer our research questions about 1) How vague, confusing, or complete are information flows?; 2) How aligned with GDPR transparency requirements are existing information flows?; 3) How relevant is the information to users?; 4) What risk/benefit information is available? This study identified 59 public information flows regarding genetic data and found that 69% were vague and 37% were confusing regarding transfers of genetic data, consequently GDPR transparency requirements may not be met. Additionally, companies lack public user-relevant information, such as the shared risks of sharing genetic data. We then discuss user-centered and contextual privacy suggestions to enhance transparency of public privacy and consent policies and suggest the use of such a contextual integrity analysis as a governance practice to assess internal practices.

Keywords: DTC genetic testing, transparency, contextual integrity, consent, human-centered design

1 Introduction

Sequencing DNA has become more and more accessible, with multiple direct to consumer (DTC) genetic testing companies across the world offering services for discovering ancestry, health issues, and family members. Customers can even access this from the comfort of their home. By 2021, approximately 26 million people have taken an at-home ancestry test worldwide and the European market is expected to grow to more than 2.7 billion USD by 2032 [1] and the European market is expected to grow to more than 2.7 billion USD by 2032 [1]). Given that the European Union (EU) has some of the most advanced data protection laws in the world and considering the manifold risks that genetic data processing entails, are the genetic data flows transparently mapped and communicated, and are these in line with data protection requirements?

Genetic data is sensitive and should be subject to a very high standard of legal and technical protection, both due to the privacy concerns it raises and the legal safeguards enshrined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2]. Sharing and storing genetic information with DTC genetic testing companies carry many risks, such as data breaches where unknown actors have access to such private information [3], re-identification based on combining public datasets [4], data sharing with law enforcement [5], or discrimination by insurance companies [6].

Beyond individual harms, one customer's decision to enter the contract with a DTC genetic company may affect genetic relatives who share a large part of their DNA and were not part of that decision. After taking a genetic test, individuals can also allow companies to further use their data for research purposes or enter online communities for ancestry and genealogy purposes, both with their own privacy risks based on the context [7]. For example, members of genetic online communities may voluntarily reveal information for a specific purpose (e.g. finding relatives) but members of the online community with access to their data could violate their privacy by sharing their information with other parties without their knowledge; or regarding data sharing for research, the scientists and organizations related to the study may not prioritize ethical practices for data security and privacy based on how they process and store the data (e.g. on the cloud). In the privacy policies that are addressed to the public, thereby to potential and acquired customers, DTC genetic testing companies often only state a subset of the relevant risks [8], and do not convey the severity of such risks accurately to customers, only stating that potential risks are possible [9, 10].

The GDPR explicitly prohibits sensitive data processing (Art. 9(1)), only allowing it only under specific conditions (Art. 9(2)). For example, when the explicit consent of the impacted individuals is obtained, which is necessary if there is a "serious data protection risk" [11]. The GDPR also stipulates that crucial data processing information should be transparently communicated to data subjects (Art. 12-13). It must also be presented in an "intelligible and easily accessible manner, through the use of clear and plain language (Art. 7(2)). In the interpretation of such obligations, guidelines from the Article 29 Working Party (WP29) on transparency [12] offers examples of policies without vague terms (e.g. using "will process" instead of "may process") and suggest disclosing data processing consequences, going beyond the strict GDPR's transparency requirements of Article 13. As the benefits and marketing of DTC genetic test kits influence customers' decisions, individuals may base their decision of

using a DTC genetic testing service on incorrect privacy expectations [13] and flawed appreciation of the risks due to incomplete, inaccurate or misleading statements. Given the sensitivity of the data and the growing market for DTC genetic tests in Europe [1], many individuals may not be well informed without useful, transparent information and thus, not be able to exercise their rights properly.

To better understand and assess current practices, we surveyed 6 large DTC genetic companies' privacy and research consent (hereafter also referred to as "consent") policies. We were interested in the most publicly available, complete descriptions of data flows and practices, which are often the privacy policies (e.g., pages about data security redirect to privacy policies) and research consent policies for secondary research. We identified the genetic data information flows from privacy and consent policies using a contextual integrity (CI) framework [14] to answer: 1) How vague, confusing, or complete are information flows?; 2) How aligned with GDPR transparency requirements are existing information flows?; 3) How relevant is the information to users?; 4) What risk and benefit information is given and where is it located?

Our results show that 1) more than half of the identified 59 information flows used vague terms, 17% were missing information such as recipient, and 37% were bloated with up to 14 different reasons for sharing the data in one CI flow 2) from the previous analysis, CI flows were not always aligned of GDPR transparency requirements; 3) most companies lacked user-relevant contextual information [15]; 4) the communication about risks and benefits varies greatly across companies (1 to 6 types of risks shared) and lacks any collective risks. This confirms a pattern of non-transparent and non-compliant public information in policies but extends to a highly sensitive data type and quickly growing market. We discuss qualitative elements regarding the type of information that is relevant to users in order to better center users as the audience of such policies. Then we suggest possible tools and guidelines for more transparent, user-relevant policies with legal and ethical safeguards and suggest using a CI analysis as part of audits by data controllers and regulators.

2 Related Work

2.1 Privacy risks and harms of sharing genetic data

Protecting genetic data requires a higher bar when compared to other personal data because of the impact of the potential harms on the data subject, and even their relatives. For example, the immutability of such information can to lasting effects as data breaches of genetic datasets can occur [16] and they have a more severe impact: whereas one can change their password if compromised in a data breach, one can never change their DNA. Moreover, discrimination and stigmatization [17, 18] may occur from the availability of genetic data. Phenotypic inference can also lead to genetic discrimination, as the case of inference of Alzheimer's could be used by insurance companies in order to charge higher premiums [19, 20]. Other risks include possible re-identification from anonymous data, which was proved possible and even quite easy through the cross-referencing of two free databases in 2013 [21]. Even if the data is anonymous, the anonymity of genetic data is debated as it could be combined with other data wherein identifiable traits such as skin color, eye color, disease, or ethnic

subgroup may be inferred by the information and become identifiable [22]. With the rise of more genetic databases and digital health information from the private and public, it can be easier to cross-reference and use the aggregate information to infer individual or family details such as disease risks [4]. In the age of big data, privacy is not only individual but networked, especially genetic data which is connected to genetic relatives and may reveal sensitive information about them as well [23–25]. Lastly, genetic testing may infringe the "right not to know" from international biomedical law, which for example may mean that one can refuse any reports of secondary findings (e.g. genetic predispositions to disease that were not the subject of the service). However, this right is not uniformly enacted across legal jurisdictions and has been criticized for contradicting the doctor's duty to inform among others [26, 27].

2.2 Information flows and public transparency of DTC genetic testing services

The disclosure of information in privacy notices should be leveraged to not only mechanically fulfill legal obligations but rather to communicate useful, actionable information to the individuals and groups impacted by the data practices. When it comes to health data sharing in particular, a recent survey found that individuals across 22 countries highly value transparency about the data uses and purposes [28]. However, in practice, privacy policies are known to be time-consuming [29], unreadable [30], difficult to comprehend for non-legal experts [31, 32] and unusable as a decision-making tool [33]. This may be a somewhat deliberate attempt, as Bhatia et al. proposes that privacy policies use vague terms in an attempt to be legally comprehensive and accurate in many circumstances, especially in unclear situations for future-proofing [34]. Thus some level of vagueness or legal framing may be expected. However, privacy policies often offer the most comprehensive information about a company's data practices available publicly and are probably the most widespread instrument to implement transparency obligations. Thus, they are often used as a window into publicly shared internal data practices of a company by regulators and researchers alike.

Much of previous work analyzing the privacy policies of DTC genetic testing companies has a US focus, and researchers have found that their policies lack transparency and adequate protections against harms [35–37], especially in relation to data sharing with law enforcement [38, 39].

Outside of legal analyses, multiple tools and frameworks exist to analyze policy information such as privacy requirements engineering [40], machine learning via crowd-sourced or automated annotations [41, 42], and the contextual integrity (CI) theory framework [43]. We focus on the theory of CI, wherein Nissenbaum states that privacy can be described as the appropriateness of information flows as defined by contextual norms dictating their transmission [44]. As the context changes, so do the privacy risks and the related privacy decisions from an individual: since processing and re-using genetic data for various purposes has diverse, far-reaching consequences, CI can offer nuanced insights into the contextual nature of data sharing. CI can also constitute a helpful framework for analyzing information flows as researchers or auditors because it is built to identify shifting contexts which then have their own privacy risks, which may influence how individuals make their decisions.

The analysis of CI information flows can also constitute support for the auditing of data processing activities. It can be applied as a framework to inspect data flows and determine, in a structured way, how personal data is shared and for which purposes, as well as the risks (thereby implementing a necessary step for data protection by design [45]). It can also be used to verify the correct implementation of transparency obligations: as these are meant to enable individuals to shape reliable expectations about the use of their data, the information must be presented in a useful and understandable manner. This is why Article 12 of the GDPR sets user-centered transparency requirements that encompass the "quality, accessibility and comprehensibility of the information" [12] of the data processing practices and the data subjects' rights. This means that communications, be it privacy policies, consent forms, or other instruments for exercising data rights, should be tailored to the specific informational needs and the abilities of the intended audience, as well as be subject to empirical tests to demonstrate their effectiveness [12, 46]. There is a movement within legal communication away from lengthy documents full of legal jargon and instead towards using information design elements [47] to address the needs and abilities of the intended audiences (who are not only legal experts) [48] and enhance the readability and comprehensibility of information [49].

In the case of DTC genetic testing companies, the contextual norms are obscured and often conflated: for instance, various legal bases are mentioned together for processing sensitive data, or consent is requested for secondary research purposes that may involve financial gain or benefit the field of genetics without clarity about what research ethics safeguards are used. This was shown in a 2015 study [7], where the declared data practices of DTC genetic testing companies were assessed via the CI approach. Huang et al. analyzed the privacy policies, terms of service, presumed consent (wherein consent is embedded in policies and not explicit), and the accessibility of links on the homepage of the website of such companies. The CI approach was pivotal to identify three different contexts for data sharing (i.e., users involved in the online genetic company community, consumers utilizing genetics tests for reasons of ancestry, and consumers who have taken genetic tests who additionally participate in research activities) and the related potential privacy breaches.

Beyond how the information flows can create new privacy contexts, Johansson et al. [15] carried out discrete choice experiments with laypeople and experts to identify the attributes and levels of information that they found relevant to make decisions with. Their results showed higher level information, such as the category of data user (e.g., pharmaceutical company/entity, academic research, technical company, or national authority), if there will be an ethical review of data sharing and transfer, and the reason for data use (e.g., developing a product, marketing, evaluating their service, or aiding national policy) were most useful to people. Some elements go beyond legal requirements for transparency under the GDPR, or offer guidance for how to frame the information in such guidelines (e.g. by category of data processor and not the exact identity). By centering user research to determine elements of transparency, organizations can follow the legal principles underlying transparency with the guidance of empirical work.

When individuals decide to use a service, their privacy expectations and the necessity of that service often constitute a more determinant element than the privacy risks or data transparency available in privacy policies [50], which may be more meaningful for privacy professionals. This may be especially true for DTC genetic testing as studies have found that customers may be concerned about privacy but still decide to use the service [17] while not fully grasping the consequences (e.g. challenges to anonymizing data or family implications) [51]. Another study found that a common expectation about DTC genetic testing companies was that the data would only be shared with the customer and the sample would be destroyed after, which did not align with the actual policies [52]. Similarly, customers based privacy risks on their knowledge of social media risks and hoped that the DTC genetic testing companies would be ethical and "*won't do anything I'll regret*" [13]. If companies want to assuage such misalignments between expected practices and actual practices, it would be important that DTC genetic testing services convey the actual possible risks and actions one can take (e.g. request deletion of a sample, discuss risks with family members, etc.) and share their risk management strategies if possible. This can also help address the application of the fairness principle according to which processing should not be detrimental, discriminatory, unexpected, or misleading to individuals [45].

3 Research Questions

Stemming from gaps in understanding the DTC genetic website's informational transparency, compliance with GDPR transparency requirements, and user-relevancy of contextual decision making information, we collected privacy and consent policies on company websites regarding genetic data sharing to answer:

1. **RQ1:** How are the contextual integrity (CI) flows described in the available policies in terms of: including all parameters, using vague language, and parameter bloating (i.e., more than 2 concepts in one parameter)?
2. **RQ2:** How aligned are the CI flows with GDPR transparency requirements?
3. **RQ3:** To what extent is the information in CI flows aligned with existing user-relevant information categories for research [15] (i.e., data user, data collector, reason for data user, information and consent, and ethical review) and what is missing to address a commercial DTC genetic testing context?
4. **RQ4:** How many and what types of risks and benefits are stated across privacy and consent policies?

This study builds on Huang et al.'s work [7] as study on transparency and GDPR compliance of DTC genetic testing website policies. Then we will analyze the CI flow based on Shvartzshnaider et al.'s work [14], contexts from Huang et al. [7], alignment to GDPR transparency requirements and user-relevant information elements [15], and contextual risks and benefits information to evaluate the state of the art of transparency disclosures with user-centered elements.

4 Methods

4.1 DTC genetic websites contextual integrity flows

4.1.1 Company criteria and the corpus of text

We were interested in general trends in public transparency and presumed GDPR compliance and not specific companies, so we chose six DTC genetic testing companies with headquarters in the USA (23andMe, AncestryDNA, and Family Tree DNA), UK (LivingDNA), Spain (TellMeGen), and Israel (MyHeritage). In addition, the companies must have EU/UK versions of their website and policies and offer similar services of ancestry, trait, and/or wellness reports (excluding medical genetic disease, paternity, microbiome, and full genome tests) available directly to consumers at home (excluding business-to-business services or services requiring a medical professional) (Step 1 in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: A process map of the steps to identifying contextual integrity (CI) genetic data flows and analyses used.

We accessed the EU or UK English versions of DNA specific websites (if offered) from each company (e.g. AncestryDNA.com and not Ancestry.com) from December 2022 to January 2023. We assessed the privacy policy and informed consent pages available online as if we were potential customers seeking information. Since TellMeGen's privacy policy only concerns data collected during website usage, we analyzed their pages titled: "legal terms", which contains conditions for usage of the website and services offered, and "legal consent", which is given before entering the contract. We were satisfied with the documents available publicly on the company's websites for the assessment, thus we did not order the genetic tests to examine if additional information was provided to their purchasers. Moreover, the information available online should be sufficient for potential customers to decide whether to resort to a service rather than another one based on their privacy practices, as well as constitute an on demand notice for actual customers to consult at their will. Information on external

pages were not included as they were linked outside the policies and would expand the scope of this research too greatly, and because most pages would refer to the privacy policy of consent policy for more information. In the end our corpus included 10 privacy policies, 10 consent pages, 1 legal terms, 1 legal consent, and (Step 2 in Fig.1).

Parameter	Description
Sender	Entity who shares or transfers data
Recipient	Entity who receives information
Transmission Principle	Terms and conditions wherein transfers should occur, including descriptions of how information is collected/used
Attribute	Information type
Subject	Subject of information flow (usually implied)

Table 1: CI analysis method from Shvartzshnaider et al. [14]

4.1.2 CI flows

Using the corpus, possible public information flows were identified based on the mention of sharing genetic information (e.g. policies mentioning genetic data, DNA data, DNA samples, or unspecified personal information that may include genetic data) by Author 1 and 2 in privacy and consent policies to contribute to answering RQ1-3. These were highlighted by one author in a shared document then verified by the other author, and disagreements were discussed and resolved by mutual agreement. Then we used a CI annotation method from Shvartzshnaider et al. [14] that organizes elements of information flows into a sender, recipient, transmission principle, attribute, and subject. Such an approach builds upon Nissenbaum’s CI framework [44] to characterize information flows and analyze the information in its related privacy context, not only as separate elements (Table 1, see Step 3 in Fig. 1). Using examples [14], both authors assigned elements of CI flows to different parameters. The transmission principle was taken as the fullest block of text within a data flow that used keywords such as "based on consent", "to perform a service", or "in order to". It may contain auxiliary information about how the data was treated, but at its core it was about the purpose for transmission. An example of annotated text is shown in Fig. 2. We checked for agreement and discussed any disagreements by consensus.

To answer RQ1, Author 1 used the methods reported in [14] for *missing information* (i.e., identifying which parameters are missing in a CI flow), *parameter bloating* (i.e., identifying any parameters that have more than two discrete entries per CI flow), and *vague terms analysis* (i.e., text matching to vague terms list which identified common vague terms and categorized them based on lexical categories: numeric quantifiers such as most or some, modal terms such as may, likely, and possibly, generalization terms such as mostly, normally, or primarily, and conditional terms such as sometimes, as necessary, and depending [34]). While detecting missing information and parameter bloating may be subjective, to clarify the determination of confusing cases Author 1 consulted Author 2. Then, Author 1 analyzed the contents of CI flows in a spreadsheet and MaxQDA <https://www.maxqda.com/> to identify missing information and

We *[sender]* work with **other companies** *[recipient]* when providing and marketing the **Services** *[transmission principle]*. As a result, these companies will have access to or otherwise process **your** *[subject]* data, including some of your **Personal Information** *[attribute]*, in their systems. These companies are subject to contractual obligations governing privacy, data security, and confidentiality consistent with applicable laws. These companies and the Personal Information they may have access to include our:

- Laboratory partners** (such as your **DNA**); **DNA test shipping providers** (such as **name, shipping address, and phone number**); **Payment processors** (such as **Payment Information**); **Cloud services infrastructure providers** (Ancestry's web and mobile services are cloud-based services; **all your data resides with our cloud service vendors**); **Biological sample storage facilities** (such as **Biological Sample and DNA test kit code**); **Vendors that assist us in marketing and consumer research analytics, fraud prevention, and security** (such as **email address**); **Communications infrastructure providers** (such as **name and email address**); and, **Vendors that help us provide some Member Services functions**, like phone support or survey tools (such as **Account Information or name or email address**)

Fig. 2: Example of annotated CI flow from AncestryDNA.

parameter bloating, while the vague terms analysis was performed in R by pattern matching between the specific vague terms and the CI flow text, then counting the occurrences of vague terms by category (modal, numeric, conditional, generalization). One vague CI flow may have more than one vague term. Author 1 categorized each CI flow by context from Huang et al. [7], where the data sharing was positioned in the context of a user in online community, a consumer buying online genetic test, or a genetic test taker participating in research.

4.2 GDPR transparency requirements mapping

To address RQ2, Author 1 analyzed the GDPR transparency requirements to identify 6 legal requirements that could be extracted from CI flow parameters or analyses (See Table 3). Art. 12(1) states that information should be "concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language", of which can be assessed by parameter bloating (conciseness), missing information (completeness), and vague terms analysis (clarity). Art. 13(1)a requires "the identity and the contact details of the controller", which is usually the sender of the information or the recipient if the data subject is sending their information to the company. Art. 13(1)e requires information on "the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data", which could include third parties or other individuals in the context of online genetic communities. The purpose of processing (Art. 13(1)c), whether the personal data is a requirement to enter a contract (Art. 13(2)e), and if the controller intends to process the data for secondary purposes (Art. 13(3)) can be identified in the transmission principle of CI flows. Requirements of transparency regarding data subject rights, DPO contact details, or data storage length were excluded as they may be part of a transmission principle, but such information was usually found outside of information flows (e.g., data security, GDPR rights, and the Data Protection Officer contacts are often in dedicated sections in privacy policies without connection to data flows). From the CI flows analysis, the presence or absence of relevant GDPR requirements could be systematically evaluated, but it is not an assessment of compliance. For example, while vague terms can be markers for vague statements, even if a vague term is present a data protection authority or officer may not rule the statement unclear.

Attributes	Levels
Health Information Collector	Who collects the information? (technological company, academic research provider, etc.)
Data User	Who is the recipient of the data? (technological or pharmaceutical company, academic research project, etc.)
Reason for Data Use	Why the data user wants access? (develop a new product or service, advertise, etc.)
Information and Consent	Will the participant be informed? (Not informed, informed and opt-out, etc.)
Review of Data Sharing	Is there a review of data access and how is the decision made? (No review, review of transfer, etc.)

Table 2: Data sharing attributes from Johansson et al. [15]

4.3 User relevant information

While the CI information flow analyses can address general transparency of information, to answer RQ3 about user-relevant information, Author 1 looked to empirically derived results from a study by Johansson et al. [15] (Table 2) to analyze the quality of the information within CI flow parameters. Mappings to CI elements are included in Table 3, however the review of data sharing, information and consent, and sometimes reason for data were not included in the transmission principle or data flows but elsewhere in the corpus. Therefore, we used portions of the policies based on relevant keywords (e.g. review, ethical, opt-out, opt-in, purpose, goal, etc.) beyond the CI flows. For example, the reason for data use in consent policies was often in specific sections about the purposes of the secondary research. A codebook began with existing attributes from the research context [15] as a top-down approach, then a bottom-up approach was also used to address any missing attributes related to a commercial context. Author 1 tried to be objective in adherence to Johansson et al.'s work and uncertainties were discussed with Author 2, though not co-coded. Some new codes in the "reason for data use" category include subcategories like: "performing a contracted service", "unspecified research", "secondary DNA service", and "not stated" to expand the codebook to address DTC genetic testing use-cases. Coding was performed by Author 1 in MaxQDA and the codebook is available in Appendix 8.

4.4 Stated risks and benefits

To answer RQ3, Author 1 identified sections in the corpus referring to risks and benefits throughout the privacy and consent policies, which often were separate from CI flows, by using keywords such as "risk" or "harm", and "benefit", or "compensation". Using MaxQDA, each section was coded for the type of risk or benefit using a bottom-up approach to map types of specific risks (e.g., exposing your family, lost sample) and benefits (e.g., financial compensation, altruistic benefit) to broader categories (e.g., re-identification, data breach, etc) based on the types of harms they fell into. Then the number and variation of risks and benefits was analyzed through MaxQDA (codebook available in Appendix 8). To minimize subjectivity, categories of risks and benefits were coded with terms found in the corpus, for example the term for third

CI Flow Element	GDPR Transparency Requirement	User Relevant Attribute
Sender	Data controller (Art. 13(1)a) and concise, transparent, clear language (Art. 12(1))	Health Information Collector
Recipient	Recipients of personal data (Art. 13(1)e) and concise, transparent, clear language (Art. 12(1))	Health Information Collector, Data User
Transmission Principle	Purpose of processing (Art. 13(1)c, secondary purposes (Art. 13(3)) and concise, transparent, clear language (Art. 12(1))	Reason for Data Use
Attribute	concise, transparent, clear language (Art. 12(1))	

Table 3: Mapping or relevant attributes from the CI flow, GDPR transparency requirements, and user-relevant information.

parties stems from TellMeGen’s text "*undesired third parties (for example, health care provider service companies or insurance companies)*," and using common categories of risks from literature such as "data breach" to describe a sample being lost or stolen.

5 Results

5.1 Contextual integrity information flows

To answer RQ1, we identified 59 CI flows across all six companies’ publicly available privacy or consent policies directly or indirectly referencing the transfer of genetic data from customer to DTC genetic testing company, company to third parties, or company to other individuals. Based on the contexts identified in Huang et al. [7], we found that 7% of CI information flows map to context 1: “user in online community“; 54% to context 2: “consumer buying online genetic test“ context“, 22% to context 3: “genetic test taker participating in research“, and 17% with multiple contexts spanning all contexts (n=2), contexts 1 and 2 (n=4), and contexts 2 and 3 (n=4). Typically, the data flows began with the data subject as the sender and the DTC genetic company as the recipient, with the transmission principle outlining the services they must process the genetic data for. Then, CI flows describe how the DTC genetic company may send the data to third parties (such as subcontractors, law enforcement, authorized individuals, etc.) for various reasons in the transmission principle. Within the 59 CI flows, 22 mentioned sharing genetic data in addition to other personal information, 18 used the term “personal information“ with no clarification (which therefore may include genetic data), only 16 CI flows specifically mentioned the use of genetic or DNA sample data, 2 flows that did not mention any type of data (thus we assumed genetic data may be included), and 1 mentioned de-identified genetic information (but due to the nature of anonymizing genetic information, it is debated whether it is truly non-personal and it was included in our analysis [21, 22]). Thus our expert analyses may have included more CI flows than the average consumer might identify as relating to genetic data sharing, but internally companies might have more than was publicly shared.

Missing information

10 (17%) of CI flows had missing information, ranging from the transmission principle (n=4), recipient (n=4), attribute (n=1), and for one CI flow, recipient, attribute, and subject were all missing. Missing recipients were usually regarding data sharing for research or processing sensitive data for multiple purposes (including but not limited to research purposes). Second most common were CI flows with no transmission principles regarding law enforcement or service providers. For example, one lists several recipients, “information“ as the attribute, and only offers an example to illustrate a transmission principle, but does not describe the general terms and conditions: “*We may share information with our professional advisers including lawyers, accountants and insurance advisers. We do not routinely share genetic information with our professional advisers, but it would be possible that this could happen, for example if court proceedings relating to genetic data were to be brought against us*“ (LivingDNA). The wording implies that non-genetic information could be shared with professional advisors outside of court proceedings, and/or information may be shared with a subset of professional advisors in other cases (as the professions could deal with different situations). The information did not describe overall terms and conditions for data sharing of information with professional advisors, thus we annotated it as missing. There were several cases where only examples were stated with no specific terms of data transfer across different companies. The unclear example above can be contrasted with a clear transmission principle from TellMeGen, “*You authorize tellmeGen to pass on to you –partially or entirely – the results (report) of your DNA analysis as well as to those persons for whom you have given previous written authorization.*“

Missing information and GDPR requirements

To address RQ2, we mapped the respective CI analyses to relevant GDPR requirements and identify misalignments. From the missing information analysis, 17% of information flows lack the information items mandated by the transparency obligation because they are incomplete (Art. 12(1)). In addition, 5 information flows did not identify the recipient of data (Art. 13(1)e), 5 did not clearly state the transmission principle which relates to purpose of processing from Art. 13(1)c and the eventuality of further processing from Art. 13(3).

Parameter bloating

Parameter bloating was found in 37% of information flows. Figure 3 shows an example of parameter bloating from AncestryDNA. This statement has one sender, one subject, 8 attributes, 10 recipients, and one broad transmission principle. Overall, we found that statements across companies had one sender, up to 9 attributes, up to 8 recipients, up to 14 transmission principles, and one subject.

Parameter bloating and GDPR requirements

More than two discrete parameters (e.g. more than two types of recipients, more than two transmission principles) can be indicative of a lack of conciseness (Art. 12(1)), showing that 37% of information flows should be reformulated to be more direct.

Fig. 3: Example of CI parameter bloating from AncestryDNA text from Fig.2 with parameter bloating

Fig. 4: Total information flows with vague words by parameter

Vague terms

Analyzing the number of information flows that had vague terms in the recipient, attribute, and transmission principle, we found that most companies had vague terms in the transmission principle, which often corresponds to more volume of text when compared to the other two (Figure 4). 69% of the transmission principles contained vague terms. Slightly surprising was that even for the attribute and recipient, which

Fig. 5: The number of CI flows with vague terminology by category of vagueness and company

are much smaller texts, 14% of recipient statements and 24% of attribute statements used at least one vague term.

Diving into the types of vague terms used in Figure 5, we can see that across all companies modal words (e.g. *may*, *can*, *possibly*) were used in 69% of all surveyed companies' information flows. This is followed by numeric quantifiers (e.g. *certain*, *some*, and *various*) at 31%, condition terms (e.g. *depending*, *as needed*, *appropriate*) at 17%. Lastly, only MyHeritage used any generalization terms such as *normally*, *usually*, or *primarily* (8%).

Vague terms and GDPR requirements

From this mapping of predetermined vague terms deriving from [34], 69% of information flows may not be using clear language (Art. 12(1)) due to the prevalence of vague terms.

5.2 User relevant information

To answer RQ3 regarding a qualitative analysis of the attributes reported in Table 2 within the information flow and related information (e.g. the reason for data use) that would add important context for the customer, we found that the information flows were generally confusing or lacking important information that would be relevant to a user to make decisions about their health data sharing. We also contributed to the attributes by expanding the levels to address a non-research setting.

Data collector

The DTC genetic testing company most closely corresponds to a technological company data collector, as the customer enters a contract to use a service and sends their

data for analysis. However, this was inferred and they may also fall under an academic research project if the research consent is given.

Data user

Instead of identifying the recipient in CI flows by name or business category, the data user is a higher level category that reveals the types of recipients relevant to the consumers (e.g. technological or pharmaceutical company). For instance, in Fig. 3, the CI flow from AncestryDNA’s privacy policy shows many technological companies of various nature. Some new categories derived from the privacy and consent policies were *healthcare professionals*, *law enforcement*, and *other users via genealogy services*. When looking at the informed consent for the further use of genetic data for research, data users such as a technological company, pharmaceutical company, national authority, or academic research project arise. In the informed consent document for research, some companies do not distinguish the various types of research being conducted, for example, “*On some research, we will collaborate with leading academics and scientists.*” (LivingDNA).

Reason for data use

34% of CI flows had more than one reason for data use per flow. Overall, “providing a contracted service” was the most common reason for data use at 35.8%, followed by “developing a new product or service” (15.6%), and “unspecified research” (12.6%). This was a new category that had to be created because the documents did not specify if the research would be used for investigating a government policy initiative, developing a new product or service, or other objectives. An example of such an instance is “*Perform statistical, scientific, and historical research*” (FamilyTreeDNA).

Fig. 6: Percentage of coded segments with reasons for data use across companies

Information and consent

Information (if individuals will be informed when information is shared and used in a new context) and consent (opt-in or opt-out) is a user-relevant attribute that is not very clear within CI flows. While privacy policies describe the purposes of data use and it can be taken as information, it is often embedded in bloated transmission principles. For example, MyHeritage has a CI flow about service providers that describes 8

different service providers, each with their own information and consent for each (some where information is given and some where both information and consent are given).

Information and consent also varied across companies for sample storage, with 23andMe, AncestryDNA and FamilyTreeDNA including information and opt-in consent within the privacy policy. AncestryDNA for instance writes, “*after our laboratory partner has processed your Biological Sample, you can consent to its storage in our bio bank for future testing at your option [...] If you do not consent to the storage of your Biological Sample, we will destroy your sample.*” While the biological sample can be used for other purposes if the individual provides consents to it, the information also includes an opt-out consent for storage but it is unclear if storage itself entails any additional sharing and using the data in a new context (e.g. by the storage facility). TellMeGen instead informs individuals that the sample is destroyed after two months, and for LivingDNA the sample is destroyed after 10 years. Family Tree DNA stated that samples would be stored for future testing.

Review of data sharing

Only 23andMe and AncestryDNA publicly mention any review when the data is shared in a new context with regards to a type of ethical review in their informed consent policies. Of the two, 23andMe states that is overseen “*by an independent ethics review board (also called an Institutional Review Board or “IRB”).*” On the other hand, AncestryDNA will “*review all research requests for Biological and DNA Samples (as described below)*” but it never describes the type of review (e.g. using national laws, using corporate guidelines).

Some companies use technical or legal jargon that is too broad to determine if there protocols for review of data sharing are in place. For example, Living DNA mentions both “*The data [...] will only be used for ethically and scientifically approved research. Careful safeguards, in line with ISO:27001, are designed to ensure the confidentiality of your data and samples.*” They use jargon to refer to an international technical standard for information security management, however they do not share how ethical data use is ensured.

5.3 Stated risks and benefits for research purposes

Regarding RQ4, first we report the number and type of risk, as well as where it was located within policies. There are 37 risks that were identified, spanning 7 categories of risks (identification, sharing with third parties without consent, inaccurate results, secondary findings, data breaches, discomfort, and general catch-all risks) compared to 5 benefits over two categories (financial benefit or data altruism). The benefits were only stated in the consent policies, while risks were primarily in consent policies with some in privacy policies. Dedicated sections for risks and benefits were clearly stated in the informed consent policies for secondary research, while risks in privacy policies were found in data security or methodological sections. For example, MyHeritage states risks of data security issues and that “*[...] while our reasonable security program is designed to manage data security risks and thus help prevent data security incidents and breaches, it cannot be assumed that the occurrence of any given incident or breach results from our failure to implement and maintain reasonable security.*” and

TellMeGen and LivingDNA mentioned a risk of error in results, for example “*There is therefore a risk (albeit small), that any report we provide may not be accurate.*” (LivingDNA).

In the privacy policies, the framing is about minimizing liability to the company. They are often passive, as with MyHeritage’s statement about security risks. Even if they center the customer, they are specifying the responsibility the individual has, as TellMeGen writes: “*[...] in the event that you decide to share your genetic information with health care professionals, you run the risk that said information can become part of your medical history and, because of this, could be in the future accessible to undesired third parties (for example, health care provider service companies or insurance companies). [...] you acknowledge that you will: [...] assume responsibility for the possible consequences.*” This contrasts with the framing in informed consent for research policies, for example AncestryDNA writes, “*When Biological Samples are physically transferred from us to Collaborators, there is a potential risk that the samples could be lost or stolen while in transit or storage. We take precautions to reduce the likelihood that this will happen and your Biological Samples are not transferred with your name or contact information*” which includes information about mitigation strategies to decrease risks to the customer.

Fig. 7: Risks across companies in descending order, based on percentage of coded segments

Risks

The type of risk communicated also varied widely between companies. As shown in Figure 7, the 7 risk categories span inaccurate results, general risks (including any future risks), data sharing with undesired third parties (e.g., law enforcement or insurance) that may lead to discrimination, identification from the data (e.g., re-identification, family and trait inference wherein genetic variants may be correlated with health, cognitive performance, and more), secondary findings (e.g., unexpected genetic relatedness, disease risk, etc.), data breaches (both on physical samples and genetic data), and discomfort from questions. Also interesting were two anti-risk categories, wherein they explicitly state an absence of physical risk (n=3) or any risks

associated with withdrawing consent (only in 23andMe). Different companies would mention different subsets of risks, with some companies trying to be more exhaustive (e.g. TellMeGen notes 6 out of 7 types of risks, while LivingDNA only mentions the risk of secondary findings).

Benefits

The benefits of participating in research are only stated in three companies' (i.e., AncestryDNA, MyHeritage, 23andMe) informed consent policies. They usually follow the same format, stating that it is free to participate, that there will be no financial compensation (with the exception of 23andMe mentioning the possibility of financial compensation via cash or charitable donations), that results of the research studies are not provided to the participants (with the exception of 23andMe that mentions that they *may* inform individuals of research findings), and that consenting to sharing genetic data will benefit research. This last benefit is framed very broadly as to what research entails. For example, "*Your participation may help advance scientific or medical knowledge,*" (AncestryDNA), "*[...] this will assist academics and researchers to better understand the human species, learn or confirm certain facts and make predictions about future trends. Thus, the more Personal Information for Research is contributed to the Project, the better any potential results*" (MyHeritage), and "*Sometime in the future, you or others, including people who share your ancestry or health characteristics, may benefit indirectly from 23andMe Research discoveries, such as those that improve 23andMe product or services offerings or contribute to ways to prevent and treat disease*" (23andMe).

Interestingly, AncestryDNA includes a section that does not concern customer benefits, but financial benefits to companies or employees from the secondary research activities: "*In some instances, AncestryDNA receives compensation from Collaborators who work on the Project. Some of the researchers who are employees of AncestryDNA also have a significant amount of stock or other ownership in AncestryDNA or Ancestry.com.*" The impact this may have on an customer's choice to consent for research purposes is hard to assess however, as there is no monetary values for potential data sharers to understand if they are contributing to a nominal or lucrative business, and it is unclear if they should feel entitled to financial compensation, or at least know the reason for data use.

6 Discussion

Overall, out of 59 CI flows about genetic data sharing, 69% used vague terms, 17% were missing information such as the recipient, and 37% were bloated with up to 8 different recipients, 9 data types, and 14 reasons for data sharing (**RQ1**). This shows a lack of informational transparency and subsequently a possible misalignment with GDPR transparency requirements from Art. 12(1) on concise, transparent, and clear language, 13(1)a,c,e on the identity of the data controller, purpose of processing, and recipients of data, and 13(3) on secondary purposes (**RQ2**). Evaluating the information in CI flows and in the corpus when necessary, the relevancy of the information to users was low – for example, a data use category, "unspecified research," had to be

created because it appeared in about 12% of CI flows, but is not specific or useful to decision making (**RQ3**). Across privacy and consent policies, different types of risks were shared across privacy (data security and methodological risks) and consent policies (identification, unspecified future risks, data security, undesired third parties, inaccurate results, secondary findings, and discomfort) with a more legal or user-centered framing, respectively (**RQ4**).

6.1 Informational opaqueness

Regarding RQ1, such vague, incomplete, bloating, and generally confusing statements make it difficult to interpret the kinds of data practices that the companies resort to, the reasons why they share data with other parties, and how to understand and evaluate them. This can lead to customer misinterpretation [13] and incorrect privacy expectations [53]. Moreover, this casts doubts on the purpose of data sharing, which should be specifically defined following one of the main principles of data protection under the GDPR. The cumulative effect of vague terminology and of incomplete or bloated information about recipients of data sharing and data processing purposes may give an overall impression of non-transparent data policies and data practices of the surveyed companies that extends beyond the communication of such aspects to potential or acquired customers. The many possible data flows and the broad transmission principle may lead to confusion due to the many different scenarios, each with their own risks and benefits, that must be evaluated together in one statement from the policy and instead of reassure the individual that their data is being used properly, only raise more questions.

Regarding the results for RQ2, transparency requirements were presumably not met in all publicly available CI flows, especially with missing data controllers in Art. 13(1)a (missing sender), recipients of personal data in Art. 13(1)c (missing recipient), or the purpose of processing in Art. 13(1)e and if the data would be used for secondary purposes in Art 13(3) (missing transmission principle). Arguably parameter bloating of 14 different transmission principles in one data flow may not be concise or clear language might be lacking due to the presence of vague terms. From the list of vague terms [34], 69% of CI flows used one or more vague terms. However, companies may be withholding this information on purpose or using vague language to fulfill legal needs. The audience of such documents is then unclear, is it a legal expert or an individual? The audience of the Article 29 WP guidelines on transparency are presumably both a legal expert and individual, as they suggest moving away from the usage of vague qualifiers such as, "may," to terms such as "will" when possible [12] and to be more specific about the purpose of processing. For example, instead of "*We may use your personal data for research purposes*" wherein the research is unclear, they suggest "*We will retain and evaluate information on your recent visits to our website and how you move around different sections of our website for analytic purposes to understand how people use our website so that we can make it more intuitive*" to clarify the type of data, analysis, and purpose. Moving away from vague terms towards shorter, more transparent data flows can uphold the principle of transparency wherein companies can be more clear and accountable to users. This can contribute to users' understanding of what rights they have regarding different contexts (e.g. regarding the contracted

service, secondary research, online communities). On the other hand, it may be too cumbersome to completely replace all data flows with more direct language because it would cause frequent updates, or policies may be out of date. Such directness should be prioritized when the possible consequences are large or when individuals have different rights they could exercise. Additionally, there is a debate on whether the consent given within the scope of a contractual relationship is freely given and therefore valid is still ongoing [11, 54–57]. Under the GDPR, consent as a legal basis would give different rights to the individual than other legal bases. For instance, if processing is based on consent then the data subject would have the right to withdraw consent, but if processing is based on the performance of a contract then the data subject would not have this right. This information should be clearly stated and user-friendly tools could help exercise control over one’s personal data by withdrawing, requesting access, or more [12].

6.2 Lack of relevant transparency

We were not only interested in legal requirements, but also the quality of information for user-relevant attributes (RQ3) that can contribute to providing understandable accountability, safeguards, and information about what rights individuals can exercise under the GDPR.

The ethical review of data sharing is especially interesting for DTC genetic testing companies given the sensitive health data they process and the history of bioethics stemming from human rights violations in the 1800s and in WW2 [58]. Usually, the decision to consent in biomedicine is safeguarded by ethical review boards, professional codes, and institutional protocols to help uphold the ethics of a consent choice and mediate the paradox of an individual’s decision to give consent when the risks may not be conceivable, no matter how transparent the information is [59]. Individuals may not even try to assess the practices, as the policies are opaque and confusing as we have shown here as others also have and others have assessed [7, 60–62]. Individuals often find the information overwhelming or the consequences of data processing difficult to grasp, and instead base their decisions on privacy expectations [50–52], that may be correct or not. Given the volume of information and expertise needed to evaluate privacy and consent policies (wherein the authors were also sometimes confused), it is cumbersome, when not impossible, for end-users to carefully and autonomously assess the risks and benefits of genetic data disclosure. If other companies have such a review, it would be useful to share this information. Such third-party oversight can be a useful safeguard to offer more independent and expert control over the transfer and use of sensitive data by other parties.

The type of data collector and reasons for data use was often missing, confusing, or vague. For example, when is the DTC genetic testing company a technological company providing a service and when is it an academic or pharmaceutical research? This is especially non-transparent in consent policies. 23andMe states a possible overlap in their research consent wherein "*Some 23andMe Research may be sponsored by or conducted in collaboration with third parties, such as non-profit organizations, pharmaceutical companies, or academic institutions whose additional expertise and/or resources can help 23andMe make important discoveries.*" However, individuals are

generally more positive towards academic and non-profit institutions [13] compared to pharmaceutical companies and may wish to only consent to certain types of data uses by certain data collectors. It might be useful to allow for more granular consent for certain types of research the participant aligns with (e.g., no pharmaceutical research, only academic research). In addition, while genetic data for research is often shared in the hopes of benefiting society [13, 53], some employees may be benefiting financially (as shown in the results). While the statements in consent policies may be vague about who they partner with, in 2018 23andMe partnered with pharmaceutical company GlaxoSmithKline for a 4-year partnership to develop for-profit drugs [63]. Participants may not know that if they consented for research purposes, they were also giving a pharmaceutical company their data for for-profit purposes. The company employees may also finally benefit as with AncestryDNA wherein employees may "*have a significant amount of stock or other ownership in AncestryDNA or Ancestry.com.*" Academic and non-profit research may also convey an image of altruism and lead individuals to believe that [53], while academic partnerships can lead to for-profit interests in the very same research outcomes [64, 65]. To address this, some additional user-relevant attributes might include if the data will be shared openly or what the financial motivations are in addition to attributes such as ethical review. Thus customers can more easily match their expectations with reality to make informed decisions.

To institutionalize such user-relevant attributes, machine-readable ontologies such as the open source Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) [66], might be a useful tool. They can help automate internal data management and policy generation as well as help to create standards in the open science space. The DPV has an extensive list of purposes for data processing and can be extended to specific use cases. Other ontologies exist for sharing genetic data, such as the Data Use Ontology (DUO) [67] from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). From that, a system using DUO can match different types of data with different permissions to those who are searching for datasets and manage data use requests. It is currently being piloted by the US National Institute of Health <https://duos.broadinstitute.org/home>. Such ontologies or tools could help institutions to standardize and automate some aspects of their system in a user-relevant, transparent manner.

Moreover, tools have been built to scan policies and assess the presence or absence of transparency requirements [68] or with all GDPR requirements [69] and can help DPOs and internal auditing. This can decrease the time needed to read long policies and identify relevant information. In the future, such tools could be enhanced by adding a contextual integrity layer on top. While the tools may break down the information automatically, they do not consider the context: even if the policy is GDPR compliant about the purposes of data processing, if there are 14 different processing purposes in one statement then it is difficult for a reader to understand and consider all the possible consequences. A CI approach can add context about if the information flow is transparent from a more holistic perspective. Further analyzing the information by CI flows and parameters along with qualitatively analyzing user-relevant attributes can streamline the process to analyze policies both for GDPR compliance and user-centered transparency. Such a transparency-enhancing process would also fulfill one

of the necessary steps to ensure data protection by design (Article 25), which encompasses the selection and implementation of appropriate technical and organizational measures that depends on a robust, nuanced appreciation of the specific context of processing and the related risks for the rights and freedoms of individuals (and their families) [45].

6.3 Risks from a consumer perspective

The answer to RQ4 elucidated the number, type, and location of risk and benefit information in privacy and consent policies. Our analysis identified various hurdles to risk communication, for example, the framing differences from privacy policy to consent policies and how companies can include as many (6 categories) or as few risks (one category) as they see fit from 7 categories of risks, each with different levels of detail.

First, an individual may not be sufficiently informed about the risks of sharing their genetic data with DTC genetic testing websites and may therefore be led to downplay the harms they could incur. This is especially concerning due to the sensitive nature of genetic data. While privacy policies are often written as data protection documents by legal experts, they are often the most complete document available for individuals to assess possible risks. For example, MyHeritage's privacy policies says, *"while our reasonable security program is designed to manage data security risks and thus help prevent data security incidents and breaches, it cannot be assumed that the occurrence of any given incident or breach results from our failure to implement and maintain reasonable security."* While legally the statement may be sound, it does not meet customer expectations. A woman who was part of a class action lawsuit against MyHeritage due to a data breach [3] stated that she would have not used the genetic services if she had known that the necessary precautions were not in place [70]. If companies want to address customer expectations and reassure them, privacy policies should also be written with an individual in mind. This would also align with the direction in which legal design is moving [47, 48].

While consent policies may be framed to address participants using active language and with a clear subject (e.g. "you"), the risks are still varied in number and category across companies and do not usefully address concerns. For example, the company whose one stated risk of unexpected secondary findings would not address any of the top harms from a survey across 22 countries of attitudes towards genomic sharing [71]. The three most commonly feared potential harms from the study were: if friends or the government obtained information without consent and the use of the information for marketing purposes. Also, while it is difficult to convey probabilities for genetic risks, usage of simple pie charts or '100 person diagrams' were preferred by participants in a study, though the most desired option was access to a health professional for questions [72]. Directly addressing common concerns using simple graphs and pictograms with professional support may be useful for DTC genetic testing websites to share risks more concretely and assuage concerns. A solution from the EU is a Data Protection Impact Assessment [73] for the purpose of delineating those risks and devising appropriate mitigation measures for those processing special categories of data (e.g. genetic data) at scale (Art. 35(3) GDPR). Not only is it good internal practice that enables

organizations to manage the substantial data protection risks that arise from genetic data processing, but some of the information could be communicated to customers to increase transparency.

Second, there was a lack of any collective harms and benefits in the privacy and consent policies. This is especially concerning as such harms do not only impact the individual that subscribes to the service: such a single-handed choice affects their genetic relatives, including past and future generations. The risk of re-identification and identification via genetic relatives has an increasing likelihood of occurrence as larger datasets are collected [21]. In the US, the Golden State Killer suspect was identified from a third cousin who was a distant relative from the 19th century [74], whose data were uploaded on the public genealogy database GEDMatch, whose purpose is for people to find relatives for personal reasons. Some DTC genetic testing companies offer genealogy communities as well and the possible entanglement with law enforcement is questionable: for instance, FamilyTreeDNA works directly with law enforcement in the USA [5]. Though similar collaborations are not yet reported in the EU, they may nevertheless impact European citizens or EU residents. An open question concerns whether law enforcement should be allowed to use data that were originally contracted to help consumers understand their genetic relations and health risks to search for possible criminals. No privacy or consent policies mention risks to genetic family members [25] or suggest that individuals discuss the opportunity of taking a genetic test with their families to make a group decision. This lack of common deliberation and the silence around this issue can be especially harmful since privacy is contextual and networked [24], so even if one individual tries to protect their privacy, another person's privacy choices may directly impact them. Conversely, they may not share the benefits of taking a DTC genetic test. Such relational risks should be clearly stated as to give impacted individuals and their family members a chance to understand the shared consequences and decide together.

While collective notice and consent is important, there are no clear guidelines for its implementation. A study was conducted that found no global consensus on how to give notice even though individuals might expect stronger safeguards [75]. While safeguards were suggested, it is not enshrined in any declarations or documents to create standards yet. In addition, collective consent has been used in biomedical research to respect indigenous cultures and their collectivist governance structures wherein communities are consulted and asked for consent [76–78]. While this research has been performed off-line, a dynamic digital platform for collective dynamic consent system in Australian Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities have been positively discussed [79]. The need for family consent has also been discussed by legal and ethical scholars [80, 81]. However, translating such proposals into actual safeguards and digital tools is still an ongoing subject of research.

7 Limitations and Future Work

This study only assessed public policies from a certain time period. So we may be missing information that could be gained through the terms and conditions, upon signing the contract, receiving the kit, on the portal with the results, that were added after

our analysis period, or that are internally available. However, we were most interested in the public consent policies to analyze what information a potential customer might have before entering the contract. We also did not analyze the privacy and consent policies from a user perspective but an expert perspective, as potential customers may not be interested in the vagueness of terms as the privacy policy is itself inaccessible. This work was an initial survey of general practices from exemplar companies, and we do not intend this to be an indictment of the companies themselves. We did not reach out to companies to clarify their policies and justify their choices. In addition, some company websites have auxiliary pages to describe the contents of the privacy policy using icons, videos, and more that we did not assess. For example 23andMe's privacy policy link at the bottom of the page directs the user to a page with icons and text wherein one can find the link to the full privacy policy. This is the first layer and may change the user experience in ways that we do not yet understand and influence some of the guidelines we gave in the discussion. We also did not assess any structural elements within policies that might enhance readability or skimming, such as bullet points, bolded text, etc. We were solely interested in the text and the quality of information in the text.

Future work should be carried out to validate the new user-relevant attributes, reach out to companies to understand their perspective of policies and their internal practices, and research collective notice and consent.

8 Conclusion

This study contributes to a survey of informational transparency of 6 DTC genetic testing privacy and consent policies from a user-centered, privacy context aware, and GDPR compliant angle. The study identified how current policies lacked transparency and possible GDPR non-compliance while analyzing the information with regards to the quality of user-relevant attributes and risk and benefit information. While policies have been known to be non-transparent, even with GDPR transparency requirements there is still vague language, missing information, and parameter bloating. Furthermore, beyond legal requirements of transparency, human-centered information about risks, benefits, data users, and review of data sharing can help guide privacy policy and consent policy writers in how to enhance usable privacy and transparency. Such an analysis with CI flows can also aid data protection officers or auditors in assessing transparency and compliance of internal practices with both a GDPR and a contextual privacy perspective. We hope this work can encourage more nuanced, human-centered informational transparency for sensitive genetic data sharing so that DTC genetic tests can be taken with more confidence.

Data Availability

Link to codebook and CI flows: https://osf.io/z8fa5/?view_only=08d4d6b145544e6eb4eddbd808998339. Other data is available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Author Contribution

Conceptualization: Xengie Doan, Fatma Sümeýra Dođan, Arianna Rossi; Methodology: Xengie Doan, Fatma Sümeýra Dođan; Formal analysis and investigation: Xengie Doan, Fatma Sümeýra Dođan; Writing - original draft preparation: Xengie Doan, Fatma Sümeýra Dođan; Writing - review and editing: Xengie Doan, Arianna Rossi

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9 Declarations

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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From Data Governance by design to Data Governance as a Service

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Abstract

Nowadays, companies and governments collect data along every phase of a product/service life cycle. The data is acquired and stored in various and continuous ways, contributing to a large and unique data fingerprint for every product/service in use. Thus, establishing policies, processes and procedures (P3) around data and subsequently enacting those to compile and use such data for effective management and decision-making is extremely important. Data governance (DG) plays an essential role in a dynamic environment with multiple entities and actors, complex IT infrastructures, and heterogeneous administrative domains. Indeed, not only is it beneficial for existing products/services/processes, but it can also support appropriate adjustments during the design of new ones. This research provides an overview of the existing literature and current state-of-the-art in the domain of data processing and government aiming to evaluate existing approaches and to investigate their limitations. To this extent, this study introduces a novel approach for data governance as a service (DGaaS), which provides a framework for (private or public) organizations that facilitate alignment with their vision, goals and legal requirements. Finally, it discusses the potential implication of DGaaS in the smart city and healthcare sectors.

Keywords: Data Governance, Data Processing, Data Quality, Decentralisation, Trust, Reliability

1 Introduction

Many organizations consider data as one of the most important assets [1] [2] [3]. By leveraging data processing (DP), they transform raw data into valuable information and tangible business/economic benefit. Data governance (DG) plays a crucial role in defining, implementing, and monitoring the context, responsibilities, tools and stakeholders involved in DP. It refers to the system of decisions and accountabilities that regulate and guide information-related processes, ensuring adherence to pre-defined policies [4]. DG outlines permissible activities, assign responsibilities to different entities and stakeholders, and determine the data to be used. It also enforces rules to enable proper data management (DM) throughout its entire lifecycle [5].

In the context of AI-based systems, DG takes a broader role as the system of processes and infrastructures that enable organizations to align AI-based technologies with their strategies, objectives, and values while maximizing the value of data [6]. To this effect, some studies propose data governance by design (DGbD), which provides matrices that facilitate the design of effective data governance frameworks (DGF) for organizations [7]. DGbD offers a comprehensive and proactive approach to managing and upholding organisations' applications and processes. It ensures through oversight of the associated data throughout its entire lifecycle, ranging from requirements elicitation and engineering to execution management.

Data is sensitive and ubiquitous in the organization's activities. The emergence of distributed systems has led to collaborative data processing (CDP), involving multiple entities and actors [8] [9]. In this context, DG encompasses a set of principles that govern the data flows processed by various entities and actors. It establishes rights and responsibilities that guide DP according to agreed-upon models, and enforcing actions that can be taken, by whom, with which data, and for what purposes [4]. DG ensures compliance with legal, ethical, regulatory, and data protection requirements, as well as the constraints imposed on DP activities. Additionally, organizations require effective strategies and performance to extract value from data and maintain a competitive edge. However, traditional approaches such as DGbD are no longer sufficient in addressing the evolving landscape. Indeed, the field of DG warrants further research and development [10]. To address the challenges posed by decentralisation and distribution, there is a need for a flexible and scalable DGF.

This research proposes a novel framework that guides organizations in designing, developing, and implementing DG systems aligned with their vision, business objectives, and legal constraints [11], while at the same time increasing awareness among individuals and teams involved in the value chain. It introduces the concept of data governance as a service (DGaaS), which provides structured and comprehensive support within the organisational context and business environment [12]. DGaaS is a robust framework that goes beyond traditional DG approaches. It provides a range of services and support to address the complexities of DG in distributed environments. By adopting DGaaS, organizations can leverage a structured and scalable approach to ensure effective DG aligned with their specific needs. The DGaaS framework serves as a valuable resource for organizations, facilitating the management, control, and utilization of data assets while promoting compliance, collaboration, and innovation in an increasingly interconnected landscape.

1.1 Background and motivation

The increasing popularity of DG is closely tied with the growing recognition of value inherited in data as observed by Zygmuntowski et al. [13]. Before the emergence of Big Data and AI, DG primarily focused on the data control and management and it constituted a task that was performed mostly by private organizations. Today, there is a growing concern among policymakers to facilitate data flows across companies and public administrations, aiming to enhance data re-use, sharing and publication to maximize its value. Yet, data often involves various, sometimes conflicting interests, such as privacy or intellectual property. Therefore, a DGF should enable data flows to be ‘as open as possible and as closed as necessary’, ensuring that the interests of different stakeholders are respected when re-using data from other entities.

Scholars have recently emphasised that DG involves exercising authority and control over the entire lifecycle with the objective of increasing the data value while minimizing associated costs and risks [14]. Others advocate for holistic approaches to DG, differentiating between various layers: the regulatory layer, the organizational layer, and the technological layer [15]. Another perspective, put forth by Micheli et al., adopts a social-science lens to understand DG. They explore power relations among entities and actors affected by or influencing DP and how the generated data value is distributed among them [16].

These diverse perspectives highlight the multifaceted nature of DG, encompassing both technical and social dimensions. By incorporating these perspectives, organizations can develop comprehensive DG strategies that align with their specific goals, uphold stakeholder interests, and optimize the value derived from data. Overall, this research can contribute to advancing knowledge, providing practical insights, and addressing critical issues related to DG, and organizational effectiveness in the data-driven era. In the next section, we outline the main challenges of current DG systems.

1.2 Challenges posed by current systems

The establishment of an optimal DG system lacks consensus, both within a country and across borders [17] (*Challenge 1*), mainly due to the absence of harmonisation among diverse national laws and regulations. Recognising the need for additional measures beyond the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [18], the European Commission has emphasized the importance of fostering private-public data sharing frameworks and requiring data sharing among companies. This raises questions about data control, storage, sharing conditions (*Challenge 2*), and the operation of effective DG systems (*Challenge 3*). In response to these challenges, the EU Strategy for Data [19] has been introduced, highlighting the development of Common European Data Spaces as a crucial enabler for the Digital Economy. However, the current state of data usage is fragmented, with data being stored and processed in isolated silos, following either legacy or proprietary formats [20], leading to the need for extensive re-processing when shared with other stakeholders (*Challenge 4*). This involves addressing semantic, syntactic, and technical disparities, resulting in redundant resource consumption. Moreover, the creation of cross-sectional Data Spaces presents significant difficulties,

necessitating the establishment of sector-specific Data Spaces based on domain characteristics and standards (*Challenge 5*), such as the European Health Data Space (EHDS) [21].

The challenges posed by Big Data, including the substantially larger volumes and complex DP, call for a comprehensive DGF. The European Union is currently considering additional legislation, such as the Data Act (DA) [22] to enhance data access and utilisation, the Data Governance Act [23] to establish data exchange platforms, the Digital Markets Act (DMA) [24] to ensure that data guardians do not impede innovation, and the AI Act (AIA) [25], the European regulatory and legal framework for AI. These initiatives aim to unlock data currently confined within silos and effectively enforce the broad data protection framework outlined in the GDPR.

Within this context, this paper presents the architectural framework and key challenges of an integrated environment designed to provide trustworthy mechanisms for DDP using AI and Big Data analytics. The proposed framework, known as DGaaS, aims to contribute to the research, technological, and societal landscapes by addressing ethical, legal and regulatory concerns, and trust issues. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the current state-of-the-art and emerging technologies that focus on data processing and governance, with an emphasis on reliability and trust. Section 3 introduces the proposed DGaaS solution, outlining the high-level architecture and the various integrated components developed to tackle the challenges associated with the use of AI and Big Data. Furthermore, Section 4 discusses the expected broader impacts of DGaaS, specifically examining its potential applicability in the smart city and healthcare sectors. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper, summarizing the key findings and highlighting the significance of the proposed framework.

2 State-of-the-art and emerging solutions

With the advent of cutting-edge technologies such as quantum computing, edge computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT), organizations today are confronted with the need to handle vast and diverse amount of data to gain valuable insights and knowledge. By engaging in DP, organisations can effectively comprehend customer's needs, and accomplish their business goals. This capability enables organisations to maintain their competitiveness, swiftly adapt to evolving circumstances, and capitalise on emerging opportunities. These technologies are reshaping DP in different ways, offering new possibilities for enhanced efficiency, scalability, and connectivity. Simultaneously, they provide viable solutions that can be implemented in decentralised and collaborative environments, ensuring greater reliability and trust.

Quantum computing leverages the principles of quantum mechanics to perform computations that surpass the capabilities of classical computers. It utilizes quantum bits (qubits) that can represent multiple states simultaneously, enabling parallel processing and solving complex problems at an unprecedented speed [26]. Quantum computing has the potential to revolutionize DP by accelerating tasks such as optimization, security, and simulation [27]. It holds promise for solving computationally

intensive problems that are currently impractical or infeasible with standard computing, while at the same time, provides stronger data security measures, protecting sensitive information from potential cyber threats, and optimised resource allocation, evading to more efficient utilisation of resources, improved task scheduling, and better load balancing.

Edge computing refers to DP at or near the node of the network, closer to the data source or end-user devices. By decentralizing computational power, edge computing reduces latency, enhances real-time decision-making, and alleviates network congestion [28]. It enables DP to occur closer to where the data is generated, resulting in faster response times and improved efficiency [29]. This enhances data privacy and security, reducing the risk of data breaches or unauthorized access during data transmission. Edge computing is particularly valuable for applications and industries such as autonomous vehicles, industrial IoT, and smart cities that require low latency, high bandwidth, and real-time processing.

IoT enables seamless communication and data exchange between devices, facilitating automation, monitoring, and control of various processes [30]. It has transformed industries such as healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture, and transportation by enabling efficient resource management, predictive maintenance, and enhanced decision-making based on real-time data [31].

As these technologies continue to advance, their integration and synergy with traditional and decentralised DP systems will further transform the way data is processed, enabling new insights, applications, and possibilities across various industries and domains.

2.1 Data processing

Data processing (DP) is performed in a sequential series of steps aimed at extracting valuable information and insights to enhance organisational governance. As emphasised by Shah et al., the main conceptual components of DP are data management and data governance [32]. In our research, we have adopted an enhanced approach to the Data Lifecycle Framework (DaLiF), as depicted in Figure 1, which ensures adherence to the principles outlined in the DMBok2 [3].

2.1.1 Data management layer

Effective management of data throughout its life cycle is crucial for organisations, as data is akin to an asset. Data management (DM) encompasses a range of processes involved in the planning, specifying, enabling, creating, acquiring, maintaining, using, controlling, and purging data [3]. This layer consists of several steps (see Figure 2):

- *Planning*: determines the activities to be performed during the entire data life cycle. The outcome is a comprehensive data management plan (DMP) that outlines policies, processes and procedures (P3) governing data handling. It defines roles, responsibilities, and access rights, serving as the foundation for data flows in projects involving multiple entities [33].

Fig. 1 The Data Lifecycle

- *Collection*: involves gathering relevant data from various sources, such as social media, IoT devices, surveys, medical records, satellite observations, and statistics. Data may exist in structured, unstructured and semi-structured formats.
- *Pre-processing*: encompasses the integration, filtering and enrichment of data to obtain datasets that reduce complexity in DP. Integration consolidates all data into a unified structure, ensuring coherence and homogeneity. Filtering identifies incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate, or irrelevant data, which are then replaced, modified, or removed. Enrichment involves enhancing collected raw data with relevant contextual information obtained from additional sources.
- *Analysis*: encompasses inspecting, transforming, and modelling data to extract knowledge and valuable insights from raw or pre-processed data. Various data analysis techniques are employed to understand what is happening (descriptive analytics),

Fig. 2 Data Management layer (re-worked from Sha et al. [32])

why something is happening (diagnostic reasoning), and what is most likely to happen (predictive analytics). These techniques include data mining [34], clustering [35] [36], classification [37], and regression [38].

- *Visualization*: focuses on representing analysis results through charts, infographics, and animations. Visual displays effectively communicate complex data relationships and explain the meaning of the retrieved information in a user-friendly manner. There are three main categories of data visualisations: exploratory, explicatory, and explanatory visualization, catering to different purposes and data volumes. Examples include dashboards, reports, and oral presentations.
- *Storage*: aims to securely save the data and ensure its availability throughout the entire data life cycle. Data availability emphasizes that data can be accessed or downloaded by data consumers at any time. Data Lakes, utilising tools like NoSQL, NewSQL, Big Data Query platforms, Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), and cloud storage technologies, serve as repository for ingesting and querying raw data from different sources and formats.

- *Access*: provides a communication system and implements access control policies between data providers and data consumers. It regulates, monitors, and documents the actors involved, mechanisms used, and duration of access [39].
- *Share/publish*: involves distributing and transferring data through information systems, data catalogues, websites, social networks, and other platforms. Sharing and publication of data can be beneficial for researchers, companies, governments, and citizens.
- *Re-use*: encompasses two activities: data and information re-use by data consumers, and collecting feedback from data consumers to improve published data.
- *Archive*: involves cataloguing, indexing, and related actions based on specific parameters or business rules. It maintains records of obsolete data that are eventually destroyed, removed from the system, or no longer required.

2.1.2 Data governance layer

Data governance (DG) plays an important role in DP, by establishing a system of P3, assets, and infrastructures to maximize the value of data and its use. This layer includes nine tasks (see Figure 3):

- *Data architecture*: involves the collection of design documents at different levels of abstraction, encompassing principles governing data collection, storage, analysis, and storage within the organisation's systems. The outcome is the enterprise data model, which includes data assets, metadata definitions, entities and their relations, and business rules.
- *Data modelling*: includes identifying, analysing, and scoping data requirements, and then representing and communicating them in a standardised form known as data model. Each model contains of elements such as entities, relationships, facts, keys, and attributes. Different schemes including relational, dimensional, object-oriented, fact-based, and NoSQL, are employed.
- *Data operations*: encompasses the design, implementation, and support of stored data to maximise its value throughout the entire lifecycle. It includes operational support, focusing on monitoring and fine-tuning data storage activities from initial implementation to data acquisition, backup, and retrieval. Technical support focuses on specifying technical requirements for defining the technical architecture, deploying and administering relevant technology, and resolving any potential issues.
- *Data security*: involves defining, developing, and implementing security and data protection policies and procedures to ensure proper authentication, authorization, access control, privacy, and confidentiality. Data confidentiality safeguards against unauthorized access, while privacy ensures that personal data, such as identity, location, and other sensitive information remain confidential and protected from misuse and malicious purposes [40].
- *Data integration and interoperability*: deals with the movement and consolidation of data within and between data stores, applications, and organisations. Integration ensures data is consolidated into consistent forms, while interoperability enables multiple systems to communicate with each other.

Fig. 3 Data Governance layer (re-worked from DMBok2 [3])

- *Document and content management*: involves controlling and monitoring the acquisition, storage, access, and use of data and documents in any form or medium, particularly unstructured and semi-unstructured information.
- *Data warehousing and business intelligence*: encompasses planning, implementation, and control activities to provide evidence-based decision support and a knowledge base for the reporting, querying, and analysis by relevant stakeholders.
- *Metadata*: aids organisations in better understand their data, systems, and workflows. It contributes to data processing, maintenance, integration, security, auditing, and governance. Metadata includes information about technical and business processes, rules, constraints, and data assets (e.g., databases, data elements, data models), concepts (e.g., application systems, software code, technology infrastructure), and connections (relationships) between the data and concepts.

- *Data quality*: involves managing data through its life cycle by defining standards and measuring data against those standards to ensure its fitness for use by data consumers. Data quality assessment includes accuracy, accessibility, completeness for the intended purpose, and interpretability [41] [42].

2.2 Collaborative vs Decentralised

When multiple infrastructures and services are interconnected to perform various stages of the DM, it forms a distributed data management (DDM) ecosystem [43]. Similarly, when multiple entities, situated in different teams or organisations, participate in the decision-making and DG, it is referred to as decentralized data governance (DDG) [44]. The combination of DDG with DDM leads to collaborative data processing (CoDP). CoDP represents a community-based approach to managing, leveraging, and sharing data, in contrast to centralized data processing (CDP), where a single entity governs the decision-making throughout the data life cycle. The adoption of CoDP and CDP is determined by the specific DP context, enabling organisations to establish a flexible DGF [45].

A centralised approach to DG offers benefits in terms of streamlined coordination between entities, efficient communication, and the ability to monitor information integrity and project progress over time [46]. However, a centralized architecture may face limitations in terms of scalability, such as constrained storage, bandwidth, computing power, energy consumption, and security capabilities, making it inadequate for handling large volumes of data [47]. Moreover, a centralized architecture is susceptible to reliability issues since it represents a single point of failure. In the event of failure, the entire infrastructure becomes compromised [48]. Consequently, organisations are increasingly considering CoDP as it enables unification, cooperation, and healthy competition among entities, addressing the shortcoming of the centralised approach.

In response to the limitations of CDP, CoDP has emerged as a viable solution [49]. It involves the active participation and interaction of both humans and computer systems [8]. This approach leverages the combination and filtering of data from various systems to enrich knowledge [50], reduce storage costs, and enhance security [51]. By utilizing multiple systems working together, CoDP addresses the capacity, reliability, and trust issues associated with a single system [52]. Achieving this requires a combination of collaborative tools and distributed systems, enabling a decentralised approach to DP where a diverse range of individuals or groups within and beyond an organization can participate. Two key concepts arise from CoDP: decentralization and distribution. Distribution pertains to the physical infrastructure of a system, consisting of autonomous processing entities interconnected through a computer network, collaborating to achieve shared objectives [51]. It also involves the distribution of datasets across multiple sites in a partial or complete way [43]. In the context of DP, distribution focuses on DM, while decentralization pertains to DG and decision making, involving multiple entities overseeing the overall ecosystem.

An example of CoDP can be found in the work of Bin Liu et al., who proposed distributed DP systems for e-business [53]. Their solution utilises a distributed DGF and multiple systems for data collection and mining. By employing a multi-agent model in diverse data environments, the model facilitates distributed DP and consolidates the

outputs. This approach reduces network traffic, enhance security, and addresses data privacy concerns [8]. Additionally, Abreha et al. introduced the concept of federated learning (FL) in an edge computing environment. FL encourages privacy-preservation collaboration among data producers, eliminating the need to combine data that may contain personal or confidential information [54]. While distributed systems share some similarities with federated systems, the key distinction lies in their objectives. Federated systems aim to provide a unified, integrated view of distributed data (e.g., a virtual database), whereas distributed systems focus on facilitating common access to distributed data (e.g., a distributed file system with built-in DM capabilities) [55]. FL mitigates data communication costs and resolves issues related to bandwidth limitations, privacy, and legal considerations. However, employing a DDG approach raises concerns regarding trust, as the self-interest of an entity processing the data may conflict with the overall benefit of other entities [56]. Furthermore, the reliability of the assets used for DP and the quality of the results must be continuously monitored.

2.3 Reliability and trust

Within the field of DP, two critical challenges stand out: reliability and trust. Although these concepts are closely interconnected, they possess distinct characteristics. Reliability is an objective measure that pertain the physical infrastructure of a system, encompassing hardware, firmware, and software. Trust, on the other hand, is subjective and resolves around resource sharing, decision-making, and a specific purpose [57]. Moreover, reliability is a context-based property of a system that correlates its operation and goals or expected behaviors. Generally, it is assessed through a set of criteria and dimensions, such as probability, intended functions, time dependence, specific conditions, performance scalability, fault prevention, fault [58]. Trust, in contrast, is a psychological condition characterised by the willingness to embrace vulnerability based upon positive anticipations regarding the intentions or actions of another entity [59]. Furthermore, in the realm of DP, Anhalt-Depies et al assert that trust plays a pivotal role in cultivating the social cohesion necessary for collaboration as well as for conflict resolution and negotiation [60].

The emergence of CoDP has brought about a shift in how these concepts are approached. Previously, centralised third parties were relied upon for any form of exchange between entities. Now, there have been a paradigm swift towards distributed systems with DDG, leading to discussions on distributed reliability and decentralized trust.

Reliability refers to the probability that a system, including hardware, firmware, and software components, will successfully perform its intended tasks within specified conditions and time frame [61]. Distributed reliability extends this concept to distributed systems. Akimova et al. defines reliability of distributed systems as a property enabling the preservation over time of the defined parameters required to fulfill the main function under the influence of malfunctions (failures and breakdowns) of hardware, software and data errors, human mistakes in standard operational conditions, and working environment when maintenance and servicing parameters are specified [62]. In the context of CoDP, distributed reliability concerns every stage of the DM, the transitions between stages, and the ultimate objective of the DP. It ensures that

each phase of the DM process is carried out by multiple systems with fault tolerance, resulting in high-quality outputs.

Trust is the belief that a DG system possesses the willingness and capabilities to generate high-quality data outputs [63]. Decentralized trust extends this notion to DDG. Trust and reliability play a significant role in CoDP, and researchers strive to ensure the trustworthiness of DP outputs. Trust represents a challenge as data typically accept vulnerability arising from human behaviour (i.e., the trustee), rather than machines [64]. However, establishing the overall reliability of distributed systems during DP is crucial to instil trust among data consumers in the results obtained through DP. Hence, reliability is regarded as an indicator of trust.

2.4 The role of blockchain

Blockchain has recently emerged as a disruptive innovation with a wide range of applications, able to redesign interactions in business activities and society at large [65]. It consists of a permanent, distributed, digital ledger, recording transactions across a peer-to-peer network [66]. Unlike other peer-to-peer networks, a blockchain does not duplicate the value being transferred. Instead, it functions as a register, noting that a value has been successfully transferred from one entity to another. This technology introduces a groundbreaking innovation by enabling an open network where participants can interact without prior knowledge or trust in each other. Transactions are automatically verified and recorded by network nodes using cryptographic algorithms, eliminating the need for human intervention, central authority, or third-party intermediaries such as governments, financial institutions, or other organizations. Even in the presence of unreliable, dishonest, or malicious nodes, the network can accurately verify transactions and safeguard the integrity of the ledger. This is achieved through a mathematical mechanism known as proof-of-work, rendering human intervention or centralized control unnecessary. The underlying principle behind this protocol is decentralized trust or trust-by-computation.

The blockchain serves as an immutable and transparent repository for storing records of documents, contracts, properties, and assets. It offers a versatile platform for embedding information and instructions, resulting in a wide array of applications. These include, for instance: a) smart contracts, namely automated and self-executing agreements between two or more entities. By leveraging blockchain technology, smart contracts enable seamless execution of predefined actions, eliminating the reliance on intermediaries; b) multi-signature transactions, which require the consensus and approval of multiple entities before they can be executed. The blockchain facilitates this by providing a trustless framework that ensures the involvement and agreement of all relevant parties; and c) smart properties, namely digital ownership of tangible and intangible assets embedded to the blockchain, which can be owned, tracked or exchanged. This concept offers enhanced security, traceability, and efficiency by leveraging the blockchain's capabilities.

When it comes to governance, the most significant innovation of blockchain is that it provides the ability to experiment with new organizational structures and distributed governance models, which are more transparent and less hierarchical than

traditional ones. Indeed, blockchain allows the creation of so-called decentralized organizations, enabling entities and actors to coordinate themselves in a peer-to-peer manner, according to a set of protocols and rules incorporated into self-executing smart contract code [67]. Nevertheless, a comprehensive assessment considering multiple factors is currently lacking to determine the viability of a blockchain-based governance model in meeting the necessary legal, security, ethical and technical requirements [68].

The above described aspects serves as fundamental pillars for establishing an effective and scalable DG system, and have been used as a basis in drafting our proposed DGaaS framework.

3 The Data Governance as a Service

We present a DGaaS framework, depicted in Figure 4, which adopts a concentric circles structure, with people, process, and technology at its core. Moving outward, we emphasise the importance of security and privacy on one side, and ethical, legal and regulatory compliance on the other. These are combined with a blockchain-enabled transactions tracking mechanism, ensuring transparency throughout the system. The subsequent circle encompasses a series of collaborative actions, including data architecture and data modelling. The outermost ring contains areas where DG plays a critical role, such as metadata management and business intelligence (as detailed in sub-section 2.1.2).

The proposed framework follows a bottom-up approach, empowering and providing support to data consumers (individuals or teams). It is flexible and adaptable to the needs of the different sectors and stakeholders, and aims at increasing the value of data and minimize DP-related costs and risks. While security and privacy remain paramount as in a centralised approach, top management remains responsible for resources allocation and communicating the overall strategy. Governance bodies still maintain their relevance, but P3 are implemented as close to the point of the data usage as possible, ensuring maximum value extraction.

Overall, the proposed framework introduces three main novel components (as illustrated in the second circle) in order to address the organisation’s technical, business and operational requirements:

a) Security, Privacy, and Access Control module

We propose the adoption of a privacy-preserving user-centric federated identity management approach based on a trusted execution environment (TEE). The TEE is located between the identity providers and service providers. An identity provider can store some of the user’s attributes in the TEE. Information that is endorsed by identity provider can then be accessed by service providers. The latter use the information to provide fine-grained access control and offer personalized services. Prior to user authentication, the service provider has to authenticate to the TEE and prove that it is authorized to access certain personal attributes. The TEE verifies the acceptability of the service provider’s information request. This verification ensures that only information from identity providers is queried, for which the identity providers (or their representative) gave their consent. The authorization information is included in the

Fig. 4 Data Governance as a Service (DGaaS) framework

certificate (or credential) of the service provider. Additionally, the user may further restrict access to personal information through a policy or an explicit consent. If the query is acceptable, the TEE forwards this request to the identity provider(s) that can provide the information.

b) Blockchain-based Transactions Tracking module

A novel blockchain-based information exchange system with built-in smart contracts for decentralised, scalable, and interoperable data processing and governance. This will ensure the tamper-proof, decentralised logging, auditing, and tracking of actions leading to traceability and non-repudiation. Moreover, the blockchain mechanisms will allow for logging, auditing and tracking of the transactional data activities (e.g., data submission, sharing, access) between the involved entities and stakeholders in a holistic manner that preserves confidentiality and data access permissions. The impact of such solution will be tangible via specific privacy metrics, including i) attack surface exposed to untrusted software, ii) amount of the trusted computing base used by security tools in terms of source lines of code (SLOC), and iii) number of access points to the TET.

Fig. 5 Data Stewardship

c) Ethical, Legal and Regulatory Compliance module

The DGaaS builds on top of the principles, protocols and recommendations outlined in the GDPR, the Data Act (DA), the Data Governance Act (DGA), the AI Act (AIA), but also ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI developed by the High-Level Expert Group. It seeks to analyse, predict, quantify, and monitor transparency, accountability and trustworthiness of DP activities using AI and Big Data, considering individual rights to ensure meaningful redress for people affected by these technologies.

3.1 Data stewardship

To foster trust in the system and promote widespread adoption, it is crucial to implement specialised data stewardship (see Figure 5) practices. The DMBok2 describes data stewardship as accountability and responsibility for data and processes that ensure effective control and use of data assets to help an organization get value from its data [3]. These practices ensure that data collection, usage, and sharing adhere to fundamental principles outlined in the GDPR such as notice and consent, purpose limitation, data minimization, retention restrictions and usage limitations. By mandating these measures, organizations can demonstrate their commitment to responsible data handling, which in turn enhances trust among stakeholders and encourages broader acceptance of the system.

DGaaS is a powerful and transformative process that relies heavily on the collaborative efforts from various stakeholders. To effectively implement it, organizations must establish an *agile governance model*, encompassing Strategy, Organization, Directives,

Measurement, and Change Management [69]. Here is an enhanced breakdown of each component:

- *Strategy*: The Data Strategy establishes a clear alignment between the organization's goals, objectives, and desired values to be accomplished. It provides a roadmap for leveraging data effectively.
- *Organization*: entails defining the roles, responsibilities, and accountabilities necessary for executing the Data Strategy. It clarifies the involvement of different stakeholders, articulates their motivations, and sets clear expectations upon them.
- *Directives*: encompasses the P3 that support and align with the organization's Data Strategy. They ensure that these P3 are effectively implemented and that the work conducted adds tangible value.
- *Measurement*: involves assessing the impact and value generated by the DG program. It incorporates both qualitative and quantitative metrics to gain a better understanding of the economic, social and environmental returns. These metrics allow organizations to gauge the effectiveness of their DG practices and make data-driven decisions for continuous improvement.
- *Change Management*: focuses on the effective communication, comprehensive training, and seamless integration to embed DG practices within the organization's culture and workflows. It aims to foster awareness, understanding, and adoption of DG practices to support the organization in advancing its mission and driving meaningful change.

By embracing the DGaaS framework and effectively implementing these steps, organizations can navigate the journey of DG, fostering collaboration, maximizing value creation, and ultimately unlocking the full potential of their data assets.

3.2 Implementing DGaaS

When initiating a DG program, organizations face several challenges that need to be addressed for its successful implementation. Here are some key challenges associated with DGaaS:

- *Change management and adoption*: persuading business stakeholders to accept implementing a DG program can be a significant obstacle. It requires organisational change management efforts that usually involves training, education, and promoting a cultural shift towards DG practices. Stakeholder engagement and effective communication strategies are crucial for driving adoption and achieving the desired outcomes.
- *Financing*: securing necessary funds can be problematic as it may require determining funding levels for tools, addressing resource and compensation constraints, and understanding how to deliver tangible value. While traditional costs associated with data, such as storage expenses, are relatively quantifiable, assessing its value to the organisation proves more complex. It is essential to recognise that data itself holds no intrinsic value, and individuals or organisations treating it as an abstract object may overlook its true worth. DG systems often come with substantial costs

and present complex integration and operational activities [70]. Moreover, its financing could often be susceptible to annual variations, making it more challenging to adequately plan compared to a continuous funding stream.

- *Resource and time constraints*: Data governance and stewardship activities, such as data collection and definition of data assets, are resources and time-consuming, despite the ability of tools to learn data structure and format directly from database structures. Moreover, many organizations nowadays operate in hybrid environments, incorporating both on-premises and cloud-based infrastructures. DGaaS must offer solutions that effectively govern data across multiple platforms and infrastructures, providing consistent governance practices, data policies, and compliance measures.
- *Learning curve, skills and commitment*: Acquiring the necessary skills and the learning curve associated with DG tools pose time investments and may hinder business adoption, presenting serious commitment challenges.
- *Establishing business priorities*: Defining a DG framework, setting priorities, determining ROI, establishing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and establishing metadata loading templates and processes can be daunting as a first-time exercise.

The concept of DGaaS offers hope for organizations lacking the momentum, size or buy-in required to initiate an organic DG organization. By overcoming these challenges, organizations can unlock the full potential of DGaaS and realize its benefits in terms of improved data management, enhanced decision-making, and compliance with regulatory requirements.

3.3 DGaaS key benefits

DGaaS fundamentally changes the approach of assessing the cost of DG, shifting the focus from “How much does DG cost?” to “How much should our organization invest in DG?”. By adopting DGaaS, organisations can distribute the implementation and program progress risk through the expertise provided across the whole data life cycle, ranging from strategy development to implementation and ongoing data stewardship. Unlike in-house staffing, DGaaS offers a flexible support structure that can be adopted to project needs, timelines, and requirements.

During the initial set-up and metadata capture phase, projects typically require higher data stewardship resources. However, the ongoing project demands decrease significantly. DGaaS facilitates staffing flexibility by combining onshore and offshore resources and services. This flexible staffing approach not only enhances cost-effectiveness, but also enables the provision of timely solutions by leveraging round-the-clock stewardship capabilities.

DGaaS delivers core stewardship services at an optimal cost, allowing organisations to allocate their internal staff to higher-value tasks. DGaaS can enhance the effectiveness of DG programs while only investing a fraction of a total program cost.

4 Expected impacts

The DGaaS can be offered to several stakeholders and more specifically to: i) private organisations for planning, designing and implementing data-driven solutions to align

their vision and business objectives with their customers' needs; ii) public organizations for organizing, planning, and monitoring the timely provision of appropriate and enhanced policies leading to efficient decision-making; and (iii) researchers involved in data processing activities, to facilitate data discovery, interoperability and use.

Moreover, DGaaS can boost the ability of public and private organisations to exploit and monetize their data assets [71], while at the same time developing novel services or enhancing the existing ones. It will open opportunities stemming from access to and consumption of data in an open, decentralized, blockchain-based environment instead of the current centralized and siloed models and solutions [20].

Below we present a summary on the possible applicability of DG in the smart city and eHealth sectors

4.1 DG in smart cities

A smart city is a dynamic ecosystem that utilizes IoT devices, sensors, networks and applications generate benefits for the communities and organisations involved. Its fundamental principle is to foster responsibility, sustainability, and inclusivity. To achieve these objectives, it is essential to establish an efficient DGF that enables public administrations to transform data into valuable information for local businesses, improve the citizens' quality of life (including improved access and participation), and effectively respond to environmental challenges.

In line with the recommendations of Eke and Ebohon, the DGF for smart cities should prioritise three key areas: people (with particular emphasis on privacy, confidentiality, and data protections concerns), businesses (ensuring efficiency gains and economic optimization), and the environment (enhancing factors like air quality and reducing emissions) [72]. Therefore, cities must establish a robust DGF that incorporates the following elements: accurate and unbiased data (eliminating representation bias, measurement bias, evaluation bias, aggregation bias, population bias, sampling bias, or data linking bias), accountable, explainable, and fair algorithms, a diverse and knowledgeable workforce to adequately address inclusion issues effectively, and the policies/standards to build trust, transparency, accountability and responsibility).

According to Choenni et al., the DGF in smart cities should not only focus on improving the quality of data to support the desired impacts of smart city applications, but also on mitigating the undesired impacts from these applications, and/or of the collected sensitive (personal or business) data [42]. By containing these undesired impacts, stakeholders' trust can be strengthened, ultimately promoting the growth of smart cities.

Franke and Gailhofer emphasise the importance of DG for promoting sustainability in the smart cities. They propose a socio-ecological approach that systematically identifies and assesses various regulatory strategies [73]. This regulatory function plays a crucial role in aligning the decision parameters and objectives of AI-enabled services with sustainability goals in smart cities. The regulation of data access and usage is essential for several reasons:

- Effective decision-making in the smart city requires an adequate dataset. Given the complex socio-ecological challenges, effective governance and planning require

a robust knowledge base to successfully implement sustainability objectives. The public authorities' ability to steer "smart" innovations in the collective interest and to update and enforce regulatory standards relies on sufficient access to data.

- Access to high-quality data is crucial for enabling and promoting sustainable solutions. Sustainable innovations and applications often rely on such data to unleash their full potential. Policies aimed at fostering sustainability greatly depend on the availability of reliable data.
- Data concentration in the hands of a few private corporations poses sustainability concerns. Private data silos can impede access to valuable data, creating barriers to innovation. Furthermore, the superior data processing capabilities and economies of scale enjoyed by these companies can further enhance their technological advantage, even if equal access to their data were provided.
- Effectively regulating the social and ecological risks associated with AI-based systems requires access to the processed dataset. Merely examining the code is insufficient to comprehend how a process operates. AI systems frequently learn and update their objectives based on data feedback to adapt to changing conditions. Therefore, access to the processed dataset is essential for comprehending and managing the risks posed by AI systems.

In summary, regulating data access and usage is crucial for facilitating informed decision-making, promoting sustainable solutions, addressing data concentration issues, and effectively managing the risks associated with AI-based systems in smart cities.

Furthermore, Johnson et al examine the inherent tensions that exist between optimized regulation to drive innovation and regulation aimed at safeguarding public interest and individual rights [74]. In light of this, they have put forth several principles that should be taken into account when designing an effective DGF for smart cities:

- Balancing government involvement and privatization: Finding the right equilibrium between government intervention and private sector participation is crucial. The DGF should strike a balance that allows for innovation and private sector contributions while ensuring adequate public oversight and control.
- Considering law enforcement objectives in relation to surveillance concerns: The DGF should carefully consider the goals of law enforcement while addressing potential privacy and surveillance-related concerns. It is important to strike a balance that upholds public safety without infringing upon individuals' rights to privacy.
- Defining the scope and purpose of the data: Clearly defining the scope and purpose of the data collected and processed within the DGF is essential. This ensures that data collection efforts align with specific objectives, avoid unnecessary invasions of privacy, and promote responsible and ethical use of data.
- Interacting with local laws and regulations: The DGF should be designed in a manner that takes into account local laws and regulations. It should harmonize with existing legal frameworks, ensuring compliance and avoiding conflicts or inconsistencies.

- **Garnering public trust through transparency and accountability:** Establishing trust among the public is crucial for the success of the DGF. Transparency and accountability should be core principles, enabling citizens to understand how their data is being used, ensuring clear accountability mechanisms are in place, and fostering public confidence in the governance of data in smart cities.

In summary, Johnson et al. highlight the need to address the tensions between regulatory optimization and the protection of public interest and individual rights. Their proposed principles emphasize the importance of balancing government and private sector involvement, considering law enforcement objectives while safeguarding privacy, defining data scope and purpose, adhering to local laws, and fostering transparency and accountability to build public trust in the DGF for smart cities.

4.2 DG in healthcare and medical research

In the EU, the effort to establish a universal, high-level DG scheme has begun. The European Health Data Space (EHDS) [21] is expected not only to support individuals in their sensitive data control but also improve the performance of organizations that carry out the research, policy making and treatment associated with healthcare. The EHDS in conjunction with the DGA [23] provides a horizontal framework for DG [75]. However, for the implementation of such a large-scale drastic change in the healthcare field, technical and organizational instruments are required, to enable the seamless transition to a digitized healthcare characterized by efficiency and transparency.

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, DG in healthcare is being revolutionized. However, we empathize that many of these changes lack granularity, failing to address all needs of the data economy equally. One example is the negligence of socio-economic status, suggesting that a more individualized approach is required, specific to the service [76]. Similarly, the World Health Organization (WHO) has pushed forth the empowerment through digital health initiative, aiming to improve European healthcare systems and among others, provide a solid European framework for DG in compliance with GDPR values. The DGA is expected to drastically affect healthcare delivery in Europe through improving personalized treatments, treating rare and chronic diseases, and is expected to save the EU health sector 120 billion euros a year [77].

Large scale initiatives are necessary for the transformation of healthcare sector and efficient DG has already revolutionized healthcare research, treatment and general services. Some cases from the US are great examples to support it. For instance, the National Cardiovascular Data Registry has utilized DG to track patient outcomes and optimize their therapy, hence improving care by informing the relevant healthcare providers [78]. Mayo clinic utilizes DG to develop novel healthcare models and improve treatment for its patients [79]. The DM process at Mayo Clinic is considered being transformative in both research and healthcare. A data ecosystem characterized by robust DG, can provide not only higher scientific standards and robustness of research, but also trust, security, privacy, confidentiality and coordination between different healthcare providers [80]. In order for such initiatives to be implemented however, we suggest that DGaaS can accelerate this progress and provide the means for a successful

transition. These frameworks can be used as guidelines to generate the organizational and technical measures necessary to cover more specific needs and represent all the subgroups of individuals.

DG is an essential tool in the facilitation of health-related research and services. While European legislation seems to be moving in the right direction, we believe DGaaS as a practical tool for DG optimization, can improve the effectiveness of healthcare through structured and robust DG modelling.

5 Conclusion

The paper investigates whether effective data processing can be achieved without formal data governance. First, it emphasised the challenges posed by current systems both from technological and legal perspective. Second, it provided an overview of the state-of-the-art solutions and emerging technologies aiming to evaluate existing approaches on data processing and governance and to investigate their limitations. We elaborated on these technologies with a special focus on decentralisation, reliability and trust. Next, we presented an innovative framework, called Data Governance as a Service (DGaaS), providing a clear and structured description of the defined elements, processes and relationships. This paper underscores the importance of DGaaS together with principles, processes and procedures (P3) for managing data effectively throughout the entire lifecycle. The DGaaS also enables collaboration from various levels of the organizations and it also provides the ability to align various data related programs with business objectives. Finally, we concluded with some useful insights into data governance initiatives in the smart city and healthcare sector by highlighting the importance of robust data governance frameworks, privacy, transparency, accountability considerations, and the need to balance innovation and public interest.

CRedit statement

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